

EARTH EXPLORER 12 CANDIDATE MISSION KEYSTONE REPORT FOR MISSION ASSESSMENT

Reference	ESA-EOPSM-KEYS-RP-5026
Issue/Revision	1.0
Date of Issue	12/06/2026
Status	Issued

Recommended citation:

ESA (2026). Report for Mission Assessment: Earth Explorer 12 Candidate Mission Keystone
European Space Agency, Noordwijk, The Netherlands, ESA-EOPSM-KEYS-RP-5026, 142 pp.
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20543287

Cover image design: Earth Observation Graphics Bureau (EOGB)

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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Special thanks are expressed to the industrial consortium led by OHB System AG (Germany), acting as payload prime, and comprising key partners including German Aerospace Centre – DLR e.V. (Germany), RAL Space (United Kingdom), OIP Sensor Systems N.V. (Belgium), and Deimos S.L. – an Indra Group Company (Spain). Further valuable contributions were provided by entities such as Thomas Keating Ltd. (United Kingdom), LIRA (France), CNRS – Observatoire de Paris EPST (France), and others. Acknowledgement is also given to the End-to-End Performance Simulator consortium led by GMV Aerospace and Defense SAU (Spain) for their support in assisting ESA in the preparation of this report.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Keystone mission would explore the Mesosphere-Thermosphere System (MTS) between 50 and 250 km of altitude, which encompasses the Earth's mesosphere, thermosphere, and the overlapping D- and E-regions of the ionosphere. The MTS is the least directly observed region of Earth's atmosphere, yet it governs the exchange of composition, energy and momentum between the lower atmosphere and near-Earth space. This knowledge gap limits the ability to assess key processes including satellite drag, space weather impacts, and upper-atmosphere climate change.

The MTS is a transition region driven by both terrestrial and solar influences. Keystone would provide critical insights into how MTS composition and dynamics respond to these influences, improving whole-atmosphere understanding. Beyond this fundamental science value, Keystone would also deliver practical socio-economic benefits, including: improved modelling of satellite drag and orbital decay, to support mitigation solutions for satellites operations (such as collision avoidance); assessing the atmospheric impacts of spacecraft re-entry; better assessment of climate forcing by quantifying upper-atmosphere cooling; and improved physical understanding of ion-neutral coupling processes relevant to enable space weather resilience strategies for communications and navigation. Keystone would address this gap by providing simultaneous limb observations of the key MTS state variables, enabling a step change in whole-atmosphere modelling and prediction. Keystone would provide a wealth of data relating to the physics and chemistry of this interfacial region where the atmosphere transitions from the dense neutral regime of the lower atmosphere to the electrodynamically driven environment of near-Earth space.

Atomic oxygen (O), produced from the photodissociation of molecular oxygen (O₂), is the major reservoir of chemical potential energy in the MTS: between 80 and 120 km, the chemical heating rate from exothermic chemical reactions involving O significantly exceeds direct heating from solar radiation. With a lifetime greater than a day, O transports chemical potential energy within the MTS (vertically and horizontally). This leads to heating in the polar night, even in the absence of solar radiation, and to a significant energy flux from the thermosphere into the mesosphere. Moreover, many reactions involving O lead to chemical products in excited states which emit light; these chemiluminescent reactions are an important energy loss process in the MTS (e.g. the recombination of O with NO is critical for thermal recovery of the thermosphere after geomagnetic storms).

Keystone would provide the first direct observations of O across the MTS, on a global and continuous basis. This would allow closure of the global MTS energy and chemical budgets, which currently cannot be achieved from indirect observations.

Although O is the most important atmospheric constituent in the MTS, controlling nearly all chemistry and playing a major role in thermal balance and dynamics, its concentration has only ever been inferred indirectly by observing emissions from various product species of exothermic reactions. Keystone would observe O directly by exploiting the very low energy spin-orbit transitions of the ground state of O, which occur in the Terahertz (THz) region of the electromagnetic spectrum.

The mission has three science goals: 1) to characterise the density, composition, chemistry and thermal balance of the MTS, by pioneering observations of O, together with key trace gases, thermal heat loss, and airglow; 2) to study and assess coupling on multiple scales in the middle and upper atmosphere, including large-scale atmospheric waves, space weather effects, and MTS inter-hemispheric coupling; and hence 3) to improve the representation, prediction and projection of the chemistry-climate system in next-generation whole-atmosphere models, with applications for climate forcing, resilience of space infrastructure to space weather impacts on orbital parameters and communication, satellite drag forecasting, and spacecraft re-entry.

The first mission objective would be to observe vertical profiles of O and a wide range of important trace gases including O₃, H₂O, CO₂, CO, NO, and OH, as well as metallic atoms and ions, and the properties of noctilucent clouds. The trace gases are necessary to determine the density, thermal balance and photochemistry in the MTS. Metallic ions are key constituents of the sporadic E-layers which affect radio communications and navigation systems. The second mission objective would be to observe coincident InfraRed (IR) and UV-Visible (UV-Vis) emissions, vital for constraining radiative energy balance and validating models of the MTS. The third objective would be to retrieve kinetic temperature profiles from THz, IR, and UV emissions to characterise atmospheric structure and support dynamic analyses. The final mission objective would be to observe line-of-sight neutral wind profiles from Doppler shifts in THz emission lines to constrain constituent transport.

The Keystone mission is conceived as a single-satellite low Earth orbit mission with continuous limb viewing, where the atmospheric volume of interest is sampled through a combination of orbital motion and regular line-of-sight scanning. The mission is designed to operate as an observatory with stable and repeatable observation geometries, well-defined calibration opportunities and co-located measurements across instruments. A Sun-synchronous orbit provides the most favourable balance between global coverage, illumination stability, thermal control and operational simplicity.

Keystone would therefore be a limb-sounding observatory combining three co-registered instruments with a common vertical scanning approach. These instruments are: 1) a THz spectrometer operating between 1.1 and 2.1 THz, the first sensor of this kind deployed in space; 2) an IR instrument measuring broadband radiance profiles in a set of channels between 2 and 15 µm; and 3) a UV-Vis spectrometer operating between 240 and 800 nm.

Keystone would be of high importance to many international programmes devoted to climate change, space weather, and space infrastructure and its resilience, under governmental and non-governmental organisations, e.g. the World Meteorological Organization (WMO), the International Science Council (ISC) and the International Union of Geodesy and Geophysics (IUGG).

In summary, Keystone would deliver the first direct, global observations of atomic oxygen together with co-located observations of composition, temperature and line-of-sight winds, enabling closure of energy and chemical budgets in the MTS. This would provide a new, observation-constrained basis for modelling the coupled atmosphere-space system, with many socio-economic benefits.

Table of Contents

Acknowledgements	3
Executive Summary	4
1. Introduction	8
1.1. Earth Explorer 12 Candidates	8
1.2. The Keystone Mission	10
2. Scientific Background and Justification	11
2.1. The Mesosphere-Thermosphere System and its Transition to the Space Environment.....	12
2.2. The Role of Atomic Oxygen in the Chemistry and Energy Balance of the Upper Atmosphere ...	16
2.3. Thermospheric Density and Drag	17
2.4. Processes Knowledge Gaps	19
3. Science Goals and Mission Objectives	22
3.1. Scientific Motivation	22
3.2. Science Goals	24
3.3. Tracing Science Goals to the ESA EO Science Strategy	24
3.4. Mission Objectives	25
3.5. Tracing of Science Goals to Mission Objectives	26
3.6. Evolution With Respect to the EE12 Proposal	26
4. Mission Requirements	28
4.1. Observables	28
4.2. Resolution and Sampling	29
4.3. Coverage and Mission Lifetime	34
4.4. Measurements	35
5. Data Products and Usage	41
5.1. Data Products	41
5.2. Data Processing Schemes	41
5.3. Data Usage	45
5.4. User Communities	52
6. Scientific Feasibility	54
6.1. Geophysical Scenarios	54
6.2. Sensitivity Assessment	55
6.3. Campaign Activities	72
7. Preliminary Mission Concept and Performance	74
7.1. Mission Concept	74
7.2. Satellite & Platform Design	79
7.3. Payload	84
7.4. Performance	94
8. Synergies and Complementarities	100
8.1. Synergies with Ground-based Observations	100
8.2. Synergies with Current and Planned Satellite Missions	103

8.3. Long-term Continuity with Heritage Datasets 105

8.4. Calibration, Stability and Interpretation Support 105

8.5. Scientific and Operational Added Value 106

References 108

Acronyms 123

Appendix A. Science Readiness Assessment 129

A.1. SRL 4 Guiding Questions 129

A.2. Roadmap to SRL 5 132

A.3. End-to-End Performance Simulator 132

Appendix B. Relevance to Evaluation Criteria 134

B.1. Criterion 1 - Relevance to the ESA EO Science Strategy 134

B.2. Criterion 2 - Scientific Merit, Uniqueness, Impact and Value 134

B.3. Criterion 3 - Scientific Feasibility and Maturity 137

B.4. Criterion 4 - Technical Merit, Maturity and Risk 138

B.5. Criterion 5 - Programmatic 139

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Earth Explorer 12 Candidates

ESA research missions drive the Earth science agenda, technological innovation in Earth observation capabilities, and future application perspectives within the Future Earth Observation (FutureEO) Programme. Earth Explorer missions focus on the atmosphere, biosphere, hydrosphere, cryosphere, and the Earth's interior, with particular emphasis on the interactions between these components and the impact of human activities on Earth system processes.

ESA's Earth Observation Science Strategy (ESA (2024)) provides the solid scientific foundation and direction for future progress and implementation decisions within the ESA Earth Observation Programme. It identifies the scientific challenges and knowledge gaps associated with six overarching science themes: the water cycle; carbon cycle and atmospheric chemistry; energy fluxes; ecosystem health; extremes and hazards; and interfaces and coupling within the Earth system. The strategy also defines Guiding Science Questions intended to shape future ESA Earth observation activities and missions through to 2040.

The Call for Earth Explorer 12 (EE12) Mission Ideas was released in February 2023, and four mission candidates were selected for a Phase 0 study out of 17 proposals in April 2024. The four candidate missions selected for assessment phase study activities are outlined hereafter:

CryoRad would target polar regions and their processes, namely the acceleration of ice sheet mass loss, the reduction of sea-ice thickness and the freshening of the Arctic Ocean. The mission would provide low-frequency passive microwave measurements from 0.4 to 2 GHz that allow the estimation of geophysical variables such as ice-sheet temperature profiles down to the bedrock.

ECO would resolve the global radiation budget. The mission would provide radiation measurements using a satellite constellation combining Sun and Earth radiometers, and wide-field visible and infrared imagers. It will enable the derivation of Earth's Energy Imbalance, a diagnostic variable for our climate.

Hydroterra+ would address rapid processes tied to the water cycle over land and to extreme events over Europe, the Mediterranean and northern Africa. The radar mission would be placed in geostationary orbit. From this fixed position above the equator, the satellite's C-band synthetic aperture radar would deliver data products multiple times a day.

Keystone would target the whole-atmosphere chemistry-climate system in the region from 50 km to 250 km. The mission would deliver measurements from a limb-sounding instrument across the Terahertz, infrared and UV-visible spectral range. It would deliver observations of atomic oxygen, other trace gases, temperature and wind.

The Reports for Mission Assessment capture the status of the respective mission idea at the end of Phase 0 activities. The four reports will be provided to the Advisory Committee for Earth Observation and, together with the mission presentations at the EE12 Phase 0 User Consultation Meeting, will form the basis for a subsequent recommendation of up to two mission candidates to enter Phase A.

Each report follows a common format and logic. Each identifies the scientific questions and related key societal issues motivating the mission and its objectives. After establishing the scientific basis and rationale, the specific mission objectives are outlined and traced to a set of requirements used for system concept definition.

Each report comprises this introductory first chapter and eight subsequent chapters as follows:

Chapter 2 identifies the background and scientific issues to be addressed by the mission. It provides justification for the mission and includes a review of the current scientific understanding of the issue in question while identifying the potential advances in knowledge that the mission could provide.

Chapter 3 draws on arguments presented in Chapter 2 and summarises specific scientific goals and related mission objectives.

Chapter 4 outlines the mission requirements, through providing quantitative descriptions and justification, including prioritisation, of the geophysical, observation and measurement requirements that would allow to fulfil the mission objectives.

Chapter 5 gives a qualitative description of the data products at Level 1 and Level 2, the operational data processing and how the data acquired by this mission would be used, and includes a description of the data user communities.

Chapter 6 briefly presents the retrieval approach, feasibility estimation with simulated and/or experimental data, and the validation concept.

Chapter 7 provides an overview of the preliminary mission architecture and the system elements, including the space segment, ground segment, and operations.

Chapter 8 describes the synergies and international context of the mission.

Appendix A documents the scientific readiness self-assessment.

Appendix B documents the relevance of the mission to the evaluation criteria.

1.2. The Keystone Mission

Keystone is an Earth Explorer candidate mission designed to investigate the Mesosphere–Thermosphere System (MTS), a key transition region of the atmosphere extending from approximately 50 to 250 km altitude, where the lower atmosphere interfaces with near-Earth space. This region plays a central role in controlling the exchange of energy, momentum, and composition across atmospheric layers, and is fundamental to understanding atmospheric coupling, space weather processes, and upper-atmosphere climate variability.

The mission is motivated by the limited observational knowledge of the MTS. The governing physical and chemical processes are not sufficiently well understood because observations are fragmented and the direct measurements of critical variables, notably atomic oxygen – the *keystone* of the MTS – are missing. Keystone addresses this gap by providing direct, global, and continuous observations of key MTS state variables, namely composition, temperature, winds and density, enabling a more complete and physically consistent description of this region.

Keystone is built around three Science Goals: the characterisation of MTS composition, chemistry, and thermal balance; the quantification of multi-scale coupling processes and variability; and the improvement of whole-atmosphere modelling and predictive capabilities. These goals are translated into Mission Objectives that define the required observations of composition, temperature, winds, and density, ensuring a coherent progression from scientific motivation to observational implementation.

The mission concept is based on a synergistic multi-instrument payload combining Terahertz (THz), Infrared (IR), and UltraViolet–Visible (UV–Vis) limb-sounding techniques. The THz instrument enables the direct observation of atomic oxygen and key drivers of energetics. The IR and UV-Vis instruments add indirect observations of trace gas profiles from thermal and airglow emissions, respectively, and together complete the picture of the thermal balance (radiative cooling) and photochemistry of the MTS. Together, these instruments provide co-located and vertically resolved observations, allowing simultaneous retrieval of key atmospheric variables.

Through this integrated observational approach, Keystone is designed to significantly advance the understanding of the MTS and its role within the coupled Earth system. Its observations contribute both to fundamental science and to applications such as improved prediction of satellite drag, assessment of space weather impacts, and better characterisation of upper-atmosphere climate processes.

2. SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND AND JUSTIFICATION

As humankind reaches out into space, it is becoming increasingly dependent on the revolutionary innovations that led to the current age of space technology. The modern world of the 2020s would not be possible without the current flotilla of Low Earth Orbit (LEO) satellites. Earth observation, numerical weather prediction, telecommunication, disaster monitoring, and security are among the ways in which satellites and satellite data have become a cornerstone of modern society. Lives and livelihoods depend on measurements and data transferred from space.

This progress is not uniform and steady. Today, with the advent of mega-constellations of small and micro-satellites, an explosion in the number of LEO satellites is occurring. Usable orbital paths are becoming more congested, collision avoidance manoeuvres are becoming more common, and the risk of a Kessler syndrome occurring is increasing. Debris from defunct spacecraft re-entering the atmosphere and burning up is predicted to become a significant contributor of chemically and radiatively active materials to the middle atmosphere, particularly since satellites are now “designed for demise” in the atmosphere to avoid striking populated areas. In spite of being significantly less dense than the lower atmosphere, all solar radiation passes through the middle atmosphere and any changes to its transmission characteristics will affect the weather and climate below.

Knowledge of the atmosphere and charged particle environment in the 50 to 250 km region (Mesosphere-Thermosphere System (MTS)) is in its early stages. The 50 km lower boundary is the maximum altitude that high-altitude balloons can reach, and the 250 km upper boundary approaches the lower limit of sustained satellite operations without continuous propulsion. Except for very sporadic rocket soundings, there is an absence of *direct* measurements in the MTS. The balances and processes that govern its state (especially above 100 km) remain poorly understood, and current theories and models are yet to be properly validated.

The development of an understanding of the MTS is further complicated by its extreme weather and seasonal variability. Models indicate that, over the course of a typical day, wind velocities, temperature, and vertical atmospheric motions exhibit pronounced variability. At higher altitudes this variability is even greater and it is primarily driven by upward propagating tides, planetary waves, and gravity waves excited in the lower atmosphere augmented by thermospheric drag higher in the MTS. Complicit in this variability are chemical reactions, solar heating, radiative cooling, and density variations, which feed back into the dynamically driven environment. During solstices, pole-to-pole circulations occur with their direction changing every six months. The density fluctuations extend upward and at LEO altitudes (400–800 km) alter the residual atmospheric drag on satellites (and space debris) and therefore their true orbits with respect to predictions.

The MTS is a transition region where terrestrial and solar influences interleave. Neutral atmospheric variability and upward-propagating waves dominate the conditions at lower heights and ionospheric plasma processes associated with geospace become important at higher altitudes. Its study is crucial for determining the upward influences that cause significant variability in the upper atmosphere, including ionosphere, and downward transport that affects the climate of the lower atmosphere. As the MTS neither falls entirely within the remit of the Earth nor Space sciences, it remains poorly understood relative to its importance as the link between the atmosphere and geospace. The region is key to understanding the Sun-Earth as a system and improving the predictive/modelling capabilities of space weather.

Despite its central role in atmospheric coupling, and its direct impact on satellite drag, radio propagation and space weather variability, the MTS remains poorly observed. Existing observations are fragmented in altitude, sensitivity and sampling, limiting their ability to characterise system-wide structure and variability or to provide consistent constraints for model evaluation. The MTS is considered to be one of the

least studied regions of the planet; one of the few remaining *terrae incognitae*. Considerable research is still required to understand the fascinating and complex phenomena occurring at the edge of space. This is driven by scientific interest and by its direct application to increasing the resilience of space infrastructure. Achieving this knowledge is absolutely crucial to understanding the atmosphere and its response to space weather.

The world is in the midst of a rapid acceleration in the use of space for communication, remote sensing and surveillance and a concurrent increase in near-Earth satellites and their re-entry in a region (the MTS) that is poorly understood and observed. There is a consequent need to understand the MTS in more detail, in particular its short-term variability. The Keystone mission would satisfy this need. Satellite orbit planning would be supported through Keystone's daily global density observations which inform satellite drag calculations. Its suite of MTS observations would unravel the complexities of this region and ensure that the consequences of the enhanced use of this region can be meaningfully evaluated. Given the upward trajectory of space utilisation, a mission such as Keystone is relevant and essential.

The MTS is introduced and the main processes that drive its variability are explained in Section 2.1. The central role of atomic oxygen in the MTS is further elaborated in Section 2.2. The implications for thermospheric density and drag are discussed in Section 2.3. Current knowledge gaps are discussed in Section 2.4.

2.1. The Mesosphere-Thermosphere System and its Transition to the Space Environment

Section 2.1 comprises an overview of the physics and chemistry in the MTS (Section 2.1.1), followed by discussions of energy balance and climate change (Section 2.1.2), atmospheric dynamics (Section 2.1.3), and the ionosphere (Section 2.1.4).

2.1.1. Overview of MTS Physics and Chemistry

As a transition region, the MTS is influenced by processes throughout the atmosphere and the ionosphere. Figure 2.1 illustrates the vertical structure of the atmosphere, together with the main physical and chemical processes important for the MTS. The mesosphere extends from the stratopause to the mesopause. The stratopause depicts a local temperature maximum, clearly visible in the red temperature profile in Figure 2.1, which results from the heat released by stratospheric ozone absorbing solar near-UV radiation. In contrast, the mesopause is at a local temperature minimum, which varies in altitude from around 85 km, in summer, to 100 km, in winter. It defines the key transition layer separating the mesosphere below from the thermosphere above. The thermosphere starts, in fact, at the mesopause, and is characterised by a rapid temperature increase with altitude due to the absorption of extreme UV radiation, mainly by O₂, at wavelengths below 200 nm. The molecular translational temperatures in the thermosphere can exceed 1000 K during solar storms; however, at the very low pressures of this region (<10⁻⁶ bar above 100 km), the internal vibrational and rotational modes of molecules are generally not in Local Thermodynamic Equilibrium (LTE) and do not match the local kinetic temperature.

Figure 2.1 also illustrates the important processes which govern the composition and chemistry of the region. The MTS is subject to high-energy solar electromagnetic radiation and charged particles (mostly solar electrons and protons (Sinnhuber et al., 2012)). The resulting photodissociation, photoionisation and high-energy collisions generate radicals and ions, often with internal excitation. The dominant process is photodissociation of O₂ through absorption in the spectral ranges 130–175 nm (Schumann-Runge continuum) and 175–195 nm (Schumann-Runge bands), with a less important contribution from O₃ photolysis (Mlynczak et al., 2013). This generates atomic O (simply referred to as “O” from here onwards), which participates in highly exothermic reactions, converting chemical potential energy into thermal ki-

Figure 2.1: Schematic representation of the Mesosphere-Thermosphere System (MTS) as the critical transition region between lower atmosphere and geospace. The region features strong connections to the domains below and above, resulting in a complex interplay of dynamics (green), radiation (yellow), neutral composition (blue), plasma (purple), and thermal structure (red). Atomic oxygen is a key player in driving photochemical, thermal, dynamic and plasma-neutral interactions (Credits: J. Gumbel, ESA EOGB).

netic energy and radiant energy (observed as airglow). A roughly similar amount of thermal kinetic energy is deposited from below by the breaking of gravity waves. The dominant cooling process is emission of thermal radiation by CO₂ near 15 μm; its degenerate bending vibrational mode is efficiently excited by collision with O atoms (Castle et al., 2012). The MTS is also the region where cosmic dust particles entering the atmosphere ablate, injecting a range of metals like Fe, Mg and Na (Plane et al., 2015). The MTS is subject to extremes: pressures falling from 0.1 mbar to below 0.1 μbar (above the homopause at a pressure around 0.5 μbar, molecular diffusion becomes more important than eddy diffusion in transporting constituent species); and temperatures ranging from below 100 K (the coldest part of the planet where noctilucent clouds occur) to over 2500 K in ablating cosmic dust particles.

Satellite mega-constellation missions are responsible for a rapid growth in the number of rocket launches and anthropogenic re-entries. Launches inject particle-phase black carbon, gas-phase nitrogen oxides, water vapour, carbon monoxide, and chlorine compounds as well as carbon dioxide in all atmospheric layers. Re-entering objects from low Earth orbits partially or fully ablate in the mesosphere. Ablating objects comprised of aluminium produce aluminium oxides/hydroxides via oxidation (Barker et al., 2024), which eventually end up in the lower layers of the atmosphere. There is evidence that about 10% of stratospheric aerosol particles already contain traces of elements that stem from discarded satellites and rocket bodies (Murphy et al., 2023). The mass flux of these elements due to anthropogenic re-entry is already comparable to natural injections due to cosmic dust particles (Schulz and Glassmeier, 2021; Schulz et al., 2026). Aerosols and an increased amounts of water vapour may lead to an enhanced

formation of noctilucent clouds (Megner et al., 2008), impact the D-layer ion chemistry (Baumann et al., 2015) and the ozone layer (Ryan et al., 2022; Ferreira et al., 2024).

2.1.2. Energy Balance and Climate Change in the MTS

The energy balance of the mesosphere and the lower thermosphere is controlled by CO₂ and NO radiative cooling, both driven by collisions with atomic oxygen (Mlynczak et al., 2010; Ranjan et al., 2023). These collisions act as essential bridges transferring the kinetic energy of the gas into internal vibrational energy of the molecules via vibrational-translational collisions with O atoms. Once vibrationally excited, the molecule can relax by emitting a photon to space, effectively cooling the atmosphere. Specifically, collisions with O excite CO₂ to its bending vibrational state $\nu_2=1$; the subsequent infrared emission by CO₂ near 15 μm dominates the cooling of the mesosphere. Collisional excitation of NO (to the vibrational state $\nu=1$) and subsequent infrared emission near 5.3 μm becomes increasingly efficient above 110 km. The efficiencies of these processes are intrinsically linked since both collisions are temperature dependent and share the collision partner (O). Because the NO production rate is strongly dependent on temperature, NO cooling is important for the regulation of thermospheric temperature during strong auroral heating events (Mlynczak et al., 2003; Weimer et al., 2015). An accurate characterization of both processes is important to correctly partition the total energy budget.

In contrast to the global warming trend of the troposphere, the middle and upper atmosphere (stratosphere, mesosphere, and thermosphere) have been cooling (Laštovička et al., 2012). Above the tropopause the atmospheric density is low enough that the blanketing effect of the troposphere no longer exists. Increases in CO₂ enhance the efficiency of radiating the thermal energy to space so these regions cool. It is of essential importance to understand these changes to this environment as they have important consequences for planning future satellite missions (Brown et al., 2021), space debris risk management (Lewis et al., 2011), and assessing the likelihood and impacts of future space weather threats. Trends in upper atmospheric density are mainly driven by the increase in CO₂. In the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) SSP1-2.6 scenario, density reductions at 400 km are estimated to be 13–30% (under high and low solar activity, respectively, Brown et al., 2024). Variations in ozone concentration, geomagnetic activity, and Earth's magnetic field play secondary roles in long-term trends (Crossen, 2020).

Regarding density variability on shorter timescales, at 85–115 km height, observations and model simulations indicate density variability of 20–40%, which is not captured by empirical models (Huyghebaert et al., 2025). This variability is driven by geomagnetic events and atmospheric phenomena, such as changes in the strength of the polar vortex, tides, planetary waves and gravity wave breaking events.

2.1.3. Atmospheric Dynamics in the MTS

The Sun is the dominant driver of the MTS, but the large-scale atmospheric structures that develop in response to this input are due to the inherent properties of the Earth: its atmosphere and associated intrinsic dynamics (waves and large scale motion) and ionosphere (Oberheide et al., 2015; Ward et al., 2021). Waves excited in the lower atmosphere grow with height and maximize in the 80 to 110 km region where many break. Here, their effects dominate the variability of constituent concentrations, temperature, and winds. Some waves penetrate to several hundred kilometres, where they affect the ionosphere (Yiğit et al., 2016; Oberheide et al., 2025). Their dissipation drives a pole-to-pole circulation in the 90 km region with associated upward transport over the summer pole and downward transport over the winter pole (Butchart, 2014). The upward transport cools the air resulting in the coldest region of the atmosphere, the summer mesopause region and the production of noctilucent clouds (also known as polar mesospheric clouds). The downward transport is a pathway for ionospheric effects to penetrate into

the lower atmosphere (Nesse et al., 2026). Recently, evidence for additional global circulation systems above this have been published (Wang et al., 2022, 2023; Koshin et al., 2025a). Their impact is still being investigated.

The waves are anisotropic and include planetary (Rossby) waves, tides and gravity (buoyancy) waves, the first being associated with latitudinal variations in angular momentum and the latter two with atmospheric buoyancy (Andrews et al., 1987). Planetary waves have temporal scales of days and spatial scales of the order of the circumference of the Earth. Tides have similar spatial scales and periods that are sub-harmonics of a day. They are driven by solar heating and the diurnal cycle in tropospheric deep convection, and impose a strong local time imprint on all observables (Khadka et al., 2026). Gravity waves are ubiquitous and have temporal scales from minutes to hours and spatial scales from kilometres to thousands of kilometres (Fritts and Alexander, 2003). They drive the large-scale circulations mentioned above and are the primary agent causing vertical mixing in the MTS (Becker and Vadas, 2020; Achatz et al., 2024). The superposition of these waves results in all atmospheric parameters having a spatially mottled appearance which shimmers in time with tides imposing a quasi-regular spatial structure on everything (see for example (Hays et al., 2003) and Figure 2.2). While the basic properties of these waves are understood, their sources, propagation and dissipation and hence role in coupling different regions of the atmosphere remain poorly understood. This is especially true in the MTS where the lack of direct observations noted earlier poorly constrains the properties of this region.

Keystone, through its broad range of co-located observables, would provide, for the first time, coherent insights into the large-scale waves and flows, their impacts and the systematic effects of gravity waves in the MTS region.

2.1.4. The Ionosphere

Extending from approximately 60 to over 1000 km (Kelley, 2009), the terrestrial ionosphere — the lower part of which overlaps with the MTS — marks the transition from a pure fluid-dynamic to a strong electrodynamic component. The ionosphere is a weakly ionised, globally neutral plasma, with ion-to-neutral ratios increasing with altitude from 10^{-8} to 10^{-2} (Schunk and Nagy, 2009). This plasma is sustained primarily by solar Extreme UltraViolet (EUV) and X-ray radiation, alongside high-latitude energetic particle precipitation from the magnetosphere. Although it behaves mostly as a cold plasma governed by electromagnetic forces, a unique collision-dominated regime emerges below 150 km due to higher neutral gas densities. The behaviour and density of its free electrons dictate the ionosphere's defining capability to influence radio wave propagation across the kHz to GHz spectrum (Hunsucker and Hargreaves, 2007). Within its broad layered structure, according to the plasma distribution with height, it is specifically the D- and E-layers that constitute the portion embedded within the upper mesosphere and lower thermosphere, functioning as a highly collisional transition regime where rapid chemical recombination and solar-driven dynamo currents dictate the local electrodynamics (Bauer and Lammer, 2004). The ionospheric layers are illustrated on the right-hand side of Figure 2.1 by the purple curve. Fundamentally, the ionosphere serves as a critical bridge for global energy transfer. It is coupled from above by solar-wind and magnetospheric forcing, and from below by terrestrial events such as earthquakes and volcanic eruptions, and lower atmosphere phenomena such as atmospheric tides, planetary waves, gravity waves and sudden stratospheric warmings that perturb the neutral background and generate ionospheric variability (Astafyeva, 2019; Yamazaki et al., 2020; Liu et al., 2024; Wüst et al., 2026).

Because the D- and E-layers constitute the highly collisional ionospheric portion embedded within the MTS, understanding this region requires resolving its electrodynamics, energetics, and neutral dynamics. Electrodynamically, neutral winds drive the ionospheric dynamo by dragging ions across magnetic field lines, while neutral composition and temperature modulate the collision frequencies that shape the conductivity tensor and current closure (Yamazaki and Maute, 2017). Energetically, neutral winds regu-

late Joule heating intensity, and composition changes, i.e., NO production and O/N₂ variations, control the radiative cooling and chemical loss rates necessary to restore thermal equilibrium (Richmond and Lu, 2000; Fuller-Rowell, 2011). Dynamically, structural features are governed by neutral-plasma interactions: vertical neutral wind shears compress metallic ions into dense Sporadic E (E_s) layers (Haldoupis et al., 2023), while atmospheric gravity waves can contribute to Travelling Ionospheric Disturbances (TIDs) and, under suitable electrodynamic and plasma conditions, help seed plasma instabilities (Nicolls and Kelley, 2005; Zawdie et al., 2022).

2.2. The Role of Atomic Oxygen in the Chemistry and Energy Balance of the Upper Atmosphere

In the mesosphere, the chemical heating rate from exothermic chemical reactions exceeds that from directly thermalised solar radiation by at least a factor of 2 (Marsh, 2011). The reactions that drive this chemical heating are all connected to the abundance of O (Mlynchak and Solomon, 1993). Due to atomic oxygen's long lifetime (greater than 1 day above around 82 km), it can transport chemical potential energy within the MTS (vertically and horizontally). This produces heating in the polar night, even in the absence of solar radiation and the transport of significant amount of chemical potential energy from the thermosphere into the mesosphere. While the relative abundance of atomic oxygen increases with height in the MTS, its number density maximises in the region between 90 and 105 km. O at these heights can vary by an order of magnitude across latitudes at a fixed height (see e.g. Figure 2.2) and so the chemical heating that depends on O is similarly highly variable.

Figure 2.2: Comparison of WACCM-X, “physics-based model” (left), and NRLMSIS 2.0, “empirical model” (right), atomic oxygen densities in the 80–130 km altitude range under quiet geomagnetic conditions (Credits: D. Marsh, H. Liu, T. Dörffel).

Many of the reactions involving O lead to chemical products in excited states which then emit light. These chemiluminescent reactions are the source of the airglow, which is an important energy loss process in the MTS. Signatures of the variability in O are present in many airglow emissions (e.g. Taylor et al., 1995; Hays et al., 2003). In addition, the recombination of O with NO is critical for recovery of the thermosphere following geomagnetic storms. O also modulates CO₂ cooling rates in the mesosphere and lower thermosphere by collisionally exciting and relaxing the bending vibrational modes of CO₂. It also provides an opportunity for remotely sensing this region of the atmosphere and quantifying the energy balance.

State-of-the-art “empirical models”, such as NRLMSIS 2.0 (Emmert et al., 2022) or DTM-2020 (Bruinsma and Boniface, 2021), are frequently used to obtain constituent concentrations in the MTS. They are de-

signed to fit a sparse set of observations to a small set of mathematical functions that must span all altitudes and latitudes. By their nature, these models produce a very smoothed (in space and time) estimate of atmospheric composition. This is especially true for atomic oxygen. Figure 2.2 illustrates the difference between NRLMSIS 2.0 “empirical model” and WACCM-X (a “physics-based” whole-atmosphere model described in Section 6.1) for a snapshot in time under the same solar and geomagnetic conditions. NRLMSIS 2.0 uses a set of spherical harmonics to fit the latitudinal and local time variation of atomic oxygen (Emmert et al., 2022). Much of the small-scale structure simulated by WACCM-X is missing in the empirical models estimate.

Geospace forcing from solar transients drives strong changes in temperature, composition, and circulation down to the upper mesosphere (Vickrey et al., 1982). Figure 2.3 illustrates the dramatic changes in the relative abundances of O during an extreme geomagnetic storm modelled to occur in January (the simulation is described in Section 6.1). Prior to the storm, O volume mixing ratio (VMR) peaks near the winter pole, where it comprises approximately 80% of the atmosphere. During the storm, strong heating in the auroral regions leads to rapid upwelling of the atmosphere above 50°N latitude and descent in tropics. The polar ascent brings air rich in molecular nitrogen up from the lower thermosphere, reducing O and increasing the mean molecular mass of the atmosphere (Figure 2.3B, first row), and therefore changing the drag on satellites and space debris. These composition changes persist after the storm (Figure 2.3C, first row). Since O is critical to the radiative cooling of the MTS, the rearrangement of O impacts how quickly the atmosphere returns to a pre-storm state and how it may respond to subsequent geomagnetic variability. In contrast, the bottom part of Figure 2.3 displays the corresponding data retrieved from the NRLMSIS-2.0 model. Again, a lack of detail compared to the WACCM-X data and also qualitative differences in the latitudinal distribution of atomic oxygen can be observed.

In addition, the redistribution of atomic oxygen during a solar storm modulates ion-neutral collision frequencies and ionospheric conductivities (Yamazaki and Maute, 2017). The MTS serves as the critical electrical load for the magnetosphere-ionosphere-thermosphere coupling system, while also acting as a complex reservoir for chemical and thermal energy. The interplay between these electrodynamic and energetic processes is governed by the plasma-neutral interactions, where atomic oxygen plays a central and multi-faceted role, modulating space weather phenomena across all latitudes (Sarris et al., 2023). Therefore, atomic oxygen provides a key link between electrodynamic forcing and the broader dynamical response of the plasma part within the upper mesosphere and lower thermosphere. At high latitudes, strong plasma convection accelerates ions through electromagnetic forcing; ion-neutral collisions then transfer momentum to the neutral gas, producing ion-drag forcing and high-latitude neutral-wind disturbances (Kwak and Richmond, 2007). Because the neutral atmosphere possesses high inertia, these winds persist long after geomagnetic forcing ceases, acting as a dynamic flywheel that drives disturbance dynamo currents back into the global circuit. At low and equatorial latitudes, lower thermosphere neutral winds drive the Equatorial Electrojet (EEJ) and regulate the electric fields that seed and modulate Equatorial Plasma Bubbles (EPBs) (Bhattacharyya et al., 2011; Balan et al., 2018; Yamazaki and Maute, 2017).

2.3. Thermospheric Density and Drag

At LEO altitudes (<1000 km), atmospheric drag is the largest contributor to satellite trajectory prediction error (Mutschler et al., 2026). Precise orbit determination for satellites and space debris is critical for collision avoidance, targeted re-entry, and anomaly detection (e.g. identifying damage from collisions). Achieving this requires an accurate estimate of atmospheric drag, which is linearly proportional to thermospheric mass density (Bruinsma et al., 2023).

During severe geomagnetic storms, energy deposited into the auroral regions causes sudden, rapid ex-

pansions of the thermosphere that spread globally within a few hours (Bruinsma et al., 2023; Parker and Linares, 2024). The resulting neutral density enhancements, which have reached up to 800% in observed extreme cases (Liu and Lühr, 2005) and could exceed 1400% in simulated 1-in-100-year events (Krauss et al., 2015), significantly amplify physical drag. Satellites can rapidly lose altitude, forcing operators or autonomous systems to execute emergency orbit-raising manoeuvres. If unpredicted, this enhanced drag causes premature re-entry, as demonstrated by the loss of 38 Starlink satellites during a moderate storm in February 2022 (Zhang et al., 2022; Berger et al., 2023; Baruah et al., 2024). Furthermore, sudden and widespread orbital shifts can cause ground systems to temporarily lose track of thousands of space objects, as occurred during the massive 1989 storm (Berger et al., 2023). With the growing density of space debris and large satellite constellations, these tracking failures drastically elevate the risk of dangerous in-orbit collisions, highlighted by the February 2024 near-miss (within 20 m) between NASA’s TIMED spacecraft and a non-functional Russian Cosmos satellite (Wall, 2024; Berger et al., 2020b). Crucially, these events were not predicted with sufficient accuracy due to the limitations of current thermospheric models. Standard empirical models are demonstrably inaccurate during space weather events (Berger et al., 2020a). For example, at an altitude of 210 km, density increases of 40–60% were observed during the February 2022 storm (the aforementioned Starlink-related event), but the NRLMSISE-00 model predicted only a ~5% change (Zhang et al., 2022). Even the newest iteration, NRLMSIS 2.0, has difficulty reconciling systematic biases among temperature and composition datasets (Emmert et al., 2021). This structural limitation is equally present in the semi-empirical DTM-2020 model (Bruinsma and Boniface, 2021).

Figure 2.4 illustrates the dramatic difference in how these models respond to geomagnetic variability

Figure 2.3: Comparison of WACCM-X, “physical model” (left), and NRLMSIS 2.0, “empirical model” (right), atomic oxygen volume mixing ratio (VMR) in the 110–250 km altitude range during a geomagnetic storm. Panels A and C show O before and after the storm, respectively, while panel B shows O at the peak of the storm (Credits: D. Marsh, F. Sainsbury-Martinez, T. Dörffel).

Figure 2.4: Relative difference in density between the state of the art “empirical models” NRLMSIS 2.0 and DTM-2020 (relative to DTM-2020), for same atmospheric conditions, at either solar minimum (green) or solar maximum (orange), over the equator (solid line) or a latitude of 65° N (dashed line) (Credits: D. Marsh, F. Sainsbury-Martinez).

under different solar flux conditions. The solar flux conditions are identified through the F10.7 index (Tapping, 2013), which measures the solar radio flux at 10.7 cm wavelength in solar flux units ($1 \text{ sfu} = 10^{-22} \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ Hz}^{-1}$), typically ranging from 65 sfu (quiet) to >250 sfu (active). The geomagnetic variability is indicated by means of the K_p index (Kauristie et al., 2017), which quantifies geomagnetic disturbance severity on a logarithmic scale from 0 (quiet) to 9 (extreme), calculated tri-hourly by averaging data from 13 magnetometer observatories distributed worldwide at subauroral latitudes. During quiet times, densities from NRLMSIS 2.0 deviate significantly from DTM-2020 predictions with deviation ranging from -20% to +25%. During geomagnetic storm conditions, even larger deviations are found: at high latitudes NRLMSIS 2.0 underestimates density as compared to DTM-2020 by 60% and more. These theoretical discrepancies translate directly into massive errors in estimated atmospheric drag. Consequently, uncertainties in current drag models routinely reach up to 60% during solar storm conditions. Such severe discrepancies compromise the operational orbit determination systems mandated by European Cooperation for Space Standardization (ECSS) (European Cooperation for Space Standardization, 2020) and utilised daily by agencies like ESA and CNES (Bruinsma and Boniface, 2021).

To safely manage the rapidly increasing number of spacecraft in LEO, there is a pressing socio-economic need for models capable of accounting for forcing from both above and below. As identified by major space weather user surveys, progress in this domain relies entirely on securing new, height-resolved temperature and species density measurements in the critical 100–200 km boundary region.

2.4. Processes Knowledge Gaps

Model Improvements: Reaction Rates

Airglow has been a topic of active research for more than a century, but important aspects of the excitation and relaxation mechanisms of many airglow emissions are still not fully understood. One of the main reasons for these gaps in scientific understanding is the lack of global, continuous and direct determination of atomic oxygen concentrations in the MTS. Complex photochemical models are available, e.g. for the airglow emissions by O, O₂ or OH (e.g. McDade et al., 1986, 1987; von Savigny et al., 2012; Lednyts'kyk et al., 2015). Most of these models are based on in-situ rocket measurements carried out during the ETON (Energy Transfer in the Oxygen Nightglow) measurement campaign in March 1982. Simultaneous nightglow and atomic oxygen profile measurements were used to adjust rate constants and empirical factors of the airglow excitation models. These models were in the last decades used to estimate mesosphere/lower thermosphere atomic oxygen profiles from satellite airglow observations with different instruments, e.g. WINDII (Russell and Lowe, 2003), OSIRIS (Sheese et al., 2011), SCIAMACHY (von Savigny and Lednyts'kyk, 2013; Kaufmann et al., 2014; Lednyts'kyk et al., 2015). However, a comprehensive validation of these models and global, continuous and direct observations of O in this region is still missing. In other words, most of our knowledge on the morphology of atomic oxygen in the mesosphere and lower thermosphere is based on photochemical models that are not well validated. Keystone would provide the essential direct, global and continuous observations of O for the

first time. The Keystone mission would therefore also provide essential information for reprocessing satellite airglow measurements with historic missions, allowing to go back in time at last to 1991, when UARS (carrying WINDII and HRDI) was launched.

One fundamental and long-standing challenge in atmospheric science is the characterization of the CO₂-O collision process and the associated conversion of kinetic energy into vibrational energy ((Ward and Fomichev, 1996), see also Section 2.1.2). For over five decades, the CO₂-O collision rate has remained poorly constrained: laboratory measurements deviate significantly from rates inferred from satellite observations; the latter exhibit differences of a factor of 3 to 4 (Feofilov et al., 2012). Precisely quantifying this rate is a prerequisite for assessing the projections of anthropogenic CO₂ increase on the MTS energy balance and to ensure the fidelity of temperature and composition retrievals, not only from Keystone IR measurements but also from previous infrared sounders. Furthermore, the rate's altitude dependence, driven by its sensitivity to local kinetic temperature, is poorly constrained. Current temperature dependence estimations point to a 30–50% rate increase from 90 to 110 km, depending on solar activity. Closing this knowledge gap is not only a priority for Earth's climate modeling but also a fundamental requirement for understanding the radiative cooling and atmospheric evolution of other planets, like Mars and Venus (Rezac et al., 2015; Hübers et al., 2023).

Large-Scale Variability Originating from the Lower Atmosphere

The role of tropospheric modes of variability, such as the quasi-biennial oscillation (QBO) and Madden-Julian Oscillation (MJO) in modulating thermospheric structure and variability remains poorly constrained (Koshin et al., 2022; Kumari et al., 2021; Singh et al., 2026). These modes influence the generation, filtering, and propagation of tides and gravity waves, thereby altering the flux of energy and momentum into the MTS and beyond. However, the resulting impacts on composition, temperature, and density are not well captured in current models due to a lack of vertically resolved, co-located observations. Keystone would provide the observations required to quantify and constrain these processes within a whole-atmosphere framework, including observations across a full QBO cycle (~2.5 years) and a very large number of MJO cycles (each ~30–60 days). This also includes sporadic events, such as sudden stratospheric warmings (SSW), whose teleconnections to the upper atmosphere are poorly studied.

The coupling between the upper and lower atmosphere is not simply upwards. NO produced in the thermosphere is transported downwards over the wintertime during polar night, where it contributes to springtime depletion of ozone in the upper stratosphere. This will impact the thermal structure of stratosphere and its wind structure, impacting wave propagation upwards and downwards (Nesse et al., 2026). This coupling is considered important enough that the impact of thermospheric NO variability is included forcing used for climate projections for the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (e.g. (Matthes et al., 2017; Funke et al., 2024)).

Space Weather Modelling

A fundamental knowledge gap in current space weather forecasting is the lack of a comprehensive empirical baseline required to rigorously constrain whole-atmosphere models. Specifically, the absence of continuous, global observations of atomic oxygen and kinetic temperatures within the MTS prevents the accurate derivation of thermospheric mass density. Identified by the International Space Weather Action Teams (ISWAT) initiative of Committee on Space Research (COSPAR), this is an Essential Space Environment Quantity (ESEQ) that serves as a critical input for space weather products in the Research to Operations (R2O) process (see Table 3.1 in Kuznetsova et al., 2026). This observational deficit sustains long-standing uncertainties in lower thermospheric dynamics, critically limiting the ability to predict satellite aerodynamic drag, especially during severe geomagnetic storms. Addressing this gap in neutral density modelling is essential for ensuring the resilience of critical space infrastructure. As the

Very Low Earth Orbit (VLEO) sector rapidly expands, robust collision avoidance, orbit propagation, and long-term orbital sustainability rely entirely on resolving these missing physical parameters to withstand extreme space weather events. Furthermore, significant observational gaps restrict the understanding of the coupled neutral-plasma processes that govern ionospheric anomalies in the E-region, like sporadic E-layers. Simultaneous medium scale observations (~ 1000 km along track and wavenumber 5 across track) of neutral wind profiles, metallic species, temperature and composition in the MTS would contribute significantly to the validation of current models. To date, comprehensive observations such as these have never been available. Addressing this gap in ion-neutral coupling represents an important step toward improving empirical space weather models. This enhanced physical understanding contributes to broader efforts to improve models of space weather effects on HF communications, over-the-horizon radar and navigation-system performance.

3. SCIENCE GOALS AND MISSION OBJECTIVES

3.1. Scientific Motivation

The Mesosphere-Thermosphere System is the dynamic interface between the lower atmosphere and space. Although foundational knowledge has been built upon remote sensing and rocket soundings, these fragmented observations are insufficient to capture its complexity. As shown in Section 2, the MTS state and its variability remain poorly understood. Keystone aims to close this gap by characterising the MTS composition, chemistry, and thermal balance, thereby decoding the processes driving this variability.

Atomic Oxygen: The Missing “Keystone”

A critical knowledge gap currently limits the fundamental understanding of the MTS: the lack of direct observations of its dominant neutral species, atomic oxygen. As the primary driver of the region’s thermal balance, photochemistry, and dynamic coupling, its true abundance remains highly uncertain. This unresolved state is largely due to the severe limitations and inaccuracies inherent in the indirect observations currently relied upon by the scientific community. Historically, the scientific understanding of the MTS has been predominantly built upon indirect observations of its composition, relying either on infrared (IR) emissions of molecules excited by collisions with O, or on UV-Vis airglow signatures of O and related species in excited states. Each of these indirect approaches suffers from distinct, systemic limitations. The accuracy of IR techniques is fundamentally limited by significant uncertainties in the collisional quenching rates of excited vibrational states by atomic oxygen, the very process that transfers energy from O to CO₂ and acts as one of the primary radiative energy sinks in the MTS. Estimates for this specific CO₂-O quenching rate remain a subject of intense debate, with differing methodologies yielding values that diverge by up to a factor of four (Feofilov et al., 2012). Consequently, abundance profiles derived from past IR missions, such as SABER (TIMED) (Esplin et al., 2023), are inherently tethered to unconstrained assumptions about the background distribution of atomic oxygen. Conversely, the accuracy of indirect techniques using UV-Vis airglow, such as those employed by the OSIRIS (Llewellyn et al., 2004) and SCIAMACHY (Bovensmann et al., 1999) missions, is limited by their reliance on complex non-local thermodynamic equilibrium (non-LTE) and photochemical models. Because these models depend heavily on assumed reaction paths and electronic quenching rates, they introduce their own set of severe uncertainties. Ultimately, both indirect approaches fail to provide the definitive, unconstrained baseline required to truly understand the region.

Keystone aims at providing the first global, continuous and direct observations of atomic oxygen in the MTS.

To resolve this knowledge gap, Keystone targets a paradigm shift from indirect to direct observation. By deploying a high-resolution THz heterodyne spectrometer, Keystone would deliver vertical profiles of ground-state atomic oxygen number density ([O]) without relying on complex photochemical assumptions. While previous instruments have pioneered THz techniques for other molecules, the direct observation of atomic oxygen based on THz measurements from space has remained technologically elusive. Keystone aims at providing direct observations of atomic oxygen abundance across the globe, closing this long-standing blind spot and enabling the first robust climatologies of this important atmospheric constituent.

Furthermore, by providing these direct THz retrievals in coincidence with heritage-style IR and UV-Vis observations, the mission pursues a transformative scientific multiplier effect. Keystone would not only provide an unprecedented, self-consistent picture of the current MTS, but would add scientific value well beyond its immediate operational lifespan: by constraining the true atomic oxygen quenching rate and

airglow photochemistry, Keystone would provide the basis required to rigorously reprocess, recalibrate, and unlock the full potential of decades of historical MTS observations.

Energy Balance

The thermal structure of the MTS is fundamentally governed by a delicate energy balance, which Keystone would observationally close from three interconnected perspectives. First, by retrieving absolute atomic oxygen profiles via THz radiometry, the mission directly quantifies the primary driver of the region's chemical and thermal energy transfer. Second, it observes the direct radiative energy loss through infrared (IR) emissions (e.g. CO₂ and NO), whose cooling rates are heavily modulated by collisions with this atomic oxygen. Third, Keystone measures the energy lost to space via chemiluminescent airglow in the UV-Vis spectrum, a process directly fuelled by atomic oxygen photochemistry. By simultaneously measuring the fundamental driver ([O]) alongside the two primary cooling channels (IR and UV-Vis emissions), Keystone would provide an unprecedented, closed-loop assessment of the upper atmosphere's energy budget.

Process Understanding and Model Improvement

To advance the understanding of the region's structure and variability, Keystone provides coordinated, multi-parameter observations of composition, temperature, winds, and ionisation across the full altitude range. Ultimately, the mission would deliver the well-calibrated empirical baseline required to validate quantitative atmospheric models, which currently depend heavily on unconstrained laboratory investigations, *ab initio* theoretical calculations, and reaction rate theories.

Vertical Coupling Across Atmospheric Domains

By providing co-located observations of atomic oxygen, temperature, winds, and airglow, Keystone enables a system-level understanding of the processes linking the lower atmosphere to the near-space environment. Ultimately, the mission would yield unprecedented insights into the multi-scale coupling processes that unite traditionally separate domains: the Mesosphere–Lower Thermosphere (MLT; ~75–120 km), the overlying thermosphere, the D- and E-region ionosphere.

Societal Relevance

The MTS responds strongly to solar and magnetospheric forcing, which drives profound short-term changes in its composition, thermal structure, and energy balance. Crucially, this neutral atmospheric response is tightly coupled to the morphology and dynamics of the ionosphere. By combining THz, IR, and UV-Vis observations, Keystone would systematically track this solar-driven variability and its effects on the MTS. Quantifying these coupled dynamics would directly underpin the evolution of next-generation space weather models, enhancing the physical basis of models used to forecast solar-storm impacts and to design mitigation strategies. A prime example is the urgent socio-economic need for accurate predictions of thermospheric drag, driven by the rapid proliferation of large satellite constellations. By improving the models used for orbit forecasting and collision risk reduction, Keystone would directly contribute to space weather resilience, societal preparedness, and the protection of orbital infrastructure worth billions of euros.

Beyond monitoring natural space weather hazards, Keystone would also track the growing human footprint on the MTS. The rapid expansion of the new-space era is introducing unprecedented levels of anthropogenic pollution into the upper atmosphere, particularly from ablating re-entry debris and rocket emissions. By elucidating the inherently complex physics and chemistry of the region, Keystone would provide the critical empirical data needed to constrain models and accurately predict the mid- and long-term consequences of this pollution on the whole atmosphere. To address these escalating natural and anthropogenic challenges, Keystone targets a critical, impending gap in the ability to monitor upper atmo-

spheric change. Over the past decades, foundational global observations of the mesosphere and lower thermosphere have been provided by a few key satellite missions. However, these satellites are now at or beyond the end of their operational lifetimes, with no direct replacements currently planned (Mlynczak et al., 2021). Given the ongoing climate-driven changes in the MTS and their cascading impacts on the space and telecommunications sectors, this looming observational gap is a substantial concern from both a scientific and a societal perspective.

Keystone would substantially expand the observational capabilities in the MTS, a vital region of the Earth system.

3.2. Science Goals

The scientific motivation drives three core Science Goals (SGs) for the mission:

SG.1: MTS Characterisation

To comprehensively characterise the density, composition, chemistry and thermal balance of the MTS, by pioneering observations of atomic oxygen – the missing keystone for understanding the critical transition region connecting the Earth’s atmosphere and space – together with key trace gases, thermal heat loss, and airglow.

SG.2: Multi-Scale Coupling

To study and assess multi-scale coupling processes within the mesosphere-thermosphere system. This includes internal phenomena such as large-scale atmospheric waves, space weather effects, and global inter-hemispheric coupling/transport.

SG.3: Whole-Atmosphere Modelling

To improve the representation, prediction and projection of the whole-atmosphere chemistry-climate system in next-generation whole-atmosphere models, with applications to space weather resilience, climate forcing, and satellite drag forecasting.

3.3. Tracing Science Goals to the ESA EO Science Strategy

At the end of 2024, ESA released its new EO Science Strategy (ESA, 2024), outlining a comprehensive vision for Earth Science through 2040 and identifying the critical priorities required to address both scientific and societal needs. The strategy establishes six Overarching Science Themes designed to engage the broad scientific community and align with major international frameworks. To effectively guide the implementation of future missions, it further defines a set of guiding Science Questions (SQs) targeting pressing knowledge gaps, alongside four primary Areas of Action (A1–A4).

Regarding the Overarching Science Themes in ESA’s EO Science Strategy, Keystone addresses the MTS as an integral part of the Earth system. This approach links directly to the central idea of the new EO Science Strategy of viewing the Earth system as an integrated network of interconnected processes, fluxes and exchanges ((ESA, 2024), p. 11). The new EO Science Strategy and Keystone thus transcend an outdated view of an Earth system that is divided into “spheres”. Embracing this holistic view, Keystone’s Science Goals are directly connected to four of ESA’s Overarching Science Themes ((ESA, 2024), pp. 32–33): SG.1–SG.3 would contribute to **Theme ST-II (The Carbon cycle and chemistry)** through their studies of trace gases and related chemical/transport processes and their description in

whole-atmosphere models. SG.1–SG.3 would contribute to **Theme ST-III (Energy fluxes)** by directly connecting radiative processes and relevant trace gases, substantially enhancing the abilities to quantify Earth’s energy budget. SG.2 and SG.3 would contribute to **Theme ST-V (Extremes and hazards)** by addressing space weather and its effects on the atmosphere through various coupling processes, enhancing our resilience as a society. Last but not least, SG.2 would contribute strongly to **Theme ST-VI (Interfaces and coupling in the Earth system)** by quantifying coupling processes on multiple scales throughout the atmosphere. Within these Overarching Science Themes, Keystone addresses in particular science questions **SQ51** (Coupled litho-, atmo-, iono- and mesosphere), **SQ45** (Climate sensitivity), and **SQ46** (Earth energy imbalance) ((ESA, 2024), pp. 36–37).

Regarding the Areas of Action in ESA’s EO Science Strategy, Keystone relates directly to **Area of Action A1 “Frontier science and discovery”** ((ESA, 2024), pp. 17–21) as it would provide for the first time new observations and improvement to models (SG.1–SG.3). In addition, there is a strong link of Keystone to **Area of Action A2 “From Science to societal benefits”** ((ESA, 2024), pp. 17–21), most notably as Keystone would provide an observational basis for the accurate determination of the satellite drag and lifetime of satellites, as in SG.3. Keystone addresses directly **A4 “Reducing critical observational gaps”** ((ESA, 2024), pp. 21–25): the mission provides the first global, vertically-resolved and direct observations of atomic oxygen concentrations, i.e. the key constituent of the MTS (SG.1–SG.2), thus providing critical knowledge for understanding and quantitatively modelling this transition region between atmosphere and space.

Keystone’s holistic approach is not limited to its Science Goals as listed in Section 3.2, but extends to the observational strategies, which rely on integrated advanced measurement and analysis techniques. The mission datasets are designed for seamless synergy with other space- and ground-based observations, as well as model approaches that provide comprehensive whole-atmosphere and Earth system perspectives. This approach aligns with ESA’s new EO Science Strategy, which explicitly emphasises the **development of novel sensor technologies** and the **exploitation of multi-sensor data** as key research avenues for advancing a comprehensive understanding of the Earth system ((ESA, 2024), p. 12).

3.4. Mission Objectives

To achieve the Science Goals, the Keystone mission needs to achieve four Mission Objectives (MOs):

MO.1: MTS Composition Profiles

To observe vertical profiles of atomic oxygen and a wide range of important trace gases including O_3 , CO_2 , NO and OH , and metallic species (e.g. Mg , Mg^+), as well as noctilucent cloud properties. These gases are necessary to determine the density, thermal balance and photochemistry in the MTS.

MO.2: Radiative Energy Balance

To observe coincident IR and UV-Vis emissions, vital for constraining radiative energy balance and validating models of the MTS.

MO.3: Temperature Profiles

To retrieve kinetic temperature profiles from THz, IR, and UV emissions to characterise atmospheric structure and support dynamic analyses.

MO.4: LOS Neutral Wind Profiles

To observe line-of-sight neutral wind profiles from Doppler shifts in THz emission lines to constrain constituent transport and ion-neutral coupling.

3.5. Tracing of Science Goals to Mission Objectives

Given that the Mesosphere-Thermosphere System is governed by interconnected chemical, thermal, and dynamic processes, no single Science Goal can be achieved through an isolated measurement. Therefore, the mission architecture dictates that all three Science Goals strictly depend on the simultaneous and combined fulfilment of all four Mission Objectives.

SG.1 serves as the foundational scientific pillar of the mission. Establishing the complete thermodynamic and chemical state of the MTS natively requires mapping the absolute abundance of atomic oxygen alongside other trace gases, including metallic species (MO.1). However, composition alone provides an incomplete picture. To truly characterise the region and resolve open issues regarding upper atmospheric thermal cooling, these compositional profiles must be integrated with coincident observations of the radiative energy balance (MO.2) and high-resolution kinetic temperature profiles (MO.3). Furthermore, capturing line-of-sight neutral winds (MO.4) is essential to contextualise how these species are physically distributed, providing the first fully constrained, baseline characterisation of the MTS.

Building upon this baseline, SG.2 investigates the highly dynamic processes that perturb the MTS from above (space weather) and below (atmospheric waves). Tracking this multi-scale coupling demands a simultaneous, multi-parameter view of the environment. The transport of energy and momentum via gravity waves, tides, and inter-hemispheric circulation can only be accurately quantified by directly observing the physical movement of the atmosphere via neutral wind profiles (MO.4) and tracking the resulting structural changes in local kinetic temperatures (MO.3). At the same time, the chemical signatures of these dynamics, as well as the intrusion of energetic particles from space weather events, must be traced using the vertical profiles of atmospheric constituents (MO.1) and their corresponding radiative emissions (MO.2).

Ultimately, SG.3 translates this fundamental physics into tangible socio-economic impact. To transition next-generation whole-atmosphere models from static climatologies to highly predictive, physics-based forecasting tools, they must assimilate a complete thermodynamic and dynamic state. The accurate prediction of thermospheric mass density, which dictates satellite aerodynamic drag, collision avoidance, and orbital lifetimes, relies entirely on assimilating absolute atomic oxygen distributions (MO.1), resolving the local radiative energy budget (MO.2), and mapping the precise thermal structure of the upper atmosphere (MO.3). Furthermore, integrating these parameters with global neutral wind fields (MO.4) captures the constituent transport and ion-neutral coupling necessary to build the robust forecasting frameworks required to safeguard modern space infrastructure and the rapidly expanding Very Low Earth Orbit sector.

3.6. Evolution With Respect to the EE12 Proposal

The scientific goals and mission objectives of Keystone have matured during Phase 0 into a convincing and self-consistent ensemble. At the proposal stage, several ideas for optional measurement capabilities have been suggested to be further studied in Phase 0. Prime examples of these were the question whether vector winds are required (thus requiring orthogonal observations), or the need for a precessing orbit with variable local times to study time-variable atmospheric tides. Dedicated sensitivity assessments and feasibility studies, combined with a thorough prioritisation of competing mission requirements,

have now provided clarity on these options.

Vector Winds

The proposal had identified the possibility of vector wind observations from THz measurements in two sideways viewing directions, similar to a capability targeted by the SMILES-2 mission concept proposed by (Shiotani et al., 2019) and (Baron et al., 2019). Detailed analyses have shown that the implementation of such a capability is challenging and that the scientific merit, relying on observations of the exact same air parcels, is limited. Line-of-sight observations of winds, particularly in combination with temperature observations, provide strong constraints on the full wind field. Therefore, vertical profiles of line-of-sight wind observations acquired in this mode can be readily exploited in models using well-established data assimilation techniques, as discussed in Section 5.3, and are sufficient to constrain transport models (MO.4). An observation strategy that keeps the lines of sight close to the orbital plane is beneficial from a sampling point of view. Therefore, ALT viewing is now taken as the main observation mode for Keystone.

Local Observation Time

The proposal expressed a preference for a variable local observation time (Local Time at Ascending Node, LTAN) enabled by a precessing orbit in order to study atmospheric tidal modes with varying phases and seasonal cycles. However, a comprehensive trade-off analysis of various scientific and technical aspects led to the choice of a Sun-Synchronous Orbit (SSO) with a fixed LTAN. To achieve an LTAN drift fast enough to resolve tidal dynamics, the orbital inclination must be significantly lowered, which sacrifices coverage of the polar and auroral regions. Because these are the primary regions for observing geospace forcing and space weather impacts, capturing them via an SSO was prioritised for the mission's core scientific objectives SG.1 (Composition) and SG.2 (Coupling). Atmospheric tidal modes (part of SG.2) would instead be studied exploiting the synergy of complementary data from Keystone and ground-based instruments as outlined in Section 8.1. Keystone observations capture the large-scale horizontal context with fixed LTAN. A range of ground-based observations sample fast temporal evolution of the MTS in a limited horizontal domain centered on the ground station. Combining near-instantaneous global coverage from satellite with near-real-time temporal resolution from ground-based plays to the individual strengths of each techniques. Lastly, an SSO greatly simplifies the payload design, particularly regarding power regulation and thermal stability, while optimising the launcher compatibility choice.

Observables

Some minor changes to the set of observables have resulted from the Phase 0 studies. The push for redundant measurements of the same species by different payloads has been relaxed, which has little to no impact on the mission objectives, but simplifies (and therefore re-risks) the payload. The focus on the ionosphere is well covered by the UV-Vis instrument, so the THz observation of NO^+ , which would have unnecessarily complicated the payload design, have been waived. On the other hand, Lithium has been identified as a detectable product in the UV-Vis, which is a very powerful indicator for the ablation of satellite and rocket debris in the MTS.

Observation Modes

The Keystone observation modes have been optimised, and additional campaign modes added. The scan range of the limb-scan was raised, removing stratospheric views (30 to 50 km) where no atomic oxygen is present. In return, the top of the limb scan now includes a deeper cross-section of the thermosphere (150 to 250 km). This extended range provides unique observations of trends in thermospheric temperature, atomic oxygen density, and winds, while also enabling the direct observation of the O^+ ion, which is highly valuable for understanding ion-neutral coupling and broader ionospheric science.

4. MISSION REQUIREMENTS

In this chapter, the Keystone Mission Requirements are presented: observation (Level 2) requirements are covered in Section 4.1; requirements on spatial and temporal resolution and sampling are discussed in Section 4.2; requirements on geographic coverage, mission lifetime and data latency are discussed in Section 4.3; measurement (Level 1) requirements are addressed in Section 4.4. Furthermore, in the chapter observation and mission-level requirements are traced to the Mission Objectives (see Section 3.4). The tracing between L1 and L2 requirements is elaborated later in the report (Chapter 6). It is noted, that the term ‘Goal’ (G) is used to denote non-mandatory requirements, towards which the implementation shall strive; all other requirements (sometimes labelled as ‘Threshold’ (T), for clarity) are considered mandatory for the mission.

4.1. Observables

In order to fulfil its Mission Objectives (MO.1 to MO.4, Section 3.4) and, therefore, to explore the MTS (i.e., to establish a complete picture of the MTS, and obtain sufficient information to study the complex interplay of energies and dynamics within it), Keystone must measure a large number of geophysical observables (L2 products), listed in Table 4.1.

The first column of the table lists the Level 2 (L2) observables along with their associated metrics (e.g. Number Density (ND), Volume Emission Rate (VER), Volume Mixing Ratio (VMR), or others). First and foremost on the list is the abundance of O, the missing Keystone measurement of the MTS (and arguably the atmosphere). To quantify the chemical reactions around O formation and destruction, OH and O₂ are needed. NO (and OH) serve as proxies of space weather forcing, affecting O₃ at lower altitudes. Finally, tracer species CO and H₂O are proxies for MTS variability due to long range transport. Measuring abundance profiles of these trace gases is MO.1. Direct measurements of MTS winds (MO.4) also help understand dynamics and transport. To understand the thermal heat loss of greenhouse gases (on collision with O) the infrared emissions in the CO₂, NO, and O₃ bands are needed. To fully understand the photochemistry, UV-Vis airglow of the (excited states) of O, O⁺, O₂ are needed. Both of these support MO.2. Metals like Mg/Mg⁺, Na, Li, K, and Fe would provide information about ionosphere-to-neutral atmosphere interactions, and how the MTS altered by (increasing numbers of) rocket launches and de-orbiting debris (MO.1). Finally, Temperature (MO.3) is a key observable that supports all science. These have never been measured collectively by a single mission. Keystone’s fathoming of the MTS is unprecedented.

The second column specifies the uncertainty threshold for each observable, at specific altitudes or altitude ranges. The uncertainty requirement set for a given observable is driven by the need to resolve specific target variabilities. The selection of the target variabilities considered is guided by the Keystone Mission Objectives and includes diurnal and seasonal cycles, and responses to geophysical phenomena such as solar storms. Target variabilities have been estimated on the basis of model simulations (using WACCM-X, see Section 6.1). Diurnal variations represent the temporally (over a month of simulation data) and latitudinally averaged difference in each constituent between noon and midnight in a quiescent conditions. Seasonal variations represent the temporally and zonally averaged difference between the northern (>24°N) and southern (>24°S) hemispheres for each constituent in the same simulation. Finally, the space weather (storm) variations represent the latitudinally averaged change in each constituent between a quiescent period before the storm (with a geomagnetic disturbance severity index $K_p = 2$) and the peak of the storm ($K_p = 9$) at 0°N in the Storm scenario. Figure 4.1 shows that with the L2 uncertainty levels specified in Table 4.1 (dashed lines) the signatures of the target variabilities (solid lines) are resolved, except for CO₂. However, this is not critical for two reasons: Keystone cannot resolve the CO₂ diurnal variability since CO₂ would not be observed at night, and solar storm impacts are not significant

within the target altitude range. Instead, the relevance lies in the seasonal variability in the vicinity of the shifting altitude of the homopause (90–110km), which reflects the complex balance between large-scale dynamics, molecular diffusion and turbulent mixing. Below 80–85km, CO₂ is well mixed and already well characterised by other sources.

It is noted that in many cases the combination of observations (based on THz, IR, and UV-Vis) is needed to meet this objective. Next, it is discussed in more details whether the required Level 2 uncertainty is sufficient to detect the natural variability – caused by, e.g. gravity waves and planetary waves – in the O green line and O₂ A-band VER profiles to be observed with the UV-Vis payload. For this purpose the O green line and O₂ A-band volume emission rate profiles were calculated with the photochemical models by Lednyts'kyy et al. (2015) and McDade et al. (1986), respectively, based on a 2-week simulation with WACCM-X. Figure 4.2 displays these results for the green line in the left panel and for the A-band in the right panel. The blue-shaded range corresponds to the $\pm 1\text{-}\sigma$ interval, the green shading to the $\pm 3\text{-}\sigma$ interval. The grey vertical lines and grey shaded areas indicate the Level 2 requirement for the uncertainty of the green line and the A-band (i.e. 20% of the VER at the peak of the VER-profile). As a conclusion, the variability in the VER profiles of these two emissions can be resolved.

The following column indicates the vertical range to be covered for each Keystone observable. These ranges are defined accounting for the domains in which constituents are present and for the natural variability of the observable as discussed above and illustrated in Figure 4.4. The remaining columns specify the observation method (the measurable feature the observation is based upon), the observation conditions (day, night, or both), and the Mission Objective(s) addressed by the observation. While species with dramatic diurnal variations, such as Temperature and O must be measured both during day and night (as indeed they are), some UV-Vis products only appear during day and some others only at night.

4.2. Resolution and Sampling

Keystone observes the MTS based on measurements of limb radiances, as illustrated in Figure 4.3

Figure 4.3: Nominal along-track limb-sounding geometry and scanning (Credit: P. Martín-Iglesias).

4.2.1. Vertical Resolution and Pointing

Vertical resolution is an important parameter for all limb observations of the atmosphere. Sufficient vertical resolution of the three Keystone payloads is particularly important in the mesopause region, where

L2 Observable		Uncertainty	Range [km]	Measurement	Day/Night	Objective(s)
Atomic oxygen						
O	ND	30% below 120 km; 10% above 120 km	100–250	THz emission	d+n	MO.1
	ND	20% @ ND peak	70–115	Vis emission (O and O ₂ airglow)	d+n	MO.1
	VER	20% @ VER peak	70–250	Vis emission, red line (¹ D– ³ P)	d+n	MO.2
	VER	20% @ VER peak	70–115	Vis emission, green line (¹ S– ¹ D)	d+n	MO.2
O⁺	VER	30%	150–250	Vis emission	d	MO.2
Molecular species and trace gases						
O₂	ND	15%	50–120	THz emission	d+n	MO.1
	VER	20%	70–130	Vis emission (O ₂ A band, b–X)	d+n	MO.2
O₃	VER	5%	50–100	IR emission	d+n	MO.2
	VMR	10% @ 50–70 km; 20% @ 75–95 km; 25% @ 100 km	50–100	IR emission	d+n	MO.1
OH	ND	20%	50–80	THz emission	d+n	MO.1
	VER	20%	70–100	Vis emission (Meinel)	n	MO.2
H₂O	ND	25%	50–100	THz emission	d+n	MO.1
NO	ND	20% between 100 and 110 km; 50% elsewhere	90–130	THz emission	d+n	MO.1
	VER	20% @ 140 km; 30% @ 150 km	50–170	IR emission	d+n	MO.2
	ND	20%	85–105	Vis emission	n	MO.2
CO	ND	10% below 110 km; 30% above 110 km	50–130	THz emission	d+n	MO.1
CO₂	VER	10%	70–120	IR emission	d+n	MO.2
	VMR	35% @ 70 km; 15% @ 90 km; 30% @ 110 km	70–120	IR emission	d	MO.1
Metals						
Mg	ND	20% @ ND peak *	70–130	UV	d	MO.1
Mg⁺	ND	20% @ ND peak *	70–130	UV	d	MO.1
Na	ND	20% @ ND peak	80–105	Vis	d+n	MO.1
Li	ND	20% @ ND peak **	80–100	Vis	d	MO.1
K	ND	20% @ ND peak	80–100	Vis	d	MO.1
Fe	ND	30% @ ND peak	70–120	Vis	d	MO.1
State variables						
Wind	LOS component	20 m s ⁻¹ below 150 km; 50 m s ⁻¹ above 150 km	50–250	Doppler shift THz emission	d+n	MO.4
Temperature		5 K below 100 km; 40 K @ 100–150 km; 100 K above 150 km	50–250	THz emission	d+n	MO.3
		2 K @ 60 km; 5 K @ 90 km; 30 K @ 110 km	50–110	IR emission	d+n	MO.3
Pressure		10 K	80–105	O ₂ A-band	d+n	MO.3
		15%	50–85	THz emission	d+n	MO.1, MO.2, MO.3, MO.4
Noctilucent clouds						
Noctilucent clouds	Particle size	10 nm mode radius @ peak LOS Optical Thick- ness	75–90	UV/Vis scattering	d	MO.1
	Ice mass	30%	75–90	UV/Vis scattering	d	MO.1
	Occurrence frequency	20%	75–90	UV/Vis scattering	d	MO.1

Table 4.1: Keystone observables along with their associated metrics (e.g. Number Density (ND), Volume Emission Rate (VER), Volume Mixing Ratio (VMR), or others), altitude range and product uncertainty requirements (for single profiles (no marker), daily zonal averages (*), monthly averages (**)), measurement basis, and tracing to Mission Objectives (Section 3.4).

Figure 4.1: Target variability of some observed constituents (solid lines) compared with observation uncertainty requirements (dashed lines) as specified in Table 4.1. Target variabilities include diurnal (blue) and seasonal cycles (yellow), and space weather events (green). Observations based on THz, IR, and UV-Vis measurements are shown as purple, black and red, respectively (Credits: F. Sainsbury-Martinez, J. Dodd).

Figure 4.2: Variability of the oxygen green line (left panel) and O₂ A-band (right panel) VER profiles based on WACCM-X simulations covering 2 weeks. The blue and green ranges display the 1- σ and 3- σ intervals, respectively (Credits: F. Wrana, C. von Savigny).

Figure 4.4: Altitude coverage envisaged for Keystone observations of MTS state variables, key constituents and emissions. Shown to the right are the tangent altitudes covered by the five nominal Keystone operation modes (Table 4.2) (Credit: J. Gumbel).

important species and thermal/non-thermal emissions occur in layers with thicknesses of about 8–10 km. Examples of these layers are the airglow emissions by atomic oxygen, Na and Fe, or the O and O₃ concentration profiles. Features of the thermosphere are vertically smoothly distributed; hence, vertical resolution requirements for thermospheric altitudes are more relaxed compared to the mesopause region. Therefore, different vertical resolution requirements are posed for a set of altitude ranges: 5 km in [50–110 km], 10 km in [110–150 km], and 25 km in [150–250 km] for a ‘Standard Operational’ mode, and 2.5 km in [70–110 km] for a ‘Zoom Vertical’ mode. The modes are introduced in Section 4.2.3. For the UV-Vis and the IR payloads of Keystone dedicated goal requirement on vertical resolution is set to 2.5 km. Vertical re-sampling operations must be possible without significant interpolation errors; therefore, the vertical sampling distance is required to be smaller than the resolution increment by a factor of 2.5. During its mission lifetime Keystone mission aims at observing the full vertical domain of the MTS (as defined in Section 2.1) and hence is required to be able to cover a vertical range from 50 km to 250 km. The observation modes (Section 4.2.3) cover specific parts of this range.

Accurate knowledge of the tangent height is needed to interpret the vertical profile data, in particularly in the mesopause region, where important species and thermal/non-thermal emissions occur in layers. Therefore, a Tangent Height (TH) knowledge is requirement to be better than 100 m (G) and 400 m (T) below 110 km and 400 m above 110 km.

4.2.2. Spatial and Temporal Sampling

Since the mesosphere and lower thermosphere exhibit strong variability over a wide range of horizontal and temporal scales, appropriate spatial and temporal sampling are fundamentally important to delivering Keystone’s mission. To meet the Science Goals and Mission Objectives, the chosen observing strategy must provide sampling that is dense enough to resolve geophysical structure, rapid enough to avoid excessive smearing of co-located measurements, and sufficiently repeatable to support both event-scale

Figure 4.5: Global sampling within 3 days for observations in ALT viewing direction with an ALT sampling distance of 1000 km. Tangent points (dots) at a tangent height of 100 km are depicted distinguishing daytime (red) and nighttime (blue) observations acquired in ascending and descending parts of the orbits (lines) (Credit: K. Palmer).

analyses and longer-term products.

A horizontal resolution and sampling distance on the order of 1,000 km (or 9° latitude) is sufficient to capture the structure of trace gas fields and to make a significant step in improvement over the current state of the art. This holds true for all the observables in Table 4.1, but is especially poignant for O, where no direct measurements currently exist, meaning that even a low-resolution data product is a real game changer. Keystone aims at observing the MTS response to gravity wave forcing, but does not need to resolve signatures of individual gravity waves, which exhibit variability on much shorter horizontal scales. In practise, Keystone observations would be assimilated in atmospheric models, so the final spatial resolution at data Level 3 would exceed the L2 sampling distance.

Trace gas distributions of species like O show intricate small-scale features on top of the shape of their global distribution (also seen in Figure 2.2). Through flexible observation modes described in Section 4.2.3 Keystone would be able to zoom in on these features during dedicated campaigns, effectively doubling its horizontal resolution by curtailing the vertical scan range. The scientific requirements on horizontal sampling follow this logic: In the Standard Operational mode, covering the full altitude range from 70 km to 250 km, an ALT horizontal sampling distance smaller than 800 (G)/1250 (T) km is required. In campaign modes, i.e., focussing on the peak ND layer of O from 70 to 110 km, tighter limits of 400 (G)/550 (T) km are set for the ALT sampling distance, in order to reveal finer details, which would allow to validate the more refined physical models.

The horizontal sampling of Keystone at a global scale is illustrated considering the tangent points of all measurements at a reference altitude of 100 km acquired during a three-days period, for an ALT sampling distance of 1,000 km in Figure 4.5. During each orbit, day-time and night-time measurements are observed due to the Local Time of the Ascending Node of the orbit, 10:00.

4.2.3. Observation Modes

Keystone needs the flexibility to operate in various observation modes since it is not possible to satisfy all observational needs in terms of vertical range, ALT sampling distance, and uncertainty targets at once. A set of modes with specific vertical ranges and ALT sampling distances have been defined, including a standard operational mode and various campaign modes with specific along-track (ALT) sampling distances and vertical ranges (see Table 4.2). The introduction of campaign modes addresses the breadth of the opportunity to “zoom in” on specific altitude ranges of interest. In zoom modes, the narrower altitude coverage is traded off against a shorter scan duration, which means improved horizontal sampling.

Mode ID	Range [km]	Vertical resolution [km]	Vertical sampling [km]	ALT sampling [km]	Viewing	Driving species
Zoom Vertical	70–110	2.5	1	800	ALT	O (THz)
Zoom Horizontal	70–110	5	2	400 (G) 550 (T)	ALT	O (THz), UV-Vis, IR
Deep	50–150	5 in [50–110] 10 in [110–150]	2 in [50–110] 4 in [110–150]	1000	ALT	All
Standard Operational	70–250	5 in [70–110] 10 in [110–150] 25 in [150–250]	2 in [70–110] 4 in [110–150] 10 in [150–250]	800 (G) 1250 (T)	ALT	All
Sideways Wind^{a,b}	70–110	Not prescribed	2	Not prescribed	Sideways	O (THz)

^a One-dimensional wind profiles shall be retrieved from measurements within all other operation modes in the ALT direction. This specific mode captures additional one-dimensional wind profiles from an across-track viewing direction to retrieve other wind components.

^b The system shall be capable of measuring wind speeds in the range 0–100 m s⁻¹.

Table 4.2: *Keystone operation modes. These modes trade off scan duration (vertical range and sampling density) against horizontal resolution. These modes are not final, they define the minimal envelope that campaign modes must allow. It is a measurement requirement that observation modes can be switched on command.*

The ‘Standard Operational’ mode encompasses the mesosphere and thermosphere above 70 km where the most important processes related to atomic oxygen take place. The ‘Zoom Vertical’ mode is ideally suited for limb observations around the mesopause, allowing for a proper vertical sampling of the layered phenomena in this atmospheric region. The narrower altitude range is traded off against a shorter scan duration, which means improved horizontal sampling. The ‘Zoom Horizontal’ mode aims at achieving observations with a short horizontal sampling distance (albeit with a smaller altitude range). The ‘Deep’ mode encompasses the entire mesosphere starting from its lower boundary near 50 km and covers the lower thermosphere. The ‘Sideways Wind’ mode allows observing across-track wind components. It is noted that the time spent in this mode is limited; limitations depend on orbital illumination conditions as discussed in Section 7.1.2.

As a true explorer, Keystone may encounter unexpected features in flight; it may be desirable to adapt the observational focus during its mission lifetime. Therefore, it is required that the modes can be adapted in flight (within the range marked out by the pre-defined modes). Nominally an observation plan can be uploaded and updated once per day. Within the observation plan several modes can be planned for the following day(s) with mode switches occurring on a sub-orbital frequency if necessary.

4.3. Coverage and Mission Lifetime

In Chapter 2 it has been presented that no direct measurements of O exist for the MTS and a global picture is therefore needed. Keystone is not about patching up gaps in existing knowledge, but establishing a first truth. Furthermore, the scientific processes that the mission aims to study cover all latitudes. QBO and MJO happen at the equator to midlatitudes, solar forcing is strongest in the auroral rings around ~80 N/S, strong meridional MTS winds reach the polar regions, and large scale transport happens at all latitudes.

Aiming at observing the MTS at all latitudes and longitudes, Keystone is required to acquire a global ‘image’ within 3 days. This 3-day requirement is aligned with the repeat cycle of an SSO. Such an image is composed of the observations acquired during ~45 orbits (see Figure 7.4). Coverage and sampling pattern of a single Keystone orbit is illustrated in Figure 7.5. Requirements are set such that worst case AXT and ALT horizontal sampling distance are on the same order: ~1000 km ACT at the equator, 800 (G)/1250 (T) ALT for the “Standard Operational” mode (see 4.2.2) for all tangent heights.

There is no scientific need for an instantaneous snapshot of the global distribution of the observables.

This would only matter for the study of fast migrating global tides, which are not a direct observable of Keystone. As explained in Chapter 5.3 high-temporal resolution tidal information can be obtained from existing networks of ground-based observations. Keystone measurements would be assimilated as 4D data points in atmospheric models, so again no instantaneous global coverage is required.

The Keystone satellite is designed for a nominal operational lifetime of 3 years (T), which is sufficient to fulfil the Mission Objectives (Section 3.4) and to investigate the range of transient processes described in Chapter 2, including diurnal and seasonal variability, QBO and MJO cycles, as well as space weather events. A longer operational lifetime would be highly desirable, as it would enable a more robust characterisation of long-term variability in the context of climate change and solar forcing.

4.4. Measurements

In order to fulfil the observation requirements described in Section 4.1 and to reach the science goals discussed in Chapter 3 measurements with a single instrument in a single spectral range are not sufficient. The novel and unique atomic oxygen profile observations require the capability to carry out measurements in the THz spectral range. For thermal radiance fluxes and several essential atmospheric constituents observations in the IR are required. In addition, some of the required chemical constituents can only be observed in the UV-Vis. For these reasons, Keystone consists of three highly complementary payloads providing simultaneous measurements in the THz, IR and UV-Vis spectral regions. Figure 4.6 illustrates the top-down traceability from Mission Objectives to L2 observables (grouped by species) and observation method (grouped by spectral range). The THz and UV-Vis instruments are spectrometers covering specific wavelength ranges in a continuous way, while the IR instrument is a multi-channel radiometer.

Figure 4.6: Keystone science traceability diagram linking Mission Objectives, as specified in Section 3.4, to L2 Observables grouped by species, and corresponding instrument classes, as specified in Table 4.1 (Credits: P. Martín-Iglesias, E. Iorfida).

The observational requirements and the science goals require the provision of vertical profiles of key chemical species and temperature in the MTS with a relatively high vertical resolution. This is because several observables, e.g. O and Temperature, have very strong vertical gradients in the MTS. O evolves from being absent at ~ 90 km to becoming the dominant species at ~ 120 km, with an almost binary diurnal cycle. The required vertical resolutions of between one to a couple of kilometres can only be achieved with a limb viewing geometry (illustrated in Figure 4.3), which is a well established technique, with several heritage missions in the MW, IR and UV-Vis spectral regions. The novel combination of the three instruments makes Keystone a unique Earth observation mission. Keystone would be capable of measuring limb radiances during the day and night using the THz, IR and UV-Vis instruments, to provide the targeted day and night observations.

Requirements on the co-registration of these instruments are elaborated in Section 4.4.1. The instrument-specific measurement requirements are introduced in Section 4.4.2 for the THz, Section 4.4.3 for the IR, and Section 4.4.4 for the UV-Vis instruments.

4.4.1. Co-registration

Keystone needs to provide simultaneous and co-located measurements of the MTS composition, temperature and wind (temporal co-registration) in order to obtain the targeted synergies: To understand the energy balance and thermal structure of the MTS, co-located measurements of the thermal IR heat loss, as well as the airglow emissions in UV and Visible are essential. The UV-Vis gives information about metals, which enables the studying of ionosphere-neutral atmosphere connections. All payloads contribute to temperature profiling, and the Doppler shift in THz spectral lines contains information on LOS winds. Therefore it is required that the lines of sight of the three payloads are aligned. Because the atmosphere is stratified, vertical co-location is more important than horizontal co-location. The co-location lengths are informed by the horizontal gradients in the 3D fields of the geophysical variables under test. In other words, they inform how far two air parcels can be separated horizontally to still be considered equivalent.

When viewing in a forward direction, the Along LOS horizontal mis-registration between any pair of spectral samples shall be smaller than 20 km (G) / 200 km (T). When viewing in a forward direction the Across LOS horizontal mis-registration at tangent point between any pair of spectral samples shall be smaller than 2 km (G) / 55 km (T). The vertical co-registration between limb measurements in any pair of spectral samples shall be known within 100 m (G) and 400 m (T) below 110 km and 400 m above 110 km.

4.4.2. Terahertz Measurements

THz measurements are used in order to retrieve concentrations of O, O₂, OH, H₂O, CO, and NO, as well as temperature, pressure, and wind would be observed at altitudes between 50 and 250 km (square brackets denote concentrations in number density, e.g. '[A]' for species A).

Spectral Range: It is required that at least one strong line of each of these target species (O, O₂, OH, H₂O, CO, NO) is covered and spectrally resolved by the THz measurements. For H₂O, additionally, coverage of a weak line is required, in order to account for saturation (due to absorption of light by H₂O itself). The implementation concepts introduced in Chapter 7 satisfy these needs by covering the frequency range from 1.1 to 2.1 THz. The THz lines of the target species in this spectral range are schematically depicted in Figure 4.7, which include the O line near 2.06 THz and multiple lines for each of the other species.

Spectral Resolution: High spectral resolution is needed such that both amplitude and shape of emission lines is resolved and information on abundance, temperature, pressure, and wind can be retrieved. A spectral resolution of 0.2 MHz is set as the threshold, to ensure dense sampling of the line shape (see

Figure 4.7: Schematic view of the THz emission lines in the spectral range from 1 to 2.1 THz. Atmospheric signal amplitudes at an arbitrary altitude of 70 km obtained from radiative transfer simulations are shown per species (colours) (Credits: P. Martín-Iglesias, P. B. Hansen).

Figure 4.8).

Spectral Sampling: An oversampling of ~ 2 is needed to meet the Nyquist sampling rate, which is needed for all spectral operations; commensurate requirements are set on the spectral sampling distances for the measurements of the O line and the other species.

Radiometric Noise: The radiometric noise requirements are driven by the L2 uncertainty: the contribution of radiometric noise to the L2 uncertainty must be limited leaving room for additional contributions from other error sources. The threshold Noise Equivalent Delta T ($NE\Delta T$) ranges from ~ 8 K at 1 THz to ~ 30 K at 2 THz, and follows a linear relationship that accounts for the technical limitation of the class of sensor (see Chapter 7). This $NE\Delta T$ performance must be met for a reference spectral resolution of 0.2 MHz. A trade has been made giving priority to better spectral resolution at the cost of higher radiometric noise. This choice has been made to ensure that line shapes can be evaluated accurately in all cases, even if averaging may be needed to reduce the noise. The quantitative demonstration that the requirements on spectral range, resolution, and sampling as well as on radiometric noise are sufficient to meet the L2 uncertainty requirements for the THz target observables is presented in Chapter 6.

Figure 4.8: Simulated profile of the 2.06 THz transition of atomic oxygen measured at 120 km tangent height (black curve). A Gaussian with a FWHM of 10 MHz is also shown (orange/light-toned curve) (Credits: P. B. Hansen, H.-W. Hübers).

4.4.3. Infrared Measurements

The Keystone IR instrument would measure broadband radiance profiles across the seven channels specified in Table 4.3, and the requirements are mainly based on the proven SABER instrument heritage (Esplin et al., 2023).

CO₂ and NO act as primary drivers of radiative cooling in the mesosphere and lower thermosphere, emitting infrared region near 15 μ m and 5.3 μ m respectively. Their emission is governed by vibrational excitation and de-excitation processes driven by collisions with atomic oxygen. The IR2 and IR5 channels are specifically dedicated to measuring the emissions from CO₂ and NO and capture the majority of the

Channel	Emitter	L2 variable	λ_0 [μm]	$\tilde{\nu}_0$ [cm^{-1}]	$\Delta\lambda_{\text{FWHM}}$ [μm]	$\Delta\tilde{\nu}_{\text{FWHM}}$ [cm^{-1}]	NER [$\text{W m}^{-2} \text{sr}^{-1}$]
IR1	CO ₂ (Narrow)	P ₀	14.89	672	0.92	42	1.75E-04
IR2	CO ₂ (Wide)	T _k , CO ₂ cooling	15.19	658	4.01	178	2.80E-04
IR3 (optional)	H ₂ O (ice)	Clouds	11.85	844	2.03	146	TBD
IR4	O ₃	O ₃ VMR	9.34	1071	1.08	124	1.27E-05
IR5	NO	NO VER, NO cooling	5.27	1898	0.16	58	9.96E-06
IR6	CO ₂	CO ₂ VMR	4.24	2358	0.12	67	1.10E-05
IR7 (optional)	OH	OH VER	2.07	4831	0.29	680	4.70E-06

Table 4.3: Keystone infrared channels.

radiative output from these species in the same manner as Mlynczak et al. (2024) using SABER/TIMED. Figure 4.9 shows simulated limb radiance spectrum at 85 km tangent altitude, using an example equator daytime climatology for January and with the proposed Keystone IR2 (top left) and IR5 (bottom right) channels highlighted.

CO₂ emissions at 15 μm IR2 are also used to derive atmospheric temperature. Although this emission departs from LTE above the middle mesosphere, kinetic temperature retrieval remains possible provided that non-LTE effects are properly included in the radiative transfer model. Accurate temperature retrieval from the IR2 channel also requires prior knowledge of CO₂ abundance, which would be derived using the IR6 channel at 4.3 μm (Rezac et al., 2015). A simulated limb radiance spectrum for this channel is also shown in Figure 4.9. Using the measurements, the CO₂ VMR profile then provides useful constraints on the location of the homopause and, more generally, on vertical mixing processes in the upper atmosphere (Garcia et al., 2014).

One technique that has been used as an indirect proxy to infer atomic oxygen in the daytime mesosphere and lower thermosphere is based on ozone abundance, exploiting the photochemical equilibrium between O and O₃, in which ozone is produced via three-body recombination reactions and rapidly destroyed by photolysis and reactions with atomic oxygen (Mlynczak et al., 2013). To validate this approach

Figure 4.9: Limb radiance spectrum at 85 km highlighting Keystone infrared channels IR1 and IR2 (top left), IR4 (top right), IR6 (bottom left) and IR5 (bottom right). The main contributions to these channels originate from ro-vibrational transitions of CO₂, O₃, CO₂ and NO molecules, respectively (Credits: A. Knížek, M. García-Comas).

using Keystone's direct observations of the ground state emission of atomic oxygen with the THz instrument, the IR4 channel has been specifically designed to observe O₃ emissions at 9.3 μm, from which O₃ VMR can be retrieved. Again, a simulated radiance spectrum for this channel is shown in Figure 4.9 (top right). Notably, the channel extends up to 1136 cm⁻¹ (~8.8 μm), and contains an O₃ band centred around 1120 cm⁻¹ (~8.9 μm), which contributes a non-negligible fraction of the radiance to the overall channel, particularly at tangent altitudes below those simulated here.

The IR1 channel centred at 14.9 μm (top left panel of Figure 4.9) is used to derive a reference pressure in the lower mesosphere using the two-colour technique (Gille and House, 1971). The two remaining optional channels IR3 at 11.8 μm, and IR7 at 2.1 μm, are used, respectively, to monitor water ice to detect polar mesospheric clouds (García-Comas et al., 2016), and to indirectly derive atomic oxygen in the nighttime mesosphere and lower thermosphere using OH emissions as a proxy (Mlynczak et al., 2018).

Together with the corresponding Noise Equivalent Radiance (NER) in Table 4.3, these bandpasses are optimal to meet the geophysical parameter requirements illustrated in Table 4.1. A shift of the IR6 bandpass to shorter wavenumbers in comparison to SABER, aimed at reducing signal contamination from CO and OH, has been proposed for Keystone. In addition, the detectors proposed for Keystone by industry may have a reduced quantum efficiency for the IR2 upper-end wavelengths. Thus, the impact of narrowing the IR2 bandpass has been assessed in Chapter 6.

4.4.4. Ultraviolet-Visible Measurements

Most of the UV-Vis data products retrieved from measurements of airglow emissions — e.g. atomic oxygen concentration profiles from the O green line emission or Na, Mg and Fe profiles from the corresponding emissions — are based on absolute radiances and require a certain radiometric accuracy. The required upper limit of absolute radiometric errors of the limb radiances depends on the radiances themselves and is <5% for limb radiances down to 10⁸ photons s⁻¹ cm⁻² sr⁻¹ nm⁻¹ and 20% for lower

Species/Parameter	Wavelength nm	Intensity of signature Rayleigh / nm
O green line VER	557.7	15 × 10 ³
O red line VER	630.0, 630.6	1 – 10 × 10 ³
O ⁺ VER	732	0.5 – 3 × 10 ³
[O] from green line	557.7	15 × 10 ³
O ₂ A-band VER	757 – 770	10 – 1000 × 10 ³
[O] from O ₂	757 – 770	10 – 1000 × 10 ³
OH Meinel VER	600 – 800	0.5 × 10 ³
[NO]	500 – 600	0.5 × 10 ³
[Mg]	285.2	10 × 10 ³
[Mg ⁺]	279.6, 280.4	10 × 10 ³
[Na]	589.9	1 – 50 × 10 ³
[Li]	670.9	0.5 × 10 ³
[K]	557.5	5 × 10 ³
[Fe]	372.0	3 × 10 ³
Temperature	757 – 770	10 – 1000 × 10 ³
NLC parameters	270 – 300	1 – 50 × 10 ⁶

Table 4.4: Spectral requirements for the UV-Vis instrument and typical intensities of the limb emissions. Units are Volume Emission Rates (VER) or concentrations (indicated via square brackets, e.g. '[A]' for species A). Table 4.1 lists which emissions are measured at daytime and/or nighttime.

radiances. With this radiometric noise performances a number of products are retrieved on a single scan basis, while others are retrieved based on daily averaged data, as indicated in Table 6.1.

UV-Vis data products typically require high relative spectral radiometric accuracy (on the 2% level), while a more relaxed absolute radiometric accuracy is acceptable. This is the case e.g. for retrievals of temperature profiles from the O₂ A-band emission, as they are based on the shape of the emission and not the absolute radiance values. The required spectral range of Keystone's UV-Vis payload is 240–800 nm (Goal) (270–775 nm, Threshold) and is determined by the spectral emission and absorption signatures to be observed. The threshold spectral range includes the majority of the planned spectral signatures (including the airglow emissions by O, O₂, Mg, Mg⁺, Fe, Na, K, OH and potentially Li as well as the absorption signatures by O₃ in the Huggins and part of the Hartley bands). The goal spectral range would in addition allow measuring the NO γ -bands in the UV that provide vertical profiles of [NO] in the mesopause region and lower thermosphere. As many of the emission signatures to be observed are single line atomic electronic transitions, a spectral resolution (defined as the Full Width at Half Maximum (FWHM) of the Instrument Spectral Response Function (ISRF)) of better than 1 nm (Goal) and 2 nm (Threshold) is required. A spectral sampling ratio higher than 2.5 is required to ensure that the spectral content of the measurements is properly sampled and that spectral operations can be performed without spectral aliasing. Table 4.4 provides an overview of the requirements for the UV-Vis data products. Units are Volume Emission Rate (VER) or concentration (for species in square brackets). The last column lists the intensity (in Rayleigh nm⁻¹) of the emission signature (or in case of NLCs the scattering) for each data product. 1 Rayleigh (R) corresponds to 10⁶ photons s⁻¹ cm⁻². In terms of radiance, a value of 10³ R nm⁻¹ = 1 kR nm⁻¹ corresponds to about 0.8 × 10⁸ photons s⁻¹ cm⁻² sr⁻¹ nm⁻¹.

5. DATA PRODUCTS AND USAGE

This chapter provides an overview of the data products of the three Keystone instruments as well as brief descriptions of the data processing schemes for all instruments. In addition, examples of data usage – including the synergistic use data sets from the three instruments – and the anticipated user communities are discussed.

5.1. Data Products

The Keystone payloads provide measurements of limb radiation in three different spectral regions, i.e. the THz, IR and UV-Vis. The THz and UV-Vis instruments are spectrometers capable of measuring limb radiance spectra in specific wavelength ranges, while the IR instrument is a multi-channel radiometer. Apart from the spectral measurements, ancillary information on spacecraft position, attitude as well as tangent height for each instrument are crucial for further processing.

Keystone data products defined at this stage include:

- **Level 0 (L0):** Uncalibrated limb radiances (or limb radiance spectra) for all three payloads in digital units.
- **Level 1 (L1):** radiometrically and spectrally calibrated, as well as geolocated limb radiances. L1 data are processed based on L0 data by applying all relevant corrections (e.g. dark current correction, corrections from instrumental effects, attitude correction).
- **Level 2 (L2):** Profiles of temperature, pressure, abundance of trace constituents (as volume mixing ratio or number density), airglow emission rates, line-of-sight winds, as well as NLC (noctilucent cloud) particle size and ice mass. The schemes used for processing L2 data based on L1 data are briefly described in Section 5.2.

Higher-level data products that would be derived from Keystone L2 data are presented in Section 5.3.

5.2. Data Processing Schemes

5.2.1. THz Data Processing

THz L1 data are exploited to retrieve profiles of the number densities [O], [O₂], [H₂O], [OH], [CO], temperature and Line-Of-Sight (LOS) wind, and (at lower altitudes) also pressure (see Table 4.1) using a retrieval scheme developed by Hansen et al. (2025).

Information on the number density of a given species is retrieved from the amplitude of line emissions of the species in the measured spectra. For the THz emissions relevant to Keystone, LTE can be assumed (Sharma et al., 1994), which means that internal states are populated according to the Boltzmann distribution and that emitted radiation is directly related to the number density and temperature. Information on temperature and pressure is extracted from the line shape, which is influenced by temperature (Doppler) broadening, and (at lower altitudes) also pressure broadening. LOS-wind information is obtained by interpreting Doppler shifts of emission signatures. Typically, the related pieces of information are essentially independent since line shapes are fully resolved and lines are located at different spectral positions. However, information can be limited when signatures are too weak or optically thick (see assessment in Section 6.2.1). The retrieval is performed for a vertical scan in one go handling all selected atmospheric parameters simultaneously;

The retrieval problem is solved iteratively using a Gauss-Newton non-linear least-squares approach, since the relationship between atmospheric parameters and the measured spectra is non-linear. Vertical

profiles are parametrised based on third order b-splines. The retrieval scheme is illustrated in Figure 5.1: First the forward model is linearised at an initial state. Then an update of the state is computed based on the difference between measured and modelled spectra and the inverse model. The forward model is then linearised around this new state. This process is repeated until convergence. The scheme is configurable, such that target species can either be handled as part of the state vector, or retrieved separately.

Figure 5.1: Flowchart of the L2 retrieval from THz measurements. The retrieval starts by linearising a forward model around an initial estimate of the atmospheric state. The linearised problem is solved using least-squares to update the estimate, and the process is repeated iteratively until convergence. T refers to the temperature, P to the air pressure, and ATW to along track horizontal winds (Credits: M. Garcia-Comas, P. B. Hansen).

5.2.2. IR Data Processing

The L1 IR measurement data are exploited to retrieve profiles of the Volume Emission Rate (VER) of CO₂, NO, O₃; the Volume Mixing Ratio (VMR) of CO₂ and O₃; as well as temperature (see Table 4.1).

Figure 5.2 depicts the L2 retrieval scheme for the estimation of atmospheric temperature and CO₂ volume mixing ratio profiles from infrared limb radiance measurements in Channels IR2 and IR6. The retrieval is based on an iterative retrieval approach. The process is initialised using *a priori* temperature and CO₂ profiles, together with pressure at a reference altitude derived from the THz measurements. These inputs are employed in a hydrostatic reconstruction step to obtain a consistent pressure profile.

The reconstructed atmospheric state, combined with prescribed non-local thermodynamic equilibrium (NLTE) parameters, is provided to the NLTE model, which computes the population distributions of the CO₂ vibrational levels (NLTE to LTE population ratios) required for radiative transfer under non-LTE conditions. These quantities are subsequently used by the forward model to simulate the infrared limb

Figure 5.2: Flowchart of the L2 retrieval of temperature and CO₂ VMR profiles from IR2 and IR6 measurements. The O₃ volume mixing ratio is subsequently retrieved from IR4 following a similar scheme, without requiring the hydrostatic reconstruction step (dashed box) (Credit: M. Garcia-Comas).

radiance for the IR2 and IR6 channels, $L_{\text{sim,IR}}$, and to evaluate the corresponding Jacobians with respect to the state vector. The simulated radiance is compared with the calibrated measurements, L_{IR} , and the state vector is iteratively updated based on the measurement residuals within a regularised inversion framework. The update accounts for both the measurement uncertainties and prior constraints on the state vector, ensuring a stable solution. A convergence criterion is applied at each iteration. If the solution has not converged, the updated state vector is reintroduced into the loop for hydrostatic reconstruction and the procedure is repeated. Upon convergence, the final state vector provides the retrieved temperature and CO₂ profiles, together with their associated retrieval uncertainty estimates.

The inversion of ozone from the simultaneously acquired calibrated radiances in the IR4 channel follows the same approach. In this case, the retrieval is initialised using the temperature and pressure profiles derived in the previous step. The NLTE populations of the O₃ vibrational levels are then computed and used in the forward model to simulate the corresponding radiances. In contrast to the temperature and CO₂ retrieval, the hydrostatic reconstruction step is not required, as the pressure profile is already available. The state vector is iteratively updated based on the residuals between measured and simulated radiances within the same regularised inversion framework described above, and convergence is assessed using the same criteria. Nitric oxide and hydroxyl volume emission rates would be determined from the limb-viewing infrared radiance measurements in channels IR5 and IR7, respectively, assuming optically thin conditions, taking into account the line-of-sight geometry to retrieve altitude-resolved emission profiles.

Various high-heritage models are available for the NLTE and radiative transfer forward model calculations (Figure 5.2) that are then used for the retrieval of the L2 products. For example, the data product pipeline to provide temperature profiles and CO₂ VMR from IR2 and IR6 measurements, and O₃ from IR4 can be implemented by combining the NLTE model of Funke et al. (2012) with a radiative transfer forward model (e.g. Dudhia (2017)) and a retrieval algorithm (e.g. Rodgers (2000)).

5.2.3. UV-Vis Data Processing

The L1 UV-Vis measurement data are exploited to retrieve profiles of airglow emission rates from O, O⁺, OH, and O₂ emissions, as well as number densities of O₃, NO, and a variety of metals and metal ions (see Table 4.1).

The data products of the UV-Vis instrument require retrieval algorithms with different degrees of complexity. The VER profiles can typically be retrieved with relatively simple linear inversions (if self-absorption can be ignored, as e.g. for the O green line or the OH Meinel emissions) implemented using regularised least-squares techniques (e.g. von Savigny et al., 2012) or also optimal estimation. The following equation corresponds to the least-squares solution with regularization:

$$\underline{x} = (\underline{K}^T \underline{S}^{-1} \underline{K} + \gamma \cdot \underline{R}^T \underline{R})^{-1} \underline{S}^{-1} \underline{K}^T \underline{y} \quad (1)$$

\underline{K} is the pathlength matrix, \underline{x} the state vector containing the VERs for different altitudes, \underline{y} the measurement vector containing the LER (Limb emission rate), \underline{S} the measurement error covariance matrix, γ the regularization factor and \underline{R} the regularization matrix (e.g. von Savigny et al., 2012). For some of the dayglow and nightglow emissions self-absorption has to be considered (e.g. Na, Mg, Mg⁺, Fe, O₂ A-band), which is, e.g. described in Langowski et al. (2014) for Mg and Langowski et al. (2016) for Na. The species concentration retrievals from the VER profiles require the corresponding photochemical models to infer temperature from the O₂ A-band emission, [O] from the O green line as well as the O₂ A-band emissions, and [Na] profiles from the Na D-line nightglow emission. Figure 5.3 illustrates as an example the algorithm for the retrieval of Na concentration profiles from the Na D-line nightglow in the mesopause region. Note that the retrieval algorithms for [O] and most of the other metal species are very

Figure 5.3: Flowchart of the L2 retrieval of Na concentration profiles from UV-Vis measurements of the Na dayglow or nightglow emission. Na here serves as an example for other metal species to be retrieved (Credits: M. Garcia-Comas, C. von Savigny).

similar. The retrieval needs to be done in an iterative way, because the self-absorption of the Na D-line nightglow emission by Na is not negligible. The self-absorption correction can be implemented by modifying the pathlength matrix \mathbf{K} (blue box on the left). At each iteration step, an [Na] profile is determined based on a modified version of the Na nightglow excitation model by Chapman (1930) and used for an updated self-absorption correction. A convergence criterion needs to be specified that determines, when the iteration loop is terminated. The output of the scheme are Na concentration profiles together with the corresponding propagated random errors as well as smoothing errors. The parameter errors required for the full error budget need to be determined independently.

For the retrieval of [O] profiles from the O green line nightglow emission the Barth (McDade et al., 1986) transfer scheme would be used. For [O] retrievals from the O₂ A-band emission the corresponding excitation scheme based on the ETON rocket campaign can be used. Concentration profiles of NO are retrieved from the NO + O nightglow emission as described in von Savigny et al. (1999).

For some of the data products based on daytime limb-scatter measurements (mesospheric O₃ and pointing information) a radiative transfer model (RTM) is employed to simulate the limb-scattered solar radiation. In addition, a numerical inversion scheme based on optimal estimation (OE) or non-linear least-squares minimization is used. SCIATRAN (Mei et al., 2023) or Sasktran (Bourassa et al., 2008) are available to the community to simulate limb-scattered solar radiances. Algorithms to retrieve mesospheric O₃ profiles from UV limb-scatter measurements with SCIAMACHY on Envisat are, e.g. described by Rohen et al. (2005). Limb pointing retrievals in the UV-Vis spectral range are based on the so-called “knee” technique, which takes advantage of the shape of the limb radiance profiles in the UV spectral range as described in Kaiser et al. (2004).

The daytime limb-scatter measurements would also be used for the detection of NLCs and the determination of NLC particle size. NLCs are detected in limb-radiance profiles based on a threshold-gradient approach checking for radiance enhancements in the altitude range of NLCs (Robert et al., 2009). NLC particle size can be retrieved from limb-scatter measurements exploiting the spectral dependence of scattering by NLC particles. This is usually done in the UV spectral range at wavelengths below 300 nm. Here, the spectral dependence of the differential NLC scattering cross section can be simply determined by dividing the NLC-scattered limb radiance spectrum by the solar irradiance spectrum (von Savigny et al., 2004). The derived spectral dependence is then modelled using scattering theory (e.g. Discrete Dipole Approximation, T-matrix or Mie-theory) and the particle mode radius is retrieved. A particle size distribution (PSD) has to be assumed for the retrievals. Past studies employed a range of different PSDs (Dirac-functions, normal, log-normal, exponential and modified Gamma-distributions).

5.3. Data Usage

This section highlights the usage of Keystone data products in pursuit of the Keystone Science Goals, as presented in Section 3.2. Each one of the three Keystone instruments produces L2 data individually. Synergies between the data from the different payloads, enabled by simultaneous observations, are exploited at higher data level. Expected application of the Keystone L2 products are outlined here and examples of synergistic use cases are highlighted.

General Use of Keystone Level 2 Data (SG.1, SG.2, SG.3)

Keystone observations of vertical profiles of temperature, LOS winds and chemical constituents would be used by many scientific communities to improve the understanding of essential chemical, dynamical and radiative atmospheric processes (see also section 5.4). Keystone L2 data would allow studying dynamical effects on the MTS such as planetary wave perturbations, impacts of SSWs, the MJO, and gravity wave effects. Keystone's altitude coverage, extending to 250 km for several data products would allow investigating some of these effects in the thermosphere for the first time. Keystone would produce a unique data set to test and validate chemical models and airglow excitation schemes in the MTS. It would observe the atmospheric mass density profile in the thermosphere, which is of crucial importance for satellite drag and trajectory calculations as well as for the prediction of reentry times and locations of satellite debris. Keystone data are also extremely well suited to study effects of solar variability on the MTS, including the effects of the solar 27-day rotational cycle, CMEs (Coronal Mass Ejections) or coronal holes. With its unique capability to observe [O] profiles in the MTS globally and directly, Keystone would very likely provide fundamentally new insights into these processes. The following sections describe important examples of Keystone L2 data usage in more detail.

Estimating Thermospheric Density to be Used in Drag Models (SG.1, SG.3)

In the thermosphere, O and N₂ are the dominant atmospheric constituents comprising about 98% of the global mean atmospheric mass. Typically, the number density of O relative to N₂ increases with height. At altitudes above about 120 km the number density of O exceeds the number density of O₂. Above about 160–180 km, [O] also exceeds [N₂]. The atmospheric mass density can be estimated at altitudes above 150 km with an accuracy below 5% (during solar maximum even less, see, e.g. Emmert (2015)) by

$$\rho = [\text{O}] \times m_{\text{O}} + [\text{N}_2] \times m_{\text{N}_2}. \quad (2)$$

where m_{O} and m_{N_2} correspond the masses of O atoms and N₂ molecules, respectively. The higher the altitude the more accurate this estimate becomes, because the O mixing ratio increases with altitude. In order to apply Equation 2 the relative abundance of O and N₂ has to be known or estimated. One option is to use climatological or modelled profiles of the O/N₂ ratio. Figure 5.4 shows an example of derived density from O observations assuming a climatological O/N₂ ratio based on output from the WACCM model. Even using this climatology, over most latitudes the errors are less than the differences between the empirical models. This provides a key validation dataset for these models that are widely used for drag prediction.

However, the synergistic use of the Keystone THz and UV-Vis measurements allows retrieving N₂. While [O] is observed by the THz instrument, [N₂] can be inferred from the O⁺ volume emission rate observed in the visible near 732 nm: The chemical lifetime of the excited state of O⁺(²P) is short, which means that excitation rates equal loss rates. The primary excitation mechanism is photo-ionisation, which depends on the known solar spectrum, known absorption cross-sections, and [O] given by the THz observation. Losses are through spontaneous emission with the O⁺ volume emission rate observed in the visible, and through quenching by O and N₂. The latter depend on the number densities [O] and [N₂] and the respective quenching rates, for which estimates are available. [N₂] is the only unknown in this balance

Figure 5.4: Retrieved monthly mean atmospheric density (in g/cm^3) at 250 km based on WACCM-X O concentrations using a climatology of O/N_2 ratio. Error estimates are made by comparison to known WACCM-X densities. Also shown are the DTM-2020 and NRLMISIS 2.0 estimates of the density under the same solar and geomagnetic conditions (Credits: D. Marsh, F.Sainsbury-Martinez).

and can hence be inferred. Using the estimate for $[\text{N}_2]$ thus obtained, the estimate of ρ can be further refined without relying on the use of climatological profiles of the O/N_2 ratio. In summary, exploiting the synergy between the Keystone payloads would make an essential contribution to provide direct observations of the thermospheric mass density profile.

Numerical Weather Prediction Above the Stratopause (SG.3)

Assimilating data collected by Keystone provides the opportunity to perform initialised hindcasts of the whole atmosphere. Such studies would, for example, enable studies that investigate the predictability of the upper atmosphere. Currently, there is only rudimentary knowledge of how local time, season, and solar activity affect the predictability of the upper atmosphere. The data would also be needed to continue whole atmospheric reanalysis products, such as JAWARA (Koshin et al., 2025b), or to create new products, respectively. Such products enable significant advances in a broad range of upper-atmosphere science, ranging from questions about day-to-day variability, driven by the lower atmosphere, and storm time variations in the ionosphere and thermosphere. Data assimilation is also an important tool for model development, as the data assimilation increments can be used to identify locations of large model-observation discrepancies, which can then be systematically addressed. This approach allows an observationally informed estimate of parameters that enter parameterisation schemes of, e.g. gravity wave drag and eddy diffusion, which have large uncertainties, and without suitable observations can only be used as tuning parameters.

Constraining the $\text{CO}_2\text{-O}$ Collision Rate Coefficient by Combining THz O and IR CO_2 (SG.1, SG.3)

One of the key scientific milestones that the Keystone mission could achieve is the resolution of the long-standing uncertainty in the collisional rate coefficient between $\text{CO}_2(v_2)$ and O ($k_{\text{CO}_2\text{-O}}$), where v_2 refers to the CO_2 vibrational bending mode. Current estimates of $k_{\text{CO}_2\text{-O}}$ exhibit discrepancies of up to a factor of three between laboratory measurements and values inferred from atmospheric observations (e.g. Feofilov et al., 2012). Resolving this discrepancy, persisting for several decades, would have significant implications for the accurate quantification of CO_2 15 μm radiative cooling in the mesosphere and lower thermosphere, and consequently for its representation in climate and general circulation models. Keystone is uniquely positioned to address this issue by exploiting simultaneous observations of O density from the THz instrument and CO_2 15 μm VER from the IR instrument. These quantities are directly linked through their proportional dependence on $k_{\text{CO}_2\text{-O}}$, enabling a self-consistent observational constraint on this parameter under realistic atmospheric conditions.

Improving Photochemistry Models by Combining THz [O] with IR and UV-Vis Radiances (SG.1, SG.3)

A large part of the knowledge on the chemical composition of the mesopause region is based on the exploitation of airglow emissions. The global morphology of O in this region is, e.g. based heavily on satellite observations of the O green line and the O₂ A-band nightglow emissions (e.g. Kaufmann et al., 2014; Lednyts'kyi et al., 2015) or OH Meinel emissions (e.g. Mlynczak et al., 2013). The photochemical models describing the excitation of emitting states were tested using a limited number of rocket campaigns that also included direct [O] profile observations. However, a comprehensive validation of these models with global, direct, and long-term observations of [O] has not been carried out due to the lack of such observations. Keystone would be the first mission to provide these [O] profiles in the MTS. Figure 5.5 shows, as an example, simulations of the O green line, based on the photochemical model described in Lednyts'kyi et al. (2015) and with chemical composition and temperature profiles calculated with the WACCM-X model. Lednyts'kyi et al. (2015) also provide uncertainties for all reaction rate constants and transition probabilities of the photochemical model. The reaction rates and transition probabilities were randomly and independently varied within the $\pm 3\text{-}\sigma$ range and the model was run 300 times (individual blue lines). The red line shows the green line VER profile for unperturbed parameters. The VER values for the different realizations cover a range of a factor of 5, illustrating the great potential to further constrain models with independent and direct [O] observations. Note that the Keystone [O] observations in combination with the UV-Vis airglow measurements may also allow identifying currently unknown excitation pathways of different airglow emissions.

Between approximately 90 and 250 km, nitric oxide (NO) chemistry is governed by a transition from ion-molecule dominated processes in the lower thermosphere and mesosphere to a regime more influenced by atomic, EUV-driven neutral chemistry in the upper thermosphere. In the lower segment of this region (90–120 km), NO is efficiently produced through mechanisms involving N₂ dissociation by solar UV radiation and energetic particle precipitation. This is followed by rapid neutral chemistry, such as the $\text{N}(^4\text{S}) + \text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{NO} + \text{O}$ reaction, and ionospheric pathways involving NO⁺ recombination (Marsh et al., 2004). These processes make NO concentrations highly sensitive to solar illumination and diurnal shifts. In the 120–250 km range, O₂ decreases, and O plays a more dominant role. There, NO production is controlled by the creation of excited nitrogen atoms, particularly N(²D), via N₂ photodissociation and auroral inputs. Therefore, NO tends to act as a tracer of thermospheric energy input, with its abundance modulated by space weather and balanced by slower loss processes and radiative cooling at 5.3 μm (Mlynczak et al., 2003). Having simultaneous data on O across this entire altitude range is considered essential, as O dictates the efficiency of both NO production and destruction while influencing the overall thermal structure and energy budget of the thermosphere. The primary challenge in refining this photochemical picture is that the short-lived nitrogen precursors N(²D) and N(⁴S) remain largely uncertain at a global scale. In this context, simultaneous direct observations of [O] and [NO] and 5.3 μm radiance become critical. While the number density provides a look at the chemical reservoir, the 5.3 μm emission offers the view of the energy being released, including the pathway of the N(²D) + O₂ reaction. Combining these datasets allows constraining the temperature-dependent rate coefficients that would otherwise remain uncertain. Ultimately, this approach enables the quantification of how solar energy is partitioned between stable chemical storage and immediate radiative cooling, providing a physical basis to improve the predictive accuracy of space weather models.

Metal Observations to Study the Effects of Satellite and Launch Vehicle Reentries (SG.1)

Observations of metal species in the mesopause region by Keystone's UV-Vis payload would be used to study the impact of the currently exponentially increasing number of launches and re-entry events on the middle atmosphere. This topic is currently intensively debated in the atmospheric science community, because the effects of the associated ablation of space debris are not well understood. Current standard

Figure 5.5: Simulations of the O green line volume emission rate profiles with the model by Lednyts'kyy et al. (2015) and based on WACCM-X input data. The red thick line shows the green line emission profile for unperturbed rate constants and transition probabilities. The thin blue lines display 300 modelled profiles for random realizations of rate constants as described in the text (Credits: C. von Savigny, F. Wrana).

practice in the aerospace industry requires that satellites and launch vehicles must not remain in Low Earth Orbit (LEO) for more than 5 years. Instead, the objects should re-enter the atmosphere and ablate, thereby injecting a variety of exotic metals into the middle atmosphere. The ablated metals rapidly oxidize in the atmosphere below 80 km to form particles. Possible consequences are a depletion of stratospheric O₃ caused by chlorine activation on aluminium particles (Hanning-Lee et al., 1996; Molina et al., 1997; Ferreira et al., 2024) or radiative, thermal and dynamical effects (Maloney et al., 2025). The artificial entry of many metal species (particularly Al and Li) into the mesosphere already exceeds the natural entry by meteoroids (Schulz et al., 2026), and it is estimated that the total annual mass input due to human activity would surpass the natural input of about 10.000 tons per year by the end of the decade. Patches of Li atoms that ablate above 80 km from the Al-Li alloy casings of space debris have recently been detected using a ground-based resonance lidar (Wing et al., 2026). With its capability to observe a variety of metals, Keystone can make an essential contribution to observing the effects of space traffic on the atmosphere.

Exploitation of LOS-Wind Observations (SG.2, SG.3)

The Line-Of-Sight (LOS) wind information retrieved from Doppler shift signatures in THz measurements is used to constrain the wind field in the MTS, where no other global wind observations currently exist. In the following the broad potential of Keystone LOS wind observations is showcased with examples of their exploitation using data assimilation, in analyses in synergy with ground-based observations, and in studies of vector winds without invoking any other data product.

It is straightforward to assimilate LOS wind data in numerical weather prediction models, as the model forward operator includes a projection of the respective model winds onto the satellite horizontal line of sight. This technique is independent of altitude. There are multiple applications for data assimilation. A valuable product that relies on data assimilation are reanalyses that cover long consecutive time periods. In addition, hindcasts are extremely valuable for case studies. Neither of them have any requirements on data latency, but both of them strongly rely on MTS data. Data assimilation in the MTS has been limited by the lack of observations in this region, but it has been clearly demonstrated that the dynamics of the MTS are significantly changed by assimilating MTS data and that this has additional impacts on the ionosphere (Sassi et al., 2024; Pedatella et al., 2018). With Keystone data this limitation can finally be overcome, contributing directly to SG.2 and SG.3.

It should be noted that assimilating Keystone winds together with temperatures retrieved from the THz instrument would be particularly beneficial, as temperature and LOS wind together put strong constraints on atmospheric wave dynamics: Zonal wind, meridional wind, and temperature are mutually linked to each other by linear theory.

Figure 5.6: June mean meridional winds in the ICON model, and LOS winds as observed by Keystone. The panels show different altitudes centred on the hour of 00 UTC and 12 UTC, respectively (Credit: C. Stephan).

Information on tidal variability can also be obtained without data assimilation. To illustrate tidal variability in MTS winds, Figure 5.6 shows global maps of LOS winds across layers with strong vertical variability. Keystone observations would allow the derivation of diurnal tidal amplitudes from differences between the ascending and descending nodes. Moreover, as already visible in Figure 5.6, the imprint of tide DE3 can be inferred. This tide has a characteristic wavenumber-4 pattern when plotted in local time, and is the source of one of the most ubiquitous tidal imprints in the MTS. The results displayed in Figure 5.6 are based on the UA-ICON (Upper Atmosphere ICOSahedral Nonhydrostatic modelling framework) model (Borchert et al., 2019) that provides the capabilities to simulate the neutral atmosphere up to 250 km at a horizontal resolution as fine as 5 km. Meso- and sub-mesoscale features can be explicitly resolved and studied as they propagate into the thermosphere. Keystone also provides information on day-to-day and seasonal variability in winds, which is not correctly captured by empirical models (Figure 5.7). The right panels show data from the empirical Horizontal Wind Model (HWM), which provides spatio-temporal information on horizontal wind vectors for a given geomagnetic forcing.

Extracting information about tidal phases and amplitudes from atmospheric data relies on Fourier spectra in both space and time. Keystone would provide global observations at fixed local times. However, the observations can be combined with ground-based meteor radar data, which are complementary in that they provided excellent temporal coverage at fixed locations (see Section 8). Zhou et al. (2018) demonstrated this approach with observation from TIDI-TIMED. They were successful at obtaining a mesospheric tidal climatology based on monthly mean values of daily tides by fitting spaceborne and ground-based daily observations into a set of normal basic functions (or Empirical Tidal Modes (ETM)). The ETM describe the inseparable latitudinal and vertical structures of tidal components and allow a decomposition of wind observations into daily tidal components with different frequencies and zonal wave numbers.

Figure 5.7: LOS wind seen by Keystone flying through ICON or HWM, respectively. Different panels are either 00 or 12 local time at 180° E, as indicated above the panels. WS, SE, SS, AE stand for winter solstice, spring equinox, summer solstice and autumn equinox. These are the central dates in each labelled column. To the right and left are plotted ± 3 days. Clearly, the empirical models lack day-to-day variability and fine structures in the vertical induced by gravity waves and tides (Credit: C. Stephan).

Besides tides, Quasi-two-day waves (Q2DWs) are one of the most prominent modes of variability in the MTS, playing a significant role in atmosphere-ionosphere coupling. They can penetrate above 100 km height to produce dynamo electric fields that drive Q2DW ionospheric variability in the F-region. He et al. (2021) combined horizontal winds from four low-latitude ($\pm 15^\circ$) specular meteor radars and the Michelson Interferometer for Global High-resolution Thermospheric Imaging (MIGHTI) instrument on the ICON satellite to resolve ambiguities in MIGHTI data that resulted from aliasing due to a nearly sun-synchronous orbit.

Finally, for some studies, it may be desirable to estimate vector winds from the Keystone LOS winds without involving any other data. Krisch et al. (2022) investigated three methods to derive two-dimensional winds for a sun-synchronous orbit with LOS wind observations. Two of them make assumptions about the true wind direction relative to the LOS and the third uses co-located ascending and descending orbit observations to remove the ambiguities in mapping LOS wind to zonal and meridional winds. The third method, which performs best, includes horizontal and temporal averaging, as there is no perfect spatial and temporal co-location of ascending and descending orbits. However, all methods can be suitable for scientific investigations, depending on the science question.

Exploitation of ‘Sideways Wind’ mode (SG.2, SG.3)

Aside from a spectrum of atmospheric waves, the neutral atmosphere of the MTS features strong zonal jets, which have a pronounced seasonal cycle (Figure 5.8). Due to their zonal orientation, ALT view is not well suited for measuring these winds, as is clear from comparing the ALT and AXT ICON columns in Figure 5.8). It can also be noted that ALT Keystone data cannot be directly used to estimate monthly means, as the local time sampling introduces biases. The reason is that the meridional wind, which is predominantly contributing to the ALT sampling, is dominated by tides that have a diurnal cycle. The zonal circulation features, in contrast, are well captured with the AXT view, as their variability is on seasonal timescales. Therefore, occasional AXT pointing via the ‘Sideways Wind’ mode (introduced in Table 4.2 and later discussed in Chapter 7) would allow a valuable quantification of the zonal circulation in the MTS. A second benefit of AXT view are measurements of meridional winds close to the poles, which are triggered by intense heating at times of geomagnetic storms.

Investigation of Sporadic E-Layers (SG.1, SG.2, SG.3)

Sporadic E layers (E_s -layers) are thin layers of metallic ions, typically only a few kilometres thick, that occur between altitudes of about 90 and 140 km and appear as patches of higher-density plasma relative to their surroundings (Plane, 2003). Observations of both the metallic ions that actually comprise the layers

Figure 5.8: For along-track view (ALT) and across-track view (AXT) the figure shows the LOS projection of the horizontal wind component in m/s (and smoothed across a distance of 1000 km) simulated by ICON (label ICON), and the same field after applying the orbital sampling of Keystone (label Keystone). Rows correspond to monthly averages for December, March, June and September, respectively (Credit: C. Stephan).

and the wind shears that drive their convergence support the characterisation of the E_s -layer formation mechanisms. The spatial structure of the E_s -layer would be directly reflected in the $[Mg^+]$ distribution (Kurihara et al., 2010), which is observed by the UV-vis instrument. Keystone UV-Vis observations of other metal ions (potentially $[Fe^+]$ and $[Ca^+]$), as well as neutral precursors like $[Mg]$, $[Na]$, and $[K]$, and THz observation of LOS-wind would be instrumental in characterising these structures. Moreover, Keystone observations of $[Mg]$, $[Na]$, and $[K]$ would help tracking sporadic neutral metal layers, which frequently co-occur with E_s -layers (Plane, 2003). Additionally, Keystone's observations of $[O]$ would help assess how quickly O reduces metallic molecular ions back to atomic ions, a critical chemical pathway in E_s -layer evolution (Plane, 2003).

By providing these direct observations, Keystone would help address open scientific challenges regarding E_s -layers. For instance, it is well understood that high-altitude winds sweep metallic ions into dense layers, a compression process that relies heavily on the tilt of the Earth's magnetic field at mid-latitudes. However, at the magnetic equator, the magnetic field is completely horizontal. This flat geometry should theoretically act as a barrier, preventing the winds from squeezing the ions into thin vertical layers. Surprisingly, E_s -layers are still frequently observed in equatorial regions, leaving their exact formation mechanism a debated puzzle, with competing theories addressing the role of steady zonal westward winds or gradient drift plasma instabilities (Arras et al., 2022). By simultaneously measuring the driving winds and the resulting ion layers over the equator, Keystone would provide the useful data to reveal how these layers manage to form under such restrictive conditions.

Due to their erratic nature, E_s -layers pose a serious operational challenge to HF radio links and over-the-horizon radars (Haldoupis, 2011). These layers behave as dense, localised plasma mirrors that reflect HF radio waves back toward the Earth. While the ionosphere is normally used to bounce radio

signals over long distances, the sudden appearance of an E_s-layer reflects these signals at much lower altitudes than the standard F-region (Cameron et al., 2022). By abruptly changing the reflection altitude and angle, the layer can cause the signal to miss its intended receiver entirely or fall into a dead zone where communication is lost. Furthermore, E_s-layers can lead to blanketing, where the layer is so dense that it physically shields the F-region, preventing signals from reaching higher altitudes and causing a total loss of the intended propagation path (Haldoupis, 2011). While less frequent than effects in the F-region, intense E_s-layers can also cause the aforementioned GNSS signal scintillation that affect the precision of GNSS and satellite communications (Chang et al., 2018; Saito et al., 2021). While ground-based ionosondes and GNSSs are excellent at detecting the presence of E_s-layers, they are inherently blind to the neutral atmospheric dynamics driving them. Keystone's unique contribution lies in its ability to simultaneously observe these neutral drivers and the metallic chemical lifecycle of the layers. This in synergy with radio-based techniques, such as ionosondes, incoherent scatter radars and GNSS, which remain essential for characterising the plasma manifestation of E_s-layers.

5.4. User Communities

Keystone data would be of great importance for numerous scientific communities and international science programmes or initiatives. The atmospheric constituent profiles – in particular the O profiles – provided by Keystone are of utmost importance for the **atmospheric chemistry and the upper-atmosphere communities**, because Keystone provides global and direct observations of O concentration at the mesopause and in the lower thermosphere for the first time. This allows for the verification and validation of high-lid global models of atmospheric chemistry and dynamics. In addition, the **airglow community** would employ the Keystone observations of O and other species to test photochemical models for the excitation of different nightglow emissions, including the O green and red lines, the O₂ A-band emission, as well as the Na D-line emission.

The Keystone mission would be central to the **atmospheric dynamics and aeronomy community**, as well as to the **whole-atmosphere modelling community**. Rapid advances in whole-atmosphere Models have revolutionised the ability to simulate the Earth's atmosphere as a dynamically continuous fluid system from the surface to the upper thermosphere, including the upward propagation of atmospheric tides, as well as of large-scale gravity waves, which are the most important drivers of momentum and energy transport in the MTS with sources below the stratosphere. To date, models show great differences in the representation of atmospheric tides and gravity waves. This is due to a lack of observational benchmarks and physical understanding, including wave interactions. Keystone's temperature and LOS wind products would provide direct information on propagating waves. Moreover, Keystone would allow novel studies on wave-mean flow interactions by providing statistics on waves and the mean flow. Finally, wave breaking, but also propagating waves, mix tracers, which are also a Keystone product. Thus, Keystone observations are essential to study the physics of the most relevant waves for the MTS across their lifecycle, i.e. propagation, interaction, dissipation. These waves are also indirectly responsible for the existence of noctilucent clouds. Here, Keystone products provide a special synergy. The Keystone mission would be highly relevant for the **noctilucent cloud community**, because it does not only provide observations of cloud occurrence, ice mass and particle size, but also simultaneous observations of temperature and H₂O profiles at the polar summer mesopause, in the context of dynamics.

Furthermore, Keystone would be highly valuable for the **ionospheric community**, e.g. for radio propagation studies due to its ability to measure neutral wind shears, metallic ions (e.g. Mg⁺), and O. These are the primary ingredients governing the erratic formation of Sporadic E-layers, which impact high-frequency (HF) communications and radar systems. Additionally, the rapidly expanding Very Low Earth Orbit (VLEO) **applications** can rely on Keystone's direct observations of O and temperature to accurately constrain total neutral atmospheric densities, significantly improving aerodynamic drag

models, collision avoidance, and orbital lifetime predictions.

Keystone is of high importance to many international programs and initiatives, including:

- the Scientific Committee on Solar-Terrestrial Physics ([SCOSTEP](#)), an initiative of the International Science Council ([ISC](#)).
- the International Commission on the Middle Atmosphere ([ICMA](#)), a commission of the International Association of Meteorology and Atmospheric Sciences ([IAMAS](#)), also an initiative of the ISC.
- Atmospheric Processes and their Role in Climate ([APARC](#)), a core project of the World Climate Research Programme ([WCRP](#)), programme of the World Meteorological Organization ([WMO](#)).
- the Network for Detection of Mesospheric Change ([NDMC](#)), with more than 50 ground-based stations for monitoring mesospheric temperature variability and change.
- the Network for the Detection of Atmospheric Composition Change ([NDACC](#)) a contributor to the Global Atmosphere Watch ([GAW](#)), programme of the WMO.
- the Antarctic Geospace and ATmosphere reseArch ([AGATA](#)) Scientific Research Programme of the Scientific Committee on Antarctic Research ([SCAR](#)), a worldwide effort to monitor and investigate the physics of the polar atmosphere and the impact of the Sun-Earth interactions.
- the International Space Weather Initiative ([ISWI](#)) of the United Nations Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space ([COPUOS](#)), dedicated to international cooperations to advance space weather science.
- the International Space Weather Action Teams ([ISWAT](#)) of the Committee on Space Research ([COSPAR](#)), particularly the teams addressing Atmosphere variability ([G2A](#)) and Ionosphere variability ([G2B](#)).
- the Interdivisional Commission on Space Weather ([ICSW](#)), part of the International Association of Geomagnetism and Aeronomy ([IAGA](#)).

6. SCIENTIFIC FEASIBILITY

This chapter presents the evidence for the scientific feasibility of the Keystone mission. Keystone provides a combination of THz heterodyne, IR, and UV-Vis techniques to get a complete picture of the composition of the MTS, as well as its thermal, dynamical and photochemical properties. The scientific feasibility assessment of Phase 0 is mainly concerned with verifying that the measurement requirements (spatial, spectral, radiometric, etc.) meet the observation requirements. The THz observation concept is possibly the most innovative payload element, providing the novel 2 THz measurements of an O emission line; some heritage exists from sub-millimetre wave and THz radiometers like MLS (UARS/Aura), which have performed successful passive limb-emission soundings up to frequencies of 2.5 THz routinely. Mission science goals would be met by combining this novel measurement with IR and UV-Vis observations that have a strong heritage; the IR observation concept traces its lineage back to SABER (TIMED), and the UV-Vis observation concept is in the footsteps of OSIRIS (Odin) and SCIAMACHY (Envisat). SABER, OSIRIS and SCIAMACHY signposted the need for a system-wide view but were not able to meet Keystone's mission objectives due to lacking an MTS-wide viewpoint.

The geophysical scenarios considered in the assessments presented here cover a wide range of atmospheric conditions and are introduced in Section 6.1. The assessments performed to demonstrate the sensitivity of the measurements in the three spectral domains to atmospheric variability of the target observables, and the consistency of the L2 observation requirements (Section 4.1) with the L1 measurement requirements (Section 4.4) is presented in Section 6.2. Finally, Section 6.3 outlines past and planned campaign activities conducted to demonstrate the THz observation concept.

6.1. Geophysical Scenarios

The geophysical reference scenarios used in the THz and UV-Vis sensitivity assessments cover MTS variability due to solar and geomagnetic forcings (expressed in terms of the F10.7 index (Tapping, 2013) and the K_p index (Kauristie et al., 2017), see also Section 2.3) as well as seasonal variability and diurnal differences. The “Quiet” scenario represents background conditions with fixed solar / geomagnetic forcing ($K_p=2$ and the F10.7 index=180 sfu). A set of “Solar storm” scenarios based on the ‘Mother’s Day Storm’ on 10-11 May 2024 (maximum $K_p=9$, (Spogli et al., 2024)) captures the conditions before the storm, at its peak, and after the storm (as presented in Figure 6.1). Data capturing seasonal variability are extracted from the “Quiet” scenario taking difference between the zonally averaged Northern ($>24^\circ$) and Southern ($>24^\circ$) hemispheres. Diurnal variability is characterised by meridional slices at midnight and noon local time. These scenarios have been generated using the WACCM-X model; simulations were performed on the ‘1°’ horizontal grid ($0.9^\circ \times 1.25^\circ$) with identical conditions, including greenhouse gas concentrations, representative of January 2000.

The representative atmospheric cases for the IR instrument assessment were selected from the ERS dataset (Extended Reference Scenarios; Errera (2023)), consisting of multi-year monthly averages of climate model simulations for quiet conditions. For the Keystone IR instrument L2 products (T, O₃, CO₂, and NO), as well as O, the data combine WACCM ACOM products (2019–2022 near-real-time operational outputs based on WACCM v6) with WACCM-X-SD v2.1 data (Liu et al., 2018), merged at 140 km. The latter corresponds to daily snapshot outputs at 00:00 UT available through NCAR’s GDEX database. Simulations representative of both minimum and maximum solar activity conditions were considered, corresponding to the periods 2009–2010 and 2002–2003, respectively.

WACCM Model

The geophysical reference scenarios have been generated using the Whole Atmosphere Community Climate Model with thermosphere and ionosphere extension (WACCM-X). It is a “high-to” Earth System

Figure 6.1: Evolution of the F10.7 solar flux (purple, right-hand y-axis) and K_p geomagnetic index (green, left-hand y-axis) for the “Solar Storm” scenario based on the ‘Mother’s Day Storm’ (10-12 May 2024). The vertical dashed lines indicate the times at which slices were extracted: at the ‘Peak’ (purple) of the storm when $K_p = 9$, ‘Before’ (green) and ‘After’ (purple) the ‘Peak’ of the storm when $K_p = 2$ (Credit: F.Sainsbury-Martinez).

Model that extends from the Earth’s surface to the exobase (500–700 km depending upon the solar cycle). WACCM-X is a part of the Community Earth System Model (CESM) Version 2 (Danabasoglu et al., 2020), which is designed to study the Earth’s climate by coupling models of the atmosphere, ocean, land and sea-ice. WACCM-X is a “physics-based” model that solves for the atmospheric state by integrating the continuity, thermodynamic and momentum equations. The atmospheric component couples a hydrostatic finite-volume dynamical core with a ‘physics’ package that includes fully interactive chemistry (Liu et al., 2018). WACCM-X tracks the flow of energy, momentum and constituents within the MTS; ionospheric electrodynamics, Joule heating, ion drag, gravity wave drag, Eddy and molecular diffusion, energetic particle precipitation, UV, EUV and x-ray photolysis and photoionization, non-LTE cooling, air-glow, and heating from exothermic reactions are all accounted for (Marsh et al., 2007; Marsh, 2011; Liu et al., 2018). In addition, WACCM-X resolves atmospheric tides resulting from heating in the lower atmosphere by solar radiation and latent heat release from tropospheric deep-convection. Planetary-scale dynamical phenomena such as the El Niño and the Southern Oscillation (ENSO), QBO and SSWs are covered in the WACCM-X scenarios, as well as tropospheric weather patterns, anthropogenic trace gas trends, and the impacts from geomagnetic forcing and solar irradiance changes. This makes WACCM-X ideal for studying the forcing of the MTS from both below and above.

6.2. Sensitivity Assessment

In this section, the assessments conducted to show the feasibility of the Keystone observations based on measurements in the three spectral domains is presented. Comprehensive sensitivity assessments and retrieval experiments have been performed for the THz (Section 6.2.1) quantifying measurable signatures of atmospheric variabilities and various contributions to the L2 uncertainty. The sensitivity of IR measurements is demonstrated based on linearised error propagation linking L1 and L2 random errors (Sec 6.2.2). The IR observation capability is considered as very mature in view of the heritage from SABER. A sensitivity study is presented on the impact of spectral channel characteristics, anticipating possible deviations from the SABER heritage due to technical limitations. Section 6.2.3 demonstrates UV-Vis observational capacity through the heritage of the OSIRIS and SCIAMACHY missions while conducting specific studies on key emission signatures. The driving errors in the L2 products are identified and reported per spectral domain (Sec 6.2.5).

6.2.1. THz Sensitivity Assessment

In this section, the tracing from L2 uncertainty requirements for the THz observables (number densities [O], [O₂], [OH], [H₂O], [CO], and [NO]; temperature; pressure; wind) to the L1 measurement requirements for the THz instrument is presented. The assessments shown are based on radiative transfer simulations, radiometric noise propagation/mapping to L2 uncertainties, and retrieval experiments using the framework described by Hansen et al. (2025). In the radiative transfer modelling spontaneous

and stimulated emission as well as absorption in a three-dimensional atmosphere are described. Line broadening related to temperature and pressure and Doppler shifts from winds are taken into account. Local thermodynamic equilibrium (LTE) is assumed, implying that the populations of the energy levels relevant for the THz emissions follow a Boltzmann distribution at the local kinetic temperature. LTE is a good approximation because the low energy THz transitions are efficiently thermalised by collisions (Sharma et al., 1994).

For the propagation/mapping of radiometric noise to L2 uncertainties and the retrieval experiments, the atmospheric state is parameterised vertically using third-order B-splines and for the retrieval experiments, the inverse problem is solved with a Gauss-Newton method. The assessments have been performed assuming measurements in line with the Keystone requirements on vertical resolution and sampling, spectral resolution and sampling, and radiometric noise (see Section 4). For the retrieval experiments, receiver noise temperatures are 6,000 K single-sideband at 1.1 THz and 15,000 K single-sideband at 2.1 THz. For 1.1 THz this is similar to what is provided by industry and for 2.1 THz this is higher than what can be provided by industry (see Section 7.3.2). When taking into account the integration times for an along-track sampling distance of 800 km, the retrieval simulations uses a $NE\Delta T$ similar to the requirement threshold at 2.1 THz and a slightly higher value around 1.1 THz. The atmosphere scenarios considered have been generated using the WACCM-X model and represent conditions a) of a quiet atmosphere, b) at the peak of a geomagnetic storm, and c) after a geomagnetic storm (see Section 6.1).

First, signatures for a quiet atmosphere are shown; then, results from retrieval experiments are reported; then, the sensitivity of the measurement to changes in observables is presented; finally, the mapping of the radiometric noise to L2 uncertainties is presented.

Figure 6.2: Examples of measurable signatures of O at ~ 100 km (left), O₂ at 70 km (middle), and H₂O at 70 km tangent height (right). In the upper panels forward simulations with realistic noise (black) are compared with fitted spectra obtained in retrieval experiments (orange); residuals are depicted in the lower panels (Credit: P. B. Hansen).

Typical THz Signal Levels

Typical THz spectra at selected tangent heights are shown in Figure 6.2. The O₂ and H₂O spectra are shown for a tangent height of 70 km, where both emission signatures exceed the radiometric noise with a large margin and are clearly detectable. In addition, the O₂ and H₂O lines exhibit inverted emission profiles caused by strong self-absorption. The O spectrum is shown for a tangent height of 100 km near to its concentration peak which results in a strong emission signal.

For all target species, measurable signatures exceed the radiometric noise level. In Figure 6.3 the measured signal near strong line centres for quiet atmospheric conditions is compared to the noise amplitude. The signature of atomic oxygen exceeds the noise significantly in the target vertical range [100–250 km] (and below 100 km where signals are saturated). The signatures of other species exceed the noise up to a certain tangent height (ranging from ~ 80 km for OH to ~ 130 km for NO), covering the target vertical ranges identified in Table 4.1.

Figure 6.3: Measurable signal near the peak of selected emissions lines normalised by the radiometric noise. Measurable signatures significantly exceed the noise in the target vertical ranges (Credit: P. B. Hansen).

Figure 6.4: Retrieval experiments for conditions before and after a solar storm and at its peak. Retrieved profiles (solid) reproduce well the synthetic truth (from WACCM-X, dashed). Deviations typically fall within the 1- σ retrieval uncertainty (coloured areas) (Credit: P. B. Hansen).

Figure 6.5: Atomic oxygen number density [O] for quiet conditions (upper panels), at the peak of a magnetic storm (middle panels), and after the event (lower panels) in a cross section along a near-meridional satellite track. The [O] field retrieved in the ‘Standard Operational’ mode (Table 4.2, right panels) captures very well the horizontal and vertical structures of the synthetic truth and thus the impact of the event (left panels) (Credit: P. B. Hansen).

THz Retrieval Experiments

Detailed retrieval experiments have been conducted for the simultaneous retrieval of six observables including [O], [O₂], [H₂O], temperature, pressure, and wind speed. These simulations capture both the propagation of instrumental noise into L2 uncertainties and smoothing errors due to vertical and horizontal variability. All retrieval simulations are for the *Standard Operational* mode defined in Table 4.2 and utilise the 2.1 THz O line, 1115 GHz O₂ line, and the 1153 and 1158 GHz H₂O lines.

Figure 6.4 shows the synthetic truth (dashed line), the retrieved profile (straight line) and the 1-σ uncertainty (coloured areas), for three atmospheric conditions. In the case of atomic oxygen the agreement is very good except below 100 km, where the uncertainty increases due to saturation of its emission line. For the peak storm scenario there are larger atomic oxygen deviations because of stronger horizontal gradients. In the case of molecular oxygen and water the agreement is very good for all three scenarios with an increasing uncertainty above 120 km (O₂) and 90 km (H₂O), due to a strong decrease of number density. In the case of temperature and pressure the agreement between model and retrieval is also very good. Above 150 km the uncertainty of the retrieved temperature increases due to the decreasing density of atomic oxygen. This is similar for the wind measurements where the uncertainty also increases above 150 km. The uncertainty of the pressure increases above 80 km because it is derived from pressure broadening which becomes negligible above 80 km altitude. The O, O₂, and H₂O spectra shown

Figure 6.6: $[O_2]$, $[H_2O]$, temperature, pressure, and LOS-wind in quiet conditions in a cross section along a near-meridional satellite track. The fields retrieved in the ‘Standard Operational’ mode (Table 4.2, right panels) capture very well the horizontal and vertical structures of the synthetic truth (left panels) (Credit: P. B. Hansen).

Figure 6.7: Retrieval uncertainty estimated based on residual errors (orange dashed) and errors due to radiometric noise (blue solid) averaged across the satellite track and across the evolution of the solar storm. L2 uncertainty requirements (black dashed) for [O], [O₂], [H₂O], temperature, pressure and LOS-wind are met in most cases and in a large part of the target vertical range (Credit: P. B. Hansen).

earlier in this section in Figure 6.2 are from the quiet conditions retrieval experiment.

Figure 6.5 presents [O] profiles from retrieval experiments along a satellite track. Results for quiet conditions before a geomagnetic storm with a smooth [O] field are shown in the top row. Results for conditions at the peak of such an event with more variability are shown in the middle row. Results after such an event are shown in the bottom panel. The synthetic truth is depicted in the first column and retrieved densities in the second column. The pronounced signatures of the geomagnetic storm are very well captured in the retrieved [O] field in the intended target vertical range above 100 km of this observable. For the quiet conditions, the rest of the observables along a satellite track are presented in Figure 6.6.

Retrieval uncertainties are compared with the uncertainty requirements in Figure 6.7. L2 uncertainties due to radiometric noise are shown in blue. L2 uncertainties estimated based on deviations from the synthetic truth include smoothing errors due to vertical and horizontal gradients and are plotted as dashed orange lines. L2 uncertainty requirements are depicted as black dashed lines. Uncertainties are within the requirements in most cases and in a large part of the vertical domain.

The retrieval simulations provide a direct comparison of radiometric noise uncertainty and smoothing errors for the before-storm case. For atomic oxygen, the uncertainties are primarily driven by radiometric noise, as demonstrated by the agreement between radiometric noise uncertainties and the actual residuals. Consequently, the gradients in WACCM-X do not appear to be the dominant error source for O. An exception is found for the peak-storm case, where residuals exceeding the radiometric noise level can be observed (Figure 6.4). In contrast, horizontal winds and H₂O are more susceptible to smoothing errors due to their stronger horizontal variability in combination of high SNR of the emissions at the lower

altitudes. Some of these smoothing effects could be mitigated through a more advanced tomographic retrieval approach combining multiple limb scans into a single retrieval rather than only two as done here. Such approaches would be investigated in a later phase.

THz Sensitivity

The sensitivity of the THz measurements to the observables is assessed considering spectral and vertical dependencies.

Spectrally resolved measurement responses near the 2.06 THz atomic oxygen line to a 20% change in the [O] profile are shown as examples for a set of tangent heights (Figure 6.8). The response is shown as colour coded map of the Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR); the vertical axis indicates the altitude of the profile perturbation. For measurements at 140 km tangent height, which fall within the target vertical range of [O], the sensitivity is excellent: it peaks at the tangent height itself and SNR values above unity are reached. In contrast, for measurements at 80 km tangent height, outside this range, sensitivity to perturbations above the tangent height with low SNR are found. It is noted that, even though the SNR values per spectral sample are not large in absolute terms, retrieval sensitivities are sufficient: retrievals exploit the entire spectral band and hence benefit from the basic fact that perturbations are spectrally correlated while radiometric noise is uncorrelated; retrieval sensitivities are assessed quantitatively in the following paragraph.

Figure 6.8: Response to density perturbations for the 2.1 THz O line at two different tangent heights (red dashed). (a) At 140 km the perturbations are larger and close to the tangent point indicating excellent sensitivity and limited correlations with higher altitudes. (b) At 80 km tangent height (outside the target vertical range), the density perturbation at 80 km is barely seen. Instead the perturbations at higher altitudes dominates with a maximum response around 120 km. This indicates poor sensitivity and large correlations with higher altitudes (Credit: P. B. Hansen).

The vertical dependence of the spectrally integrated measurement sensitivity is presented for the observables [O], [O₂], [OH], [H₂O], [CO], [NO], temperature, pressure, and line-of-sight wind (see Figure 6.9). The horizontal axis represents the tangent height and the vertical axis the altitude of the profile perturbation, illustrating qualitatively the altitude from which the information in a given limb view originates.

Measurements of the O signature near 2.06 THz at tangent heights above 100 km are sensitive to changes in O, temperature, and LOS-wind at the tangent height and above. Temperature and LOS-wind information below 100 km is constrained mainly by measurements of the H₂O, O₂, and CO signatures. In Figure 6.9, this synergy is illustrated exemplarily for O and the H₂O line near 1.153 THz.

Pressure information from the H₂O line is largely limited to altitudes below ~80 km, which is sufficient since pressures at higher altitudes are inferred under the assumption of hydrostatic equilibrium.

THz Radiometric Noise Contribution to L2 Uncertainties

The mapping of radiometric noise to L2 uncertainties was done for each of the THz observables using a spherically symmetric atmosphere corresponding to the location of median O density for the quiet atmo-

Figure 6.9: Response of the THz observation at a given tangent height (horizontal axes) to a perturbation in the profile of the observable at a given altitude (vertical axes), for number densities (a-f), temperature (g,h), LOS-wind (i,j) and pressure (k), inferred by the spectrally integrated noise-normalised sensitivity (colours). Observations are sensitive in the target vertical ranges (Table 4.1). The measurements of the O and H₂O emission lines bring complementary information on temperature and LOS-wind (Credit: P. B. Hansen).

sphere. For a given observable, perfect knowledge of the others were assumed. I.e., for the mapping of radiometric noise for some emission line to species density, perfect knowledge of temperature, pressure, and winds are assumed and vice versa. The results are shown in Figure 6.10. The results are in line with the sensitivity analyses above: at altitudes below 100 km, radiometric noise propagates to large O density uncertainties (Figure 6.10a). For the other THz species (Figure 6.10b-f), the opposite is true. I.e., the radiometric noise propagates to small relative uncertainties. For the temperature and line-of-sight winds (Figure 6.10g-h), the synergy of L2 sensitivity from different emissions are highlighted: O provides low retrieval uncertainties above 100 km, while O₂ and H₂O provides low uncertainties below 100 km. The L2 requirements are indicated by dashed black lines in the plots. The mapped radiometric noise generally results in retrieval uncertainties at or below these requirements. For temperature and line-of-sight winds, the L2 requirements must be achieved through the combined use of multiple emission

lines. This approach was used in the retrieval simulations described above. As NO has a low density, its percentage sensitivity is low compared to the other species. However, orbital or zonal averaging can be employed to improve sensitivity.

Figure 6.10: Uncertainty in THz observable profiles due to radiometric noise (colours). The emission lines exploited are specified in the legends. Measurements of the 2.1 THz O line and of other signatures bring complementary information on temperature and wind (g, h). Pressure information comes from the H₂O and O₂ lines (i). The L2 uncertainty requirements (black dashed, Table 4.1) are met in most cases in a large part of the target vertical range (Credit: P. B. Hansen).

6.2.2. IR Sensitivity Assessment

Keystone’s IR channels (Table 4.3) are defined following to a large degree the heritage from the Sounding of the Atmosphere using Broadband Emission Radiometry (SABER) instrument on NASA’s Thermosphere-Ionosphere-Mesosphere Energetics and Dynamics (TIMED) mission (Esplin et al., 2023). A subset of SABER channels is inherited; the optional water ice channel (IR3) is inspired by a similar channel from the Spatial Infrared Imaging Telescope (SPIRIT) III radiometer on the Midcourse Space Experiment (MSX)

(O’Neil et al., 2008). Keystone IR L2 uncertainty requirements follow those of SABER. Since Keystone L1 performance is required to match or exceed SABER’s specifications (Table 4.3), its L2 performance is expected to be at least comparable. The capability to retrieve L2 geophysical variables from the inherited channels has been extensively demonstrated by: Remsberg et al. (2008) and García-Comas et al. (2008) for temperature and reference pressure from the 15 μm channels, Rezac et al. (2015) for CO₂ VMR from the 4.2 μm channel, Rong et al. (2019) for O₃ VMR from the 9.3 μm channel, and Mlynczak et al. (2024) for NO VER and CO₂ VER from the 15 μm and the 5.3 μm channels. These works give solid confidence that the Keystone, s L2 requirements for the IR products (Table 4.1) are met.

Nevertheless, a series of sensitivity studies are presented for Keystone to corroborate the flow-down from observation to measurement requirements, and to quantify the contribution of radiometric noise to uncertainties in the IR observables temperature, O₃ Volume Mixing Ratio (VMR), CO₂ VMR, NO Volume Emission Rate (VER), and pressure. These assessment account for a larger radiometric noise in the 4.2 μm channel (IR6) and a change in the long wavelength cut-off of IR6 to minimise signals from interfering species, as compared to SABER.

Dedicated sensitivity analyses have been conducted to quantify the possible impact of a deviation in IR2 from the SABER heritage on temperature retrieval and pressure registration: Keystone’s wide channel (IR2) at 15 μm may be narrower due to possible limitations in quantum efficiency of available European detectors above 15.5 μm (not reaching SABER’s long wavelength cut-off at 17.5 μm).

Methodology and Tools

Limb emissions in the IR channels were computed using the line-by-line Reference Forward Model (RFM, Dudhia, 2017). These emissions originate from the radiative relaxation of rovibrationally excited states of atmospheric species. In the middle mesosphere and above, due to the exponential decrease of atmospheric density with altitude, these species are in a state of Non-Local Thermodynamic Equilibrium (NLTE): the population of excited states deviates from the Boltzmann distribution and the emitted radiation is hence no longer a simple function of the local kinetic temperature. Handling NLTE in atmospheric retrievals is complex. The sensitivity studies conducted for Keystone presented in this section have fully accounted for NLTE using the Generic RADIative transfer AnD non-LTE population Algorithm (GRANADA Funke et al., 2012). Limb emissions were computed using RFM taking vibrational level populations from GRANADA. Both tools have been extensively validated against measurements from the MIPAS instrument.

Errors were propagated linearly, viz.: $\underline{y} = \underline{K} \underline{x}$, where \underline{x} is the atmospheric state vector (temperature, VMR or VER), \underline{y} represents the measurement vector (i.e., broadband radiances L_{IR} in the IR channels), and \underline{K} is the linearised forward model or Jacobian matrix with elements $K_{ij} = \partial y_i / \partial x_j$. The error covariance matrix (\underline{S}_x) is given by $\underline{S}_x = (\underline{K}^T \underline{S}_y^{-1} \underline{K})^{-1}$ where \underline{S}_y is the measurement noise covariance matrix, assumed diagonal here and with the Noise Equivalent Radiance (NER) of the channels on its diagonal. The Jacobians represent the sensitivity of the measured radiance to changes in the L2 variable at each altitude level.

Radiance spectra and Jacobians were computed at $5 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ spectral resolution and integrated in the spectral bandpass domains of the IR channel (Table 4.3). The vertical resolution is represented by a trapezoidal field-of-view function (FWHM of 2.5 km). Additional to the main emitter, interfering species contributing to the channel measurement were considered.

Sensitivity assessments were conducted for a set of representative atmospheric cases. To capture diurnal, seasonal and solar variability, six atmospheric conditions from the ERS database were selected for the IR assessment based on January climatology: *Equatorial day* (0° latitude); *South polar day* (80°S), representing polar summer conditions; and, *North polar night* (80°N) representing polar winter

conditions, both for quiet and high solar activity scenarios.

Temperature – IR2

Figure 6.11a exhibits the sensitivity assessment for the IR2 channel used to derive temperature profiles, considering long wavelength cut-offs at 17.5 μm (solid lines) and 15.5 μm (dashed lines). The left panel shows the IR2 radiance profiles for a subset of three scenarios that captures the variability across the six scenarios (colours and symbols). The striking lower signal in the 70–95 km range in the *South polar day* case showcases the ability of Keystone to discriminate the very cold mesopause ($\sim 150\text{ K}$) typical for polar summer from other conditions. The middle panel shows the response in the IR2 signal to a perturbation in temperature ΔT_{req} commensurate to the temperature uncertainty requirement (Table 4.1). The response per altitude level is evaluated as $\Delta L_{IR2} = \partial L_{IR2} / \partial T \Delta T_{req}$. The response exceeds the NER level of the radiometric noise requirement (grey area) in all cases, except for the *South polar day* scenario (polar summer) around 90 km. The right panel shows the contribution σ_T of IR2 radiometric noise to the L2 temperature product uncertainty (evaluated as $\sigma_T = \sigma_{NER} / (\partial L_{IR2} / \partial T)$, thus applying an analogous error propagation in the opposite direction). Consistently with the above-mentioned results, this error contribution is well below the temperature uncertainty requirement levels (dashed grey) in most cases, with the same exception. A reduction of the long wavelength cut-off (17.5 μm to 15.5 μm) has a minor impact on the sensitivity. It is concluded that the ratio of the NER to the unscaled Jacobian, $NER / (\partial L_{IR2} / \partial T)$. This is an estimation of the propagated noise error into the observable (L2 product) space, for which a diagonal Jacobian matrix has been assumed. The dark grey dashed line shows the observable requirements in from Table 4.1 for reference. Again, with the exception of the polar summer (south polar day), the NER always represents a smaller contribution to the temperature error than the requirement, also for an IR2 filter with a 15.5 μm cutoff, meaning that Keystone would be able to measure temperature with the required sensitivity and precision, and leaving room for additional sources of errors.

O₃ VMR – IR4

A similar exercise has been conducted to study the sensitivity for IR4 at 9.3 μm , from which O₃ VMR would be retrieved. The Jacobians $\partial L_{IR4} / \partial O_3$ have been calculated with respect to the O₃ VMR. The results are shown in Figure 6.11b. The ozone VMR profile features a secondary maximum near 90 km during the day and 95 km at night; the daytime peak is approximately eight times smaller due to photodissociation. In these daytime cases (represented by the blue and orange lines), ozone concentration decreases abruptly above 90 km. This rapid decline causes a dramatic drop in both radiance and scaled sensitivity, leading to an increase in the relative VMR error due to NER. Consequently, the O₃ VMR requirement is exceeded at these higher altitudes during the day. In all other cases, the O₃ VMR requirement is comfortably met, allowing margin for other errors. It is also worth noting the slight improvement in sensitivity around the tertiary maximum, located at approximately 70–75 km during the polar winter night (*North polar night* shown in light grey in the Figure), compared to the other atmospheric conditions.

CO₂ VMR – IR6

Figure 6.11c shows analogous results for the sensitivity analysis for IR6 at 4.2 μm , from which CO₂ VMR would be retrieved only at daytime. The lower simulated radiance for the *South polar day* case compared to the *Equatorial day* case above 90 km is primarily due to the lower CO₂ mixing ratio in WACCM during the polar summer in that altitude range. Additionally, a larger solar zenith angle, and the resulting smaller solar flux, leads to lower excitation of CO₂ levels at 4.3 μm . This also reduces the scaled sensitivity for this case and, consequently, increases the noise error in the CO₂ VMR, causing the requirement to exceed the limit above 115 km in this particular case. Otherwise, the requirement is comfortably met. The decrease in sensitivity at 100 and 110 km for both the *South Polar day* and *Equatorial day* cases is due to the increased optical thickness of the CO₂ 4.3 μm fundamental band, combined with the still-weak

Figure 6.11: Keystone L2 sensitivity for (a) temperature from channel IR2, with solid and dashed lines showing results for 17.5 μm and 15.5 μm long-wavelength cut-offs, respectively; (b) O₃ VMR from channel IR4; (c) CO₂ VMR from channel IR6; and (d) NO VER from channel IR5, for selected cases as shown in the legend. The left, centre, and right panels in each plot show, respectively, channel-integrated limb radiance, radiance sensitivity (Jacobian) scaled by the corresponding requirement and compared with NER (grey shading), and the NER contribution to L2 error compared with Keystone's requirement (black dashed) (Credits: A. Knížek, M. García-Comas).

contribution of other hot bands to the channel.

NO VER – IR5

Figure 6.11d illustrates the sensitivity of the Keystone IR5 channel (5.3 μm) for determining the NO VER. Unlike previous channels, these simulations include high solar activity scenarios, as NO production, driven by the photodissociation of N₂ and O₂, is strongly dependent on solar flux. While radiances in the left panel were calculated following the standard procedure for IR channels, the sensitivity analysis assumes a direct proportionality between radiance and VER. This approach relies on the assumption that the observed emission is heavily weighted towards the tangent point along the atmospheric ray path. Consequently, the NO VER requirement is translated into an equivalent relative radiance difference. The middle panel demonstrates that a 20% limb radiance variation remains above the NER at all altitudes across most scenarios, except for the quiet nighttime case. Finally, the right panel shows the NER contribution to the VER error; it confirms that the instrument meets the requirement at all altitudes during high

Figure 6.12: Left: Sensitivity of the spectral radiance L to a variation of 1 K in temperature (red) and 1% in pressure (blue), in the spectral region of the IR1 and IR2 channels. The Jacobian spectra $\frac{\partial L}{\partial T}$ and $\frac{\partial L}{\partial p}$ have been computed with the RFM. The actual spectrum, scaled by 0.01, is shown in grey. Keystone filters IR1 and IR2 with various IR2 longwave cut-off limits are shown in green and orange, respectively. Center and right: Contribution of radiometric noise to L2 random error in pressure and temperature as a function of altitude for various IR2 longwave cut-off limits (the cut-off values in the legend are given in micrometer). Pressure and temperature meet requirement below 70 km (Credits: A. Dudhia, A. Knižek).

solar activity, whereas for standard daytime cases, compliance is maintained up to 150–160 km.

Pressure Registration

The retrieval of temperature profiles from the IR2 channel requires knowledge of atmospheric pressure at each altitude. The latter is obtained via hydrostatic reconstruction (see Figure 5.2), which requires knowledge of a reference pressure p_0 at a reference altitude z_0 . Keystone can provide a reference pressure in two ways: (1) using the so-called two-colour technique, and (2) from the THz measurements.

Following the two-colour technique used in SABER (Gille and House, 1971), p_0 is estimated using a narrow and a wide channel near 15 μm, corresponding to the Keystone channels IR1 and IR2, respectively. However, this technique gives pressure with sufficient precision only in the vicinity of the stratopause due to saturated signals at lower altitudes and NLTE effects at higher altitudes. Thus, for Keystone observation modes that do not cover these altitudes (modes other than ‘Deep’), p_0 from THz retrievals, primarily based on O₂ and H₂O signatures, would be used.

The following sections describe Keystone’s expected p_0 precision using both methods and its impact on L2 temperature.

Two-Color Technique

The simultaneous retrieval of tangent point pressure (p) and temperature (T) from the 15 μm CO₂ narrow and wide channels (IR1 and IR2, respectively) using the two-colour technique is assessed. Various IR2 cut-off wavelengths were considered, including 17.2, 15.5 and 14.5 μm. The IR2 NER was computed from the nominal value (the requirement threshold for an IR2 with a cut-off at 17.5 μm) assuming that it scales with the square root of the channel width.

Example radiance and Jacobian spectra are shown in the left panel of Figure 6.12. These Jacobians now correspond to the radiance sensitivity in IR1 and IR2 to changes in p and T at each altitude level ($\partial L_{IR}/\partial p, \partial L_{IR}/\partial T$). Effective p and T discrimination is achieved when the off-diagonal elements of $\underline{S}_x = \underline{K}^{-1} \underline{S}_y (\underline{K}^{-1})^T$ are small relative to the diagonal elements, indicating low correlation between the two variables.

The error covariances were calculated for a variety of altitudes and IR2 filter widths. Correlation between

the retrieved variables contributes to the total retrieval uncertainty and is reflected both in the off-diagonal terms and in the magnitude of the diagonal elements. The centre and right panels of Figure 6.12 show the precision estimates for the p and T retrievals, respectively. As expected, they exhibit a steady deterioration with altitude, reflecting the decreasing signal while noise remains constant.

Error estimates for pressure and temperature remain stable and very well-controlled (below 1% and 1 K, respectively) at 50–55 km altitudes for all tested cut-off limits. Both the 17.2 μm and the 15.5 μm cut-offs perform comfortably within Keystone's temperature requirement, leaving room for other error sources below 65 km. Thus, it is verified that narrowing the IR2 does not compromise p - T discrimination. Moreover, a 14.5 μm cut-off would be even better in terms of p and T discrimination. This wavelength is the cut-off point at which the two filters no longer overlap, so this maximises the independence of the information in the two channels.

IR Temperature Retrieval Using Pressure from the THz

As demonstrated in Section 6.2.1, the THz instrument provides pressure around $z_0=70$ –75 km with a 7–10% uncertainty (Figure 6.7). In a hydrostatical reconstruction of the pressure profile, the pressure relative uncertainty is conserved at all altitudes ($\partial p/p = \partial p_0/p_0$). A perturbation in pressure is equivalent to a vertical displacement of the temperature profile. For the less favourable polar summer scenario, characterised by strong temperature vertical gradients of about -5 K/km at 70–75 km, a 7–10% pressure uncertainty translates into a vertical displacement $\Delta z \approx H \Delta p_0/p_0 \sim 0.4$ –0.6 km, where a scale height $H = RT/Mg$ of ~ 6 km has been assumed. This results in a 2–3 K temperature error, which remains within Keystone's temperature requirement at those altitudes. The strategy to use a reference pressure from the THz for modes not covering the lower mesosphere is hence valid for Keystone.

6.2.3. UV-Vis Sensitivity Assessment

The feasibility of the Keystone UV-Vis observations is demonstrated based on heritage and based on an assessment of simulated Keystone measurements.

UV-Vis Heritage

For the Keystone mission the heritage from OSIRIS/Odin (Llewellyn et al., 2004) and SCIAMACHY/Envisat (Bovensmann et al., 1999) is particularly important. OSIRIS is a limb-viewing payload consisting of a UV-Vis spectrograph and 3 NIR channels covering the $\text{O}_2(^1\Delta)$ airglow emission near 1.27 μm as well as OH Meinel emissions at around 1.5 μm . OSIRIS' optical spectrograph covers the spectral range from 280 to 800 nm — which is similar to the spectral range of Keystone — with about 1 nm spectral resolution. SCIAMACHY was capable of performing nadir, limb and solar/lunar occultation measurements covering the spectral range between 220 and 2400 nm with a wavelength-dependent spectral resolution between 0.2 (UV) and 1.5 nm (near-IR). The Keystone L1 requirements on radiometric noise of the UV-VIS instrument at night translate to a LER (Limb Emission Rate) noise of about 1.25×10^8 photons $\text{cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1} \text{nm}^{-1}$ assuming the Goal and about 2.5×10^8 photons $\text{cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1} \text{nm}^{-1}$ assuming the Threshold noise level. These values are significantly lower than the typical LER noise in OSIRIS ($\sim 1 \times 10^9$ photons $\text{cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1} \text{nm}^{-1}$ for green line nightglow measurements) and SCIAMACHY data ($\sim 7 \times 10^9$ photons $\text{cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1} \text{nm}^{-1}$). Based on this comparison, it is concluded that all data products that were successfully retrieved with these heritage instruments would be retrievable from the Keystone UV-VIS measurements with even better performance.

Table 6.1 provides an overview of Keystone data products that were successfully retrieved in past missions (i.e. OSIRIS/Odin, SCIAMACHY/Envisat and WINDII/UARS). The Keystone L2 uncertainty requirements for the UV-Vis products (4.1) are guided by the performances of these heritage missions and are therefore expected to be met.

Figure 6.13: Limb Emission Rate (LER) for O green line (top left), O₂ A-band (top right), O red line (bottom left) and O⁺ (bottom right) emissions. Signals exceed the levels corresponding to the Goal (green) and Threshold (red) radiometric noise requirements (Table 4.4.4) in the target vertical ranges (Credits: C. von Savigny, F. Wrana).

The observation of Lithium emissions is a special case: While profile retrievals have not yet been demonstrated, the Li emission near 671 nm has been identified in dayglow spectra from OSIRIS. For some days, the emission is clearly visible in daily and zonally averaged spectra, for other days, the emission is barely present. It is expected that Li emissions would be detectable in monthly averages, and possibly in averages across shorter periods in cases of strong enhancements caused by re-entering artificial space objects (Wing et al., 2026).

UV-Vis Measurement Signal Levels

An assessment of the measurable signatures has been performed for the most important emissions (O green at 557.7 nm, O₂ around 750 nm, O red at 630 nm, O⁺ at 732 nm). Figure 6.13 shows forward modelled limb emission rates (LER) profiles for the O green line (top left), O₂ A-band (top right), O red line (bottom) panel, and O⁺ (bottom right) emissions. The O green line, O₂ A-band, and O red line signals are based on WACCM-X data representing conditions before and during a solar storm; O⁺ emission profiles were taken from Shepherd et al. (2014). Data were averaged over the 50°–82°S latitude range, where the storm effects are most pronounced. The green and red vertical lines correspond to Goal and Threshold levels of the L1 radiometric noise requirements (Table 4.4.4). For the O green line, only the pre-storm scenario is shown because the storm had very little impact on its amplitude; for the O₂ A-band and the O red line, both the before-storm and the peak-storm scenarios are shown. LER values of the emissions considered exceed by far the noise levels in the target vertical ranges, which confirms that the emissions would be observable with the Keystone UV-Vis payload both before and during the storm event. It is also evident that changes commensurate to the L2 observation uncertainty requirements (20% at peak for O green, 20% in [70-130 km] for O₂-A, 20% at peak for O red, and 30% in [150-250 km]) exceed the radiometric noise level.

Figure 6.14: Volume emission rates of the $O(^1D-^3P)$ red line (top row) and the $O_2(0,0)$ A-band emission (bottom row) as a function of latitude and height before (left), during (middle), and after (right) the Mother's day solar storm 2024. Perturbations by the storm (colours and iso-lines) exceed by far the random noise levels (~ 2 photons $cm^{-3} s^{-1}$ for the O red line VER; < 1 photon $cm^{-3} s^{-1}$ for the O_2 A-band VER) (Credits: C. von Savigny, F. Wrana).

Figure 6.14 illustrates the observable signatures of a solar storm. The VER of the O red line (top) and O_2 A-band (bottom) are depicted before (left), during (middle) and after (right) the event. Both emissions are strongly affected by the storm; variations (see iso-lines) exceed the noise levels (~ 2 photons $cm^{-3} s^{-1}$ for the O red line VER; < 1 photon $cm^{-3} s^{-1}$ for the O_2 A-band VER). It is concluded that Keystone can make essential contributions to improve the understanding of solar storms on the MTS.

Data product	Availability	Source/heritage
[O] profiles from O green line	single scans	OSIRIS data
O green line & O_2 A-band VER profiles	single scans	OSIRIS data
O_2 A-band temperature profiles	single scans	OSIRIS, Sheese et al. (2010)
[O] profiles from A-band	single scans	OSIRIS, Sheese et al. (2011)
[K] profiles	single scans	OSIRIS, Dawkins et al. (2014)
[Na] profiles	single scans	OSIRIS, Gumbel et al. (2007)
O^+ VER profiles	single scans	WINDII data (Shepherd et al., 2014)
[Mg] & $[Mg^+]$ profiles	daily zonally averaged	SCIAMACHY, Langowski et al. (2014)
[Fe] profiles	daily zonally averaged	SCIAMACHY data
[Li] profiles	daily or monthly averaged	see text for details

Table 6.1: Heritage of the Keystone UV-Vis L2 data products.

6.2.4. Synergy of THz and UV-Vis Retrievals of Atomic Oxygen

The synergy between atomic oxygen observations using THz and UV-Vis measurements plays a central role in Keystone's mission objectives. The altitude ranges covered by the two instruments complement each other very well: The THz retrievals cover altitudes up to 250 km and become less sensitive below 100 km. This is where the UV-Vis retrievals are available and allow extending the [O] observations down

Figure 6.15: Uncertainty estimates of [O] retrieved from THz (blue lines) and UV-Vis O green line (orange line) observations for a single scan (dashed line) and an average from pole to pole (solid lines). This figure highlights the excellent complementarity of the [O] retrievals provided by Keystone’s THz and UV-Vis payloads. Their sensitive altitude ranges overlap, allowing for direct comparisons and validation of airglow excitation models as well as for extending the [O] profiles down to below 85 km (Credits: P. B. Hansen, C. von Savigny).

to about 80 km altitude. Figure 6.15 shows uncertainties of [O] profile retrievals from single scan (dashed) and orbital average (solid) measurements of THz (blue) and UV-Vis O green line (orange) emission. In the vertical overlap region (~90–100 km), the quality of both data products are sufficiently high to allow for a joint scientific exploitation, e.g. to test photochemical airglow excitation models.

6.2.5. Main Contributors to THz, IR, and UV-Vis L2 Uncertainty

The main expected contributors to the uncertainty in Keystone L2 products are identified in Table 6.2. The contributors include instrument related as well as retrieval related errors, which depend on observation principles (emission, solar-scattered radiation) and modelling approaches (e.g. NLTE for IR and photochemistry for UV-Vis) employed. The relative importance of each error source varies between data products and instruments.

Error source	L2 THz	L2 IR	L2 UV-Vis
Radiometric noise	1	1	1
Pointing accuracy	2	3	2
Absolute Radiometric Accuracy	2	2	2
ISRF knowledge		3	
PSF knowledge		3	2
Horizontal and vertical smoothing error	2	2	2
Modeling errors:			
NLTE: collisional / reaction rates, a priori knowledge on O, O(¹ D), N(¹ S), N(² D)		1	
Photochemistry: chemical rate constants, a priori knowledge on T, O ₂ , N ₂			2
For NLC products: particle size distribution, meteoric nuclei type/size			2
Spectroscopy	3	3	3
Reference pressure (<i>p</i> ₀)		2	
L2 cross-talk errors or propagated L2 uncertainties	2	2	
Uncertainties in interfering species within channel bandpasses		3	

Table 6.2: Expected L2 product uncertainties for the three instruments. Relative importance of contributions to the total error is indicated with (1) Major, (2) Intermediate, or (3) Minor.

6.3. Campaign Activities

6.3.1. Heritage: Airborne THz Observations of Atomic Oxygen

Low-resolution observations of O using the THz were made with the Cryogenic Infrared Spectrometers and Telescopes for the Atmosphere (CRISTA) on the space shuttle in the 1990s (Offermann et al., 1999; Grossmann et al., 2000). With this spectrometer, atomic oxygen densities were determined at altitudes from 130 to 175 km. THz observations of O were also carried out with the Far-Infrared Spectrometer (FIRS-2), a Fourier transform spectrometer on a high-altitude (~38 km) balloon (Mlynczak et al., 2004); however, the O emission line shape was not resolved and O altitude profiles could not be retrieved.

The first highly spectrally resolved measurements of the THz emission of O were made by DLR using the THz heterodyne spectrometer GREAT (German Receiver for Astronomy at Terahertz Frequencies) on board the Stratospheric Observatory for Infrared Astronomy (SOFIA) (NASA, 2021). The concentration profiles derived from these measurements agree well with atmospheric models based on NRLMSISE-00 and SABER observations (Richter et al., 2021), demonstrating the advantages of high-resolution THz remote sensing of O and the potential of combining THz with IR measurements.

6.3.2. Balloon Campaigns

OSAS-B Campaign 2025

Atomic oxygen in the mesosphere and thermosphere has been measured with DLR's OSAS-B (Oxygen Spectrometer for Atmospheric Science on a Balloon) instrument during stratospheric balloon flights over Kiruna/Sweden in 2022 and Timmins/Canada in August 2025 (Wienold et al., 2024). OSAS-B is a balloon-borne THz heterodyne spectrometer comprising two frequency bands centred at the emission frequencies of atomic oxygen at 2.1 THz and 4.7 THz. Figure 6.16 shows two emission spectra of atomic oxygen with an excellent signal-to-noise ratio: The spectrum at 2.1 THz displays an almost Gaussian-shaped line with no indication of saturation (due to absorption of light by atmospheric O itself), while the emission at 4.7 THz is strongly saturated as indicated by the plateau in the line centre. Measured spectra are in excellent agreement with simulated spectra obtained using forward radiative transfer modelling based on the atomic oxygen concentration (from MSIS 2.1), which confirms the high quality of the measurements and the forward model.

Figure 6.16: Measured emission profiles of the 2.1 THz (left) and 4.7 THz (right) emission lines shown with black lines. The orange lines are simulations with a forward model. The lower panels show the residuals (measured minus simulated). Note that the residuals are less than 3 K (2.1 THz) and 5 K (4.7 THz) corresponding to less than 5% (Credit: DLR).

TV BALLET Campaign 2026

Following the successful 2025 balloon campaign, a new balloon campaign is planned for August 2026 with a launch from the Arctic ESRANGE Space Center. It combines the OSAS-B THz spectrometer (see previous paragraph) with the UV-Vis spectrometer OSIRIS of the University of Saskatchewan (a smaller version of the Optical Spectrograph and InfraRed Imaging System on the Odin satellite). A central goal of the balloon campaign, now being prepared as Thz Visible BALLOonExperiment (TV BALLET), is to develop and test the basic concept of combining THz and UV-Vis observations from a shared platform, analogous to the Keystone instrument suite. This includes joint measurement strategies, co-analysis approaches, and validation against ground-based instrumentation. The campaign will provide valuable data to develop and test retrieval schemes for Keystone L2 target parameters during Phase A. The main focus is on atomic oxygen, related molecules, and atomic and molecular oxygen volume emission rates, which are key to the mission's MTS composition objectives.

7. PRELIMINARY MISSION CONCEPT AND PERFORMANCE

This chapter provides a technical description of the Keystone mission. These proposed technical concepts were developed in a single Phase 0 system study (including associated risk retirement activities) by a consortia led by OHB Systems AG. The industrial consortia consists of OHB Systems AG as payload prime, DLR and RAL Space for the THz instrument, OHB Systems AG for the IR instrument and OIP Sensor Systems N.V. for the UV-Vis instrument. The figures in this chapter are courtesy of the respective industrial consortia unless otherwise stated in the figure’s caption.

7.1. Mission Concept

7.1.1. Mission Architecture

The Keystone mission architecture, as depicted in Figure 7.1, comprises the following elements:

- **Launch Segment:** Keystone is designed to be compatible with launch on Vega-C;
- **Space Segment:** Limb-Scanning Satellite hosting a THz radiometer, Infrared (IR) Multi-Spectral Imager and UV-VIS Spectrometer;
- **Ground Segment:** Keystone is compatible with ESA’s Earth Explorer Ground Segment, utilising only S-Band communications and ground stations.

Keystone would fly in a Low Earth orbit, Sun Synchronous orbit. The co-aligned three payload complement provide observations in the THz, Infrared and UV-VIS domains. Keystone would provide Along-Track Limb observations across tangent heights between 50 km and 250 km by means of scanning the instrument continuously throughout every orbit.

Figure 7.1: Keystone mission architecture and summary of the baseline Keystone mission concept (Credit: OHB System AG).

7.1.2. Observation Geometry and Sampling Concept

Keystone adopts along-track (ALT) limb sounding as the nominal observation geometry, in which the instrument line of sights observe in the flight direction. These line of sights are scanned vertically through the atmosphere to cover all target tangent point heights. This configuration provides a robust compromise between vertical coverage, horizontal sampling and platform stability, consistent with the mission requirements defined in Chapter 4. The observation geometry is illustrated in Figure 4.3.

The vertical scan law is dedicated for each observation mode with a slow upward scan ($0.01^\circ/s$ to $0.14^\circ/s$) used for science acquisition followed by a faster return slew ($0.08^\circ/s$ to $0.18^\circ/s$) towards the lowest tangent height (50–70 km). The observation modes, including their vertical and horizontal sampling characteristics, are defined in Chapter 4 and summarised in Table 4.2. These modes are used to define the system architecture, report performance compliance and define the observation scenarios and therefore drive the system design. The scan timing is primarily driven by the THz instrument radiometric sensitivity, which sets the integration time per tangent altitude to 2 seconds.

Additionally, during the faster return phase there is the opportunity to continue observations when internal calibration is not required. This would increase the point cloud density of sampling, though with degraded resolution due to the faster speed. This would be investigated within Phase A.

Keystone adopts continuous ALT sounding as the baseline, while retaining the capability for occasional campaign observations to sample in an Across track (AXT) direction, perpendicular to the satellite velocity, through a dedicated 90° spacecraft yaw manoeuvre. The available observation time in AXT mode is mainly governed by the varying illumination conditions in the orbit, affecting power generation and radiator rejection capability. Therefore, the total time for AXT observations is limited between 15 min and 40 min at a frequency of every 1–4 orbits, depending on the orbit location of the observations.

The three instruments are co-aligned to observe a common atmospheric volume at the tangent point. Their projected fields of view at the tangent point, illustrated in Figure 7.2, remain confined by the AXT co-registration of the instrument channels within a limited cross-track extent of 55 km, enabling co-registered multi-spectral observations of nearly the same air mass.

The THz channels sample the scene with footprints of 2.5–4.5 km, the IR instrument with footprints of 2 km, and the UV-Visible spectrometer with a rectangular footprint of 40 km horizontally and 5 km vertically at the tangent point. This combined sampling supports consistent retrieval of temperature, pressure, composition and wind products across the different spectral domains.

Figure 7.2: Projected fields of view at the atmospheric tangent point altitude of 70 km, of the Keystone THz, IR and UV-Visible instruments. The figure illustrates the vertical and across-track co-registration of the different spectral channels in a plane normal to the line of sight, relative to the tangent point of the 2.06 THz channel (Credit: P. Martín-Iglesias).

The temporal sampling is primarily driven by the THz instrument, whose radiometric sensitivity requirements impose integration times of around 2 seconds per altitude level. This leads to scan durations of 40 to 80 seconds (depending on the observation mode) for the science acquisition phase, followed by a faster return motion of between 26 and 60 seconds (depending on the observation mode). The total scan duration is then constrained by the required horizontal sampling in each mode, leading to a trade-off between integration time required for the radiometric requirements and platform agility.

7.1.3. Driving Requirements

The driving requirements for Keystone are shown in Table 7.1 and discussed below.

Parameter	Requirement	Reference
Coverage	Global Coverage	4.3
Co-registration AXT / Vertical	<55 km / <400 m	4.4.1
Tangent Point Height Knowledge	<400 m	4.2.1
AXT Sampling	<1000 km	4.2
ALT Sampling*	400–1250 km	4.2
Vertical Sampling / Resolution*	1–10 km / 2.5–25 km	4.2.1
Altitude Range*	50 km to 250 km	4.2.3
THz NEDT	<8 K @ 1 THz and <31 K @ 2 THz	4.4.2
UV-VIS SNR	>50 at night, >100 during day	4.4.4
IR NEDT	< $2.8 \times 10^{-4} W m^{-2} sr^{-1}$ for IR 1/2 & < $1.3 \times 10^{-5} W m^{-2} sr^{-1}$ for IR 4/5/6	4.4.3
IR ARA	<5% (T) / <3% (G) of the signal	4.4.3
Spectral Channels/Range/Sampling	THz: 1-2 lines per species in range 1–2.5 THz	4.4.2
	UV-VIS: 275–775 nm (T), 240–800 nm (G) @ 1 nm (G), 2 nm resolution (T)	4.4.4
Lifetime	IR: 5 Channels between 1.78 μm - 15.5 μm	4.4.4
	3 years (T), 5 years (G) + 2 years of propellant	4.3

Table 7.1: Driving Requirements Summary. References refer to section numbers within this document.

* These driving parameters are defined differently for the specific observation modes shown in Table 4.2 and discussed in Section 4.2.3. The ranges across all modes are shown here.

Along Track and Vertical Sampling, Vertical Ranges and THz Radiometric Requirements

The Keystone mission concept is primarily driven by sensitivity and sampling requirements. The satisfaction of the ALT and vertical sampling requirements, coupled with the altitude ranges of tangent heights to be observed per scan and the THz radiometric sensitivity, directly define the operational scenario of Keystone. This scenario constrains the time available between tangent height samples and hence imposes limits on the maximum integration time of the instruments and the 'return time' of the scan to the next tangent height sample. From these operational constraints, driving requirements are derived on the vertical scanning strategy and consequently on the scan law and platform agility. Conversely, a minimum integration time is imposed by the THz radiometric sensitivity requirements when technological constraints are considered. These constraints define a narrow operational window of suitable integration times, around 2 seconds per sample. In addition, the fixed spectral resolution requirements further constrain the achievable radiometric performance, limiting the ability to trade integration time against sensitivity. The resulting radiometric performance requirements drive the receiver noise temperature, and consequently the need for cryogenic cooling of the THz front-end. The radiometric and absolute accuracy requirements further drive the calibration concept, including calibration frequency, which directly interact with the scanning strategy and observation duty cycle.

Co-Registration and Geometric Requirements

The need for co-registered multi-instrument measurements (THz, IR, UV-Visible), defined as the tangent point, imposes stringent requirements on co-registration accuracy. In particular, the driving aspect is the vertical co-registration of the spectral samples. Similarly, the Tangent Height Knowledge

requirement of each sample is a key driver, being highly sensitive to across line-of-sight pointing errors. Both requirements require state-of-the-art co-registration within and between each instrument, especially in regards to in-orbit alignment knowledge, on-ground co-alignment, thermoelastic stability and AOCS pointing knowledge. The Tangent Height Knowledge requirement in particular drives the need for the star trackers to be hosted on the payload module to limit the corresponding error contributions and ensure compliance. These constraints directly translate into stringent requirements on payload structural stability and microvibration control. The tangent point geolocation knowledge, along-track co-registration and across-track co-registration are compliant and do not drive the design.

Spectral Requirements, IR and UV-VIS Radiometric Requirements

The major driver for the Keystone mission as a whole is the need for multi-spectral measurements across multiple frequency ranges. For the THz instrument, radiometric and spectral performance jointly govern the front-end design, particularly at 2 THz. This imposes demanding requirements in terms of sensitivity, bandwidth, spectral resolution and spectral knowledge, leading to stringent constraints on the local oscillator chain and frequency stability. The required technologies for local oscillator generation, mixing, and amplification in a cryogenic environment rely on state-of-the-art processes, with a need for early development to consolidate the design and confirm the achievable performance. The radiometric performance requirements further drive the receiver noise temperature and dynamic range, imposing strict linearity and calibration constraints on the detection chain.

The IR in particular is driven by the need for long-wavelength coverage up to 15.5 μm , which requires state-of-the-art European detector technology. These high IR wavelengths lead to increased dark noise in the system which, in conjunction with the radiometric requirements, drives the cooling need for the IR focal plane, requiring a cryogenically cooled detector (of the order of 60 K). The IR radiometric requirements (NEDT and ARA) also impose the need for a two-point calibration scheme including the accommodation of an internal blackbody.

Finally, the UV-VIS spectrometer requirements include a large spectral range extending into the UV, which drives performance both spectrally and radiometrically, as well as imposing strict requirements on cleanliness and internal alignment activities. This is compounded by the requirement for an SNR of 50 during nighttime acquisitions, driven primarily by the UV region where detector sensitivity is reduced. This drives the need for high optical throughput, including grating efficiency and detector performance, as well as appropriate instrument design and calibration.

7.1.4. Mission Analysis and Coverage Considerations

Several orbit options were investigated during Phase 0, including Sun-synchronous (SSO) and non-SSO (inclined, drifting LTAN) low Earth orbits at altitudes of 400–900 km and repeat cycles from 1 to 30 days. The analysis covered coverage, sampling, illumination, ΔV and operational aspects to identify a robust baseline.

The selected baseline is a low-altitude SSO at ~ 460 km with LTAN of 10:00, offering the best trade-off between coverage, illumination stability, calibration robustness, potential sun-blinding events, thermal simplicity, launcher compatibility and compliance to space debris mitigation requirements. Low-altitude SSO solutions (420–460 km) ensure improved across track spatial sampling, due to the faster orbital periods, and vertical scanning performance, as at lower altitudes the scan range is reduced. These orbits also are compatible with lifetime and platform constraints, and enabling efficient tomographic reconstruction without excessive orbit maintenance.

(a) Ascending orbit track spacing vs Lat. (b) Num. of samples in a Lat. Band $x \pm 2.5^\circ$ (c) Keystone Global Sampling

Figure 7.4: Keystone sampling at a Tangent Height = 100 km, after 3 days with ALT sampling of 550 km equivalent to the Zoom Horizontal Mode. See Table 4.2 for specification of all modes (Credit: K. Palmer).

The adopted 15+1/3 repeat cycle ensures that the distance between vertical profiles at the equator is <870 km after 3 days (see Figure 7.4). The resulting geometry ensures repeatable and homogeneous global sampling of tangent heights with respect to the Earth’s surface (Figure 7.5). The orbit is compatible with launcher performance, mission lifetime and debris mitigation requirements. The total ΔV budget (320–330 m/s over 7.5 years, including disposal) remains within the capabilities of the selected, standard platform and supports controlled re-entry.

Figure 7.5: Example of the nominal Keystone limb-sounding observation geometry for the selected Sun-synchronous orbit baseline (~460 km altitude). The coloured track shows the evolution of atmospheric tangent point altitudes during consecutive vertical scans, illustrating the along-track sampling pattern and the spatial coverage achieved by the instrument. The grey markers indicate the satellite ground track (Credit: P. Martín-Iglesias).

7.2. Satellite & Platform Design

The mission-level analyses performed during Phase 0 converge towards a space segment architecture based on a single spacecraft carrying a co-registered three-instrument payload. The vertical limb scanning concept is implemented through spacecraft attitude steering with a payload-based scanning capability retained as a compatible performance-enhancement option to ensure sufficient timing margin and operational robustness.

The spacecraft platform, currently using the 4 solar panel variant of the OHB EOS Standard platform, implements the platform-driven scanning concept and provides the pointing, thermal and structural stability required to achieve the observation and sampling performance defined above.

7.2.1. Scanning Concept

The definition of the vertical scanning concept results from a trade-off between platform-based attitude steering and a dedicated payload scanning mechanism. Platform scanning offers architectural simplicity and avoids the introduction of moving parts within the payload, but is limited in terms of achievable scanning speeds, agility, and operational flexibility. Conversely, a payload-based scanning mechanism enables significantly faster motion (reducing the return time), at the expense of additional complexity, mass, and potential micro-vibration contributions. Phase 0 analyses converged towards a hybrid approach in which the platform provides the baseline scanning capability while maintaining compatibility with a dedicated payload scanning system as a performance enhancement option, in line with the system-level trades reported in the payload concept design.

Figure 7.6: Illustration of the Keystone line-of-sight (LOS) scanning geometry. The satellite performs a pitch scan, sweeping the instrument field of view across a range of viewing angles. The resulting LOS directions are indicated by the red vectors (left). An example of the vertical sampling for the Standard Operation mode (2 s integration time per sample) and the along-track sampling distance requirement are shown in purple for illustration (right) (Credit: P. Martín-Iglesias).

In the baseline implementation, the vertical scan is generated through spacecraft attitude steering, as illustrated by the line-of-sight geometry in Figure 7.6 and the corresponding timing diagram of the measurement cycle in Figure 7.7, with science acquisition performed during a slow upward scan followed by a faster return motion. The required scanning is continuous but remains within a limited angular excursion ($\sim 1\text{--}3^\circ$ depending on the mode, always $< 6^\circ$), with typical upward scan velocities in the range $0.01\text{--}0.15^\circ/\text{s}$, depending on the mode, and moderate accelerations of a few $10^{-3}\text{--}10^{-2} \text{ }^\circ/\text{s}^2$.

The upward scan is dominated by quasi-constant cruise phases (typically $\sim 10\text{--}80$ s depending on the mode), ensuring stable radiometric acquisition, while the return motion is performed significantly faster (typically $\sim 25\text{--}60$ s), resulting in total cycle durations on the order of $\sim 70\text{--}160$ s.

Figure 7.7: Illustration of the timing diagram of the measurement cycle (Standard Operational mode) showing platform scanning profile and instrument operation, including science acquisition, calibration phases, and THz cold-sky opportunities (Credit: P. Martín-Iglesias).

The AOCS analyses in Phase 0, based on the CO2M/EOS AOCS simulator, demonstrate compliance to the required scan amplitudes, slew rates and platform pointing performance for the observation modes, delivering the ALT and vertical sampling performances.

A dedicated payload scanning system is retained as a performance-enhancement option completely compatible with the current design. This system allows significantly faster return motions, typically on the order of a few seconds instead of tens of seconds for platform manoeuvres, improving the ALT sampling distance. This system consists of a common scanning mechanism located in front of the three instruments, Figure 7.8, using flat mirrors to steer the instantaneous field of view of each channel along a common scan axis. This architecture allows all instruments to share a consistent line-of-sight geometry while keeping their telescopes fixed, minimizing moving mass and improving optical co-registration stability.

Figure 7.8: View of the payload scanning mechanism and common scan mirror configuration (Credit: OHB System AG).

7.2.2. Attitude and Orbit Control & Pointing Performance

The Attitude and Orbit Control System (AOCS) ensures accurate and stable satellite pointing performances and initiates the required scan law, see Section 7.2.1, and complies with the driving requirements shown in Section 7.1.3. The subsystem achieves the pointing towards the required Earth limb view throughout the orbit, compensating for the effects of Earth oblateness and orbit inclination. The AOCS design incorporates the common set of actuators and sensors, including a coarse gyroscope.

The driving geometric performances, AXT co-registration and Tangent point height knowledge, are driven by spacecraft attitude knowledge and stability, combined with instrument alignment and thermo-elastic effects between the payload and the attitude reference sensors. While the AOCS provides arcsecond-level attitude knowledge and sub-arcsecond stability, the overall pointing budget is dominated by system-level contributions, including alignment knowledge between star trackers and instrument line-of-sight and thermo-elastic deformations along the optical path.

All geometric performances, including those driving the design, are assessed as compliant at this stage.

7.2.3. Mechanical, Thermal & Propulsion Design

From a mechanical perspective, the payload is mounted on a stiff internal optical bench designed to ensure high structural stability, supporting the compliance to the driving AXT co-registration and tangent height knowledge requirements. The instruments are rigidly fixed with respect to this structure. This configuration minimizes moving mass and reduces sensitivity to disturbances, which is particularly important in the presence of cryogenic subsystems. The overall accommodation is driven by the need to maintain precise co-alignment between instruments, ensure favourable radiator placement towards cold space, and minimise thermo-elastic distortions over the mission lifetime.

Thermal design is a key driver of the payload configuration. The IR instrument requires cooling to 60 K, while one of the THz instrument concepts requires 80 K, implying active cooling. The total payload dissipation is therefore around 400 W. Phase 0 assessed both distributed cryogenic architectures (dedicated cryocoolers per instrument) and shared cooling-chain solutions. Both are expected to be within the available radiator capacity and power budget, with current thermal sizing (e.g. 130 W at 260 K and 75 W at 290 K interfaces) providing sufficient margin to meet combined IR and THz cooling needs under conservative assumptions. The preferred concept adopts instrument-level cryocoolers, minimising thermal cross-coupling, simplifying interfaces, and enabling independent optimisation of temperature stability. The IR instrument dominates the cryogenic load, with remaining capacity available for the THz subsystem and other elements, confirming overall compliance to the design constraints with margin. Shared architectures remain an option to be studied in Phase A. The optical bench is thermally stabilised to preserve co-registration and radiometric performance, including temperature control of critical elements such as THz calibration loads.

Finally, the propulsion subsystem included with the EOS standard platform is shown to be compatible with the delta-V and propulsion requirements (Table 7.5) of the Keystone mission.

7.2.4. Power and Energy Storage

With the need for cryocooling and the three instrument architectures, Keystone requires four solar panels of 3 m² each and two battery modules, as used on EE10 Harmony mission, is used to provide ample power generation and storage for all operations. These systems are well within the qualified capabilities of the EOS platform.

7.2.5. Payload Data Handling, Data Downlink, and TT&C

The Keystone concept relies fully on the EOS standard platform data handling and control electronics units and falls well within its capabilities. The currently stated data volume of the Keystone mission in its Standard Operational Mode is 15.7 Gbits/day, has enabled the use of a combined data downlink and Telemetry, Tracking and Control subsystem (see Section 7.2.7 and Table 7.4 for details). This encompasses the use of a single, redundant S-band subsystem for both daily control passes and 1–2 data downlink passes per orbit.

7.2.6. Operational Concept

The architecture supports near-continuous limb observations. Science acquisition is performed during the upward scan, while calibration activities are interleaved between successive scans, with integration times of a few seconds per tangent altitude. The scanning system is described in Section 7.2.1 and the sampling concept in Section 7.1.2. An example operational scan sequence shown in Figure 7.7.

The operational strategy will make use of daily S-band TT&C passes to upload to the spacecraft a mission timeline including the modes to be deployed. These modes can be switched between in a sub-orbital frequency but it is expected that they will be maintained across multiple orbits at least. Calibration is largely interleaved seamlessly into the science observations or during the 'return' phase of the scanning concept. Additional calibration needs, vicarious or specific targets, can also be accommodated at their desciired frequencies whilst maintaining a compliant availability budget. The technical requirements and frequencies of the calibration needed per instrument is discussed in Section 7.4.3.

7.2.7. Satellite configuration and budgets

The satellite mass and power budgets can be found in Tables 7.2 and 7.3. The satellite is well within the launcher capability, with 924 kg of margin, and the full payload module mass is well within the capabilities of the EOS platform. The power needs are also within the EOS platform capabilities.

Subsystem	Mass [kg]
Platform Dry Mass	843.6
Payload	
THz Instrument	42.5.0
UV–VIS Instrument	23.0
Infrared Instrument	38.5
Payload Module Structure & Radiator	108.0
Payload Mass	212.0
Total Dry Mass + 15% System Margin	1213.9
Propellant Mass	206.7
Total Wet Mass	1420.6
Launcher Adapter	95.0
Total Launch Mass	1515.6
Expected Launcher Performance	2440.0
Excess Launcher Capacity	924.4

Table 7.2: Spacecraft mass budget.

The Keystone sampling concepts and its instrumentation provide a data rate of 182.1 kbits/s which results in a daily data volume of 15.7 Gbits/day, see Table 7.4. As discussed in Section 7.2.5, this data volume facilitates the use of a combined S-Band TT&C and payload downlink strategy and the removal of the X-band subsytem from the platform.

Subsystem	Power [W]
Platform Total	670.7
Payload	
THz Instrument	150.0
Infrared Instrument	60.0
UV–VIS Instrument	18.0
IR & Thz Cryocoolers	156.0
Payload Power Consumption	384.0
Spacecraft Total	1054.7
System Margin (15%)	158.2
Total Power	1212.9

Table 7.3: Spacecraft power budget.

Parameter	Value
Instrument Average Orbital Data Rates	
THz	179.6 kbit/s
IR	0.04 kbit/s
UV-VIS	2.5 kbit/s
Total Data Rate	182.1 kbit/s
Data Volume	
Orbital Data Volume	1024.9 Mbit/orbit
Daily Data Volume	15.7 Gbit/day

Table 7.4: Keystone Data Volume and Rate Budget for Standard Operational Mode.

The Keystone orbit, at reference altitude of 459.8 km has significant orbit maintenance requirements due to the low orbit but which is offset with a lower disposal burn required at end of life to safely deorbit Keystone in a controlled manner. In total, the Delta-V required for 7.5 years (6 months commissioning, Goal lifetime of 5 years + 2 extra years of propellant load) is 330 m/s, which requires just under 200 kg of fuel. This is well within the capabilities of the propulsion subsystem that is part of the EOS standard platform which accommodates up to 230 kg of Hydrazine.

Finally, the Keystone satellite is shown in Figure 7.9 to demonstrate the compatibility volumetrically with the Vega-C fairing (255 mm to the platform and 835 mm to the payload), with 924 kg margin to its launch capability and compliance to the launcher requirements on centre-of-mass and launch frequencies.

Manoeuvre / Mission Phase	ΔV [m/s]
Nominal Orbit Acquisition	
Injection Error Correction	24.65
Orbit Maintenance	
In-Plane Control	83.95
Out-of-Plane Control	53.32
Collision Avoidance	
Collision Avoidance Manoeuvres	33.46
End-of-Life Disposal	
Controlled Re-entry Burn	134.22
Total	
ΔV (incl. 15% margin)	329.59
Propellant Mass [kg]	199.65

Table 7.5: Keystone ΔV budget for a 459.8 km SSO orbit with a 7.5-year operational lifetime.

Figure 7.9: Keystone satellite compatibility with the Vega-C fairing, showing significant mass and volume margin (Credit: OHB Systems AG).

7.2.8. Ground Segment

The ground segment remains compatible with the standard Earth Explorer operational principles, including separation between flight operations and payload data processing. Phase 0 analyses of data flow, downlink and latency confirm compatibility with realistic ground-station visibility and data-handling constraints, without requiring non-standard concepts. In fact, Keystone would only rely on the S-band Ground station network as an X-band downlink system is currently assessed as not necessary.

7.2.9. Compliance with Debris Policy

Compliance with debris mitigation requirements is ensured through an end-of-life controlled re-entry strategy. The mission-level ΔV budget includes disposal, launcher injection correction, routine orbit maintenance and collision avoidance, and is incorporated in the baseline architecture.

7.3. Payload

7.3.1. Payload Overview

The Keystone space segment consists of a single satellite accommodating a co-registered three-instrument limb-sounding payload: a THz heterodyne spectrometer operating over 143–273 μm (1.1–2.1 THz), an infrared radiometer covering 2.07–14.9 μm , and a UV-Visible spectrometer spanning 240–800 nm.

This multi-spectral payload enables simultaneous retrieval of key atmospheric parameters, including atomic oxygen, temperature, winds and trace gases. Co-registration ensures consistent sampling of a common atmospheric volume across the three instruments, as illustrated in Figure 4.6.

In the proposed system architecture, each of the instruments are mechanically fixed to the payload module throughout nominal operations, with the line-of-sight scan generated through spacecraft attitude steering. This configuration minimises moving mass and supports stable optical alignment over the mission lifetime. It ensures inherent temporal and spatial synchronisation of the payloads and allows the co-registration requirements to be met by design rather than through operational correction. The projected fields of view of each instrument, in this configuration, can be seen in Figure 7.2. A dedicated flat scan mirror for each payload would be considered as part of the back-up payload scanning implementation only, as discussed in Section 7.2.1.

Figure 7.10: Baseline Keystone mission architecture and payload accommodation concept (left, Credit: OHB System AG) together with the Keystone payload electronic architecture overview (right, Credits: OHB System AG, P. Martín-Iglesias).

7.3.2. THz Instrument

The Terahertz (THz) instrument is the key scientific enabler of the Keystone mission, as it provides, for the first time, direct satellite-based observations of atomic oxygen in the mesosphere and lower thermosphere. Its heterodyne limb-sounding approach provides high spectral resolution and frequency accuracy, supporting the retrieval of species concentrations, temperature, pressure and line-of-sight winds from atmospheric emission lines. These objectives impose stringent constraints on radiometric sensitivity, optical stability, vertical resolution and calibration accuracy, which strongly influence the overall payload and system architecture.

Architecturally, the THz instrument is implemented as a dedicated limb sounder with its own telescope, front-end optics, optical distribution network and receiver chain. At Phase 0, two parallel industrial studies were initiated for the THz instrument, led respectively by DLR (DE) and RAL Space (UK), to explore alternative implementations and consolidate the instrument concept. The DLR study is referred to as Concept 1, while the RAL Space study is referred to as Concept 2. While a common telescope design is adopted in both concepts, the optical distribution network, receiver design, and thermal architecture are concept-specific and differ between the two implementations.

Instrument Concept and Measurement Chain

The measurement concept relies on spectrally resolved atmospheric emission lines, whose frequencies, shapes and Doppler shifts provide sensitivity to species concentration, temperature and line-of-sight winds. The instrument frequency coverage is therefore driven by the selection of spectral lines required to meet MO.1, MO.3 and MO.4.

Among the available atomic oxygen transitions, the line around 2.06 THz was selected as the preferred solution, enabling compliance with the vertical resolution requirement (< 2.5 km) while remaining compatible with moderate instrument complexity. Higher-frequency alternatives around 4.7 THz, as well as complementary concepts targeting O_2 , H_2O and OH transitions in the 0.77 THz and 2.5–3.5 THz ranges, were assessed during Phase 0 but not retained because of their higher implementation complexity, technical maturity (particularly at 2.5, 3.5 and 4.7 THz), thermal constraints and technology demands.

Receiver architecture and frequency allocation

Radiation collected by the telescope is routed through an optical distribution network towards a limited number of broadband receiver chains, typically two or three depending on the design concept, covering bands selected within the ranges 1.1–1.2 THz and 1.8–2.1 THz. This enables simultaneous observation of multiple spectral lines while limiting the number of receiver channels.

The 1–2.1 THz range contains numerous spectral lines from several species, providing broad diagnostic capability (See Figure 4.7). In contrast, atomic oxygen is characterised by a single transition (around 2.06 THz) within the accessible frequency ranges, which defines a mandatory observing band, while only a limited number of OH lines are available, primarily within the 1.8–2.1 THz range. These constraints drive the selection of the receiver bands, around which additional spectral lines are grouped to maximise scientific return within the available bandwidth.

During Phase 0, consortia were provided with required spectral lines, candidate line catalogues and expected brightness temperatures for each species. These inputs supported the optimisation of the instrument frequency plan and receiver architecture through the optical distribution network, where frequency separation and routing are achieved using polarisation splitters and/or dichroic elements. This enables simultaneous observation of multiple spectral bands while minimising optical losses, a key driver of system noise temperature and radiometric sensitivity.

Figure 7.11: Tracing of geophysical observables to THz receiver bands for the two Keystone receiver concepts: Concept 1 (left) and Concept 2 (right) (Credit: P. Martin-Iglesias).

This trade-off between spectral coverage, receiver count and scientific return drives the allocation of frequency bands to the receivers. Two representative implementations developed by DLR and RAL are shown in Figure 7.11, illustrating different band-allocation strategies and spectral-line distributions across the receiver bands.

Each receiver chain is based on a sub-harmonic Schottky-diode mixer driven by a high-frequency local oscillator. This technology is well suited for spaceborne THz applications because it enables operation at very high frequencies with mature and robust performance while requiring limited or no active cooling compared with superconducting alternatives. This simplifies the thermal architecture at instrument and spacecraft level, albeit at the expense of higher noise temperatures compared with HEB mixers. The generation and distribution of stable, low-phase-noise local oscillator signals through frequency multiplication chains nevertheless remain important drivers for instrument complexity, stability and power consumption. An example of a high-frequency Schottky mixer implementation is shown in Figure 7.12.

The down-converted intermediate-frequency signals are further processed through amplification, filtering and, where required, additional frequency conversion stages before being analysed by a high-resolution spectrometer backend, such as a Chirp Transform Spectrometer, providing high heritage and maturity, or a Fast Fourier Transform Spectrometer, offering increased flexibility in bandwidth allocation and reduced complexity of the intermediate-frequency processing. The spectral resolution of the back-end directly determines the capability to resolve pressure- and Doppler-broadened line shapes as well as small Doppler shifts, and is therefore critical for accurate wind, temperature and composition retrieval.

Figure 7.12: SEM image of a 1200 GHz mixer developed for JUICE-SWI (left) and 2 THz mixer and multiplier blocks (right) (Credits: LIRA, CNRS – Observatoire de Paris).

Radiometric sensitivity is governed by the overall system noise temperature, including contributions from the mixer, optical losses and first-stage LNA. Critical front-end components therefore require passive or active cooling depending on the selected implementation, directly impacting payload accommodation, power consumption and system complexity. In the Concept 1 implementation, the THz front-end relies on a dedicated cryo-cooler independent from the IR cooling chain, simplifying thermal interfaces and reducing operational coupling. Calibration approach is described inside section 7.4.

THz Receiver Designs

Within the common payload architecture, two independent THz receiver concepts were developed in parallel during Phase 0. Both concepts are compatible with the adopted platform-based scanning architecture and support co-registered measurements with the IR and UV-Vis instruments, while also remaining compatible with a payload-level scanning approach based on a dedicated scanning mechanism. They differ primarily in receiver partitioning, bandwidth strategy and cooling philosophy, leading to different trade-offs in optical complexity, thermal architecture and subsystem integration.

Design Concept 1: Broadband Dual-Channel Receiver Concept

Concept 1 adopts a broadband heterodyne architecture with a limited number of wideband receiver channels covering large instantaneous bandwidths, enabling simultaneous observation of multiple spectral lines.

This concept relies on active cooling of critical front-end components to achieve the required radiometric performance over large bandwidths, enabling a reduced number of receiver chains and a simplified optical distribution based primarily on polarisation splitting. Compared with Concept 2, this approach simplifies the optical chain and receiver partitioning, but introduces increased thermal complexity, power consumption and cryocooler integration requirements.

Receiver noise temperatures for this approach are of the order of 6,400 K (SSB) at ~ 1.1 THz and 13,400 K at ~ 2 THz, assuming an operating temperature of 80 K.

Figure 7.13: THz receiver architecture concepts considered for Keystone: Concept 1 (left) and Concept 2 (right) (Credit: P. Martin-Iglesias).

Design Concept 2: Tri-Band Narrower-Channel Receiver Concept

Concept 2 adopts a segmented approach in which the THz measurement requirements are met by three narrower-band receiver chains, each optimised for a defined subset of spectral lines, emphasising modularity and frequency selectivity.

In this implementation, individual frequency bands are served by dedicated heterodyne receiver chains and associated local oscillator subsystems. The reduced instantaneous bandwidth per chain relaxes IF processing requirements but increases the number of receiver chains. As a result, the optical distribution network becomes more complex, requiring frequency-selective elements such as dichroic filters in addition to polarisation splitting in order to route the different bands to their respective receivers (See section 7.3.2).

Thermal control relies primarily on passively cooled front-end components, typically in the range of 150–220 K, including the mixer, first-stage LNA and parts of the local oscillator chain. This approach reduces the demand on cryogenic subsystems at the expense of increased optical and integration complexity.

Receiver noise temperatures for this approach are of the order of 6,100 K (SSB) in the ~ 1.1 THz band and 12,100 K around 2 THz.

Optical Design Concept and Distribution Network

The THz optical design consists of a front-end telescope, common to both proposed THz instrument concepts, coupled to an optical distribution network and heterodyne receivers, optimised for 1.1–2.1 THz limb emission with high efficiency and low loss. The most stringent vertical resolution requirement (~ 2.5 km), driven by atomic oxygen observations, determines the observing frequency and, via diffraction, the primary mirror size.

In the nominal configuration, the telescope is fixed and vertical scanning is achieved through spacecraft attitude steering, with a scan mirror defined as a back-up design for payload-scanning. The telescope adopts a compact off-axis reflective architecture compatible with accommodation constraints.

The primary mirror (M1), sized to ~ 18 cm from a trade-off between angular resolution, sensitivity, and accommodation, ensures the required performance at 2.06 THz. For tangent point distances of ~ 1700 – 2400 km, this corresponds to vertical resolutions ~ 2.5 – 5 km across the band. The effective resolution also includes motion smearing due to spacecraft motion and finite integration times (~ 2 s), which is comparable to the beam size; the selected aperture provides margin when both effects are accounted for.

The optical distribution network separates the incoming radiation into receiver bands. A dual-channel implementation uses a wire-grid polarizer, minimizing loss and complexity, whereas tri-band solutions require dichroics or lower-loss Martin–Puplett diplexers. A preliminary feedhorn design has been implemented, providing a more realistic representation of the antenna pattern performance.

Optical losses (mirrors, polarisers, splitters) directly increase system noise temperature and include both ohmic and spillover contributions, the latter driven by straylight and instrument thermal environment. Their minimisation, together with beam quality, sidelobe control, and thermo-elastic stability, is a key design driver. Losses are expected to be a few tenths of a dB per element, with feedhorns dominating pre-mixer contributions; these can be reduced via mixer integration in the horn block.

Phase 0 analyses confirm that the telescope and optical distribution network meet the payload requirements in terms of beamwidth, beam efficiency, cross-polarisation, optical losses, and accommodation. The overall optical configurations are shown in Figure 7.14.

Representative antenna patterns at 1.15 THz and 2.06 THz are shown in Figure 7.15, illustrating the beam shape and angular distribution of the radiated power. The results confirm the expected narrowing of the beam at higher frequencies and the compatibility of the antenna performance with the required spatial resolution.

Figure 7.14: Conceptual optical layout of the Keystone THz instrument, illustrating the telescope, optical distribution network, and receiver accommodation for receiver Concept 1 (right) and Concept 2 (left) (Credit: Thomas Keating Ltd., RAL Space and DLR).

Figure 7.15: Beam intensity (total power) as a function of viewing angles θ_x and θ_y at 1150 and 2060 GHz. The left panel corresponds to 1150 GHz and the right panel to 2060 GHz (Credit: Thomas Keating Ltd., P. Martín-Iglesias & S. van Berkel).

Critical RF Technologies and Risk-Reduction Activities

A number of critical RF technologies have been identified during the Keystone Phase 0 activities, in particular for the THz receiver subsystem. Several have already benefited from ESA Technology Development Element (TDE) activities, notably in local oscillator generation and calibration subsystems, including Schottky-based frequency multipliers, Quantum Cascade Lasers (QCLs), low-phase-noise oscillators and quasi-optical calibration reference targets.

The development of high-performance Schottky-based THz receivers at frequencies approaching and exceeding 2 THz remains challenging, with limited demonstrated heritage worldwide. Europe benefits from a well-established ecosystem of specialised institutes and industrial partners with recognised expertise in THz heterodyne instrumentation, high-frequency multiplier chains, mixer technologies and quasi-optical systems, including LERMA/LIRA – CNRS Observatoire de Paris, Chalmers University of Technology, the Rutherford Appleton Laboratory (RAL), AAC Clyde - Omnisys, ACST and RPG. This technological base provides Keystone with access to advanced European capabilities in spaceborne THz instrumentation.

Additional Risk Reduction Activities (RRAs) have been initiated during Phase 0 to address key RF components and subsystem performance. These include the design and breadboarding of the Quasi-Optical Network (QON) to assess insertion losses in the receiver noise budget, and the characterisation of radiometric and frequency stability of a 1.2 THz Schottky-based receiver inherited from the JUICE-SWI development.

Further RRAs are being initiated to extend and validate Schottky receiver technology towards frequencies around 2 THz, improving receiver noise performance under both ambient and cryogenic operating conditions.

7.3.3. Ultraviolet – Visible Spectrometer (UV-Vis) Instrument

The UV-Visible (UV-Vis) instrument is implemented as a limb-viewing grating spectrometer operating currently in the 275–775 nm spectral range. Within the Keystone payload complement, the instrument provides synergistic observations of airglow emissions and scattered solar radiation.

Instrument Concept

The UV-Vis instrument concept is a grating spectrometer with a dedicated telescope and spectrometer assembly. The driving requirements for the UV-VIS instrument are discussed in Section 7.1.3 and include the spectral range, the spectral resolution and the SNR of the measurements at night. The large field of view of the UV-VIS instrument covering 50 km in the across line of sight direction and 5 km in the vertical direction, coupled with a qualified matrix detector and integration times of up to 2 s provide the SNR higher than 50 required for night observations. These nighttime observations are critical to capture the airglow emissions. The daytime SNR requirement of greater than 100 is automatically satisfied with the compliant nighttime SNR. During the Phase A, the possibility of adapting the design to extend the spectral range and reduce the vertical resolution towards the Goal requirements would be explored.

Design Concept 1: Single Channel, Single-Blaze Grating Design

Concept 1 of the UV-VIS is built bottom up based on the Keystone requirements by the subcontractor, whilst relying on their specific heritage in space optical instrumentation. The design is a single-blaze convex grating and aspheric mirror design that ensures a compact, low complexity system.

The optical unit of the UV-Vis payload comprises of the telescope, consisting of an off-axis parabola, and the Offner spectrometer, as shown in Figure 7.16. The slit is perpendicular to the scanning direction, resulting in a 40km FoV in this dimension and 5 km in the scanning direction. The imaged spatial pixels across the FoV are all combined to provide the required SNR. In the spectral direction, the spectrum is sampled with a 2 nm resolution and 2.5 sampling ratio across the spectrum in line with the requirements. Each of these spectral samples are provided on ground.

The optical bench is made of Aluminium will be the supporting structure for the optical unit. This athermal design would tolerate uniform temperature variations without degradation in performance.

Figure 7.16: Concept 1 A: UV-VIS spectrometer (Credit: OIP).

A two-channel architecture, splitting the Goal spectral range into 240–440 nm and 400–800 nm bands, and a single-channel configuration, covering the Threshold spectral range, 275 nm–775 nm, were considered. Though the two channel solution achieved higher performance, the single-channel concept was shown to be compliant to the most demanding performances required, SNR and Spectral sampling. As a simpler and lower complexity design, the single channel design was therefore selected as the baseline. The single spectrometer solution relies on a single-blazed diffraction grating providing the necessary efficiency to provide the critical SNR at night. Analysis in the Phase 0 showed this could be achieved with a grating of constant groove density of 387 lines/mm at a blaze wavelength of 395 nm and nominal blaze angle of 4.65°. This grating demonstrates compliance to the SNR requirement with the diffraction efficiency shown in Figure 7.16b. The polarization sensitivity of the grating and system is compliant in most of the spectral range, with a non-compliance between the 650–775 nm. This is not considered a critical feature of the design and, furthermore, should be improved in further design iterations.

Three options were considered in the detector trade-off: the CCD42-20 and CIS120-LN from Teledyne-e2V, and the CAE302 "ELOIS" from Caeleste. The CIS120 LN detector is selected as the baseline due to its lower operational complexity, higher robustness to radiation, and better suitability for end-of-life performance (see Section 7.4.1). It also benefits from demonstrated flight heritage through its use in missions such as the Japanese GOSAT-GW satellite and its upcoming application in the CO2M mission.

Design Concept 2: OSIRIS Instrument Based Solution

The Canadian Space Agency instrument named OSIRIS, in particular the Optical Spectrograph component, launched on the Swedish ODIN satellite (ESA Third Party Mission) in 2001, is the inspiration behind the Keystone UV-VIS spectrometer (Llewellyn et al., 2004). As such, a Risk-Retirement Activity to ascertain the likelihood, performance and required development plan to rebuild the OSIRIS Optical Spectrograph, modernised with currently available European and Canadian equipment and suppliers is being initiated. In general, the Keystone requirements tend to be less stringent (Vertical resolution, upper spectral range, spectral resolution) or similar (SNR, lower spectral range) and therefore a concept relying on the OSIRIS heritage is likely to be suited for Keystone, Figure 7.17.

(a) The OSIRIS instrument, flown on the Swedish ODIN satellite in 2001 (Credit: University of Saskatchewan).

Parameter	OSIRIS	Keystone Requirement
Spectral Range	274–810 nm	275–775 nm (T) / 240–800 nm (G)
Vertical Resolution	1 km	5 km (T) / 2.5 km (G)
Spectral Resolution	1 nm < 450 nm < 2 nm > 450 nm	2 nm (T) / 1 nm (G)
Horizontal FoV	40 km	40 km (T) / 10 km (G)

(b) Comparison of OSIRIS instrument performance with Keystone UV-VIS requirements.

Figure 7.17: The OSIRIS Instrument and Performance.

7.3.4. Infrared (IR) Instrument

The IR instrument is implemented as a dedicated limb-viewing radiometer operating in a broad IR spectral range from Mid-Wave IR (MWIR) to Very-Long-Wave IR (VLWIR). It contains 5 spectral channels ranging from 4.2 μm to 15.5 μm , as specified in Table 4.3. The instrument includes its telescope, focal-plane assembly (FPA), electronics and thermal systems. A block diagram of the instrument is provided in Figure 7.18.

Figure 7.18: Keystone IR instrument functional block diagram (Credit: OHB Systems AG).

Instrument Concept

The IR optical system is operated at a passively stabilised temperature of 230 K, while the IR FPA is housed within a cryostat, using an Integrated Detector and Cooling Assembly (IDCA) to maintain actively a temperature of 60 K. This cryogenic environment is supported by a dedicated cryocooler providing the cooling required for detector stability and radiometric performance. This cryogenic subsystem is independent from the THz cooling architecture required for the THz Concept 1 implementation.

Although the IR instrument generally exhibits less stringent radiometric sensitivity requirements than the THz system, it remains subject thermal stability knowledge in the order of 1mK, considered state of the art, to maintain radiometric accuracy performance at low signal levels. The selected fixed-instrument architecture, combined with platform-based scanning, offers a highly stable thermal and mechanical environment that supports these needs.

Focal Plane Assembly (FPA) Subsystem

The most critical feature of the IR design is its Focal Plane Assembly (FPA) and the detector itself. Therefore, this was the main focus of work within Phase 0 activities.

The instrument's heritage inspiration, the SABER instrument, relies on Photoconductive Mercury Cadmium Telluride (PC-MCT) technology. This technology has low heritage and hence there are very few space qualified products in Europe relying on this technology. To mitigate this supply chain risk, two distinct development streams were established, with a fully Photovoltaic MCT (PV-MCT) technology solution, with much deeper heritage in Europe, also explored alongside a European PC-MCT solutions.

- **Concept 1: PV-MCT Concept (Baseline):** This baseline route focuses on adapting and utilizing Photovoltaic (PV-MCT) technology, which is more readily available in Europe. This stream leverages several pre-development activities undertaken for the Earth Explorer 11 CAIRT candidate mission. The primary technical driver at the detector level is the long cut-off wavelength required for the IR2 channel (15.5 μm threshold, 17.2 μm goal). While multiple European suppliers exist for this technology, Leonardo UK (LDO) was selected during Phase 0. Collaboration would expand to include all potential European suppliers during Phase A, facilitating multiple 'baseline-type' solutions.
- **Concept 2: PC-MCT Concept (back-up):** In parallel, a PC-MCT technology route has been initiated to explore an alternative development path. This would be maintained through Phase A as a potential backup solution and engages VIGO PL as a potential supplier. This route offers the advantages of heritage alignment with the SABER instrument, reduced thermal requirements, and a higher operating temperature that simplifies the cryocooler load. However, it would likely require a mechanical chopper to mitigate noise and achieve the target signal-to-noise ratio.

Both concepts utilise dedicated single-element detectors, primarily chosen for their simple layout and low development risk. Because single-element detectors lack the capability for bad-pixel deselection, AXT redundancy is provided by adding a second detector element per spectral band. These redundant pixels feature independent readout electronics and can be operated simultaneously, thereby providing the opportunity to further improve the overall Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) during nominal operations when operated in hot redundancy.

The FPA is split into two distinct regions, with different MCT material to facilitate the large spectral range. IR1 & IR2 are housed together and IR4, IR5 and IR6 are grouped together. The different MCT materials require a separation of 700 μm between each other. The Butcher block filter manufacturing constraints impose a 300 μm separation between the channels that utilise the same MCT material. Every channel is arranged in a single row creating a focal plane of 2600 μm in the AXT direction that translates to 52 km at a tangent height of 100 km, Figure 7.19a. This is the driver for the Keystone horizontal FoV. The single row design removes any vertical separation of the channels that would significantly increase the vertical field of view of Keystone which increases the scan cycle duration and decreases the ALT sampling performance.

Figure 7.19: The IR Focal Plane assembly (a) and optical layout of the telescope (b) (Credit: OHB Systems AG).

The FPA requires cooling in the region of 60–65 K. These temperatures require an active cryocooler to achieve. In order to reduce the risk on achieving the low temperatures and to simplify procurement and design complexity, an IDCA solution is currently selected. This system houses the detectors in a compact assembly including a pulse tube cryocooler. The IDCA concept uses the existing LPT-6510 cryocooler from Absolute Systems.

Telescope Subsystem

The telescope design is fully optimised for the IR instrument concept, utilizing a four-mirror anastigmat configuration with an intermediate image plane and an accessible exit pupil. The intermediate focal plane incorporates a field stop to eliminate stray, out-of-field radiation, alongside the filters required for the instrument’s spectral channels. Furthermore, the telescope’s exit pupil is perfectly matched to the designated cold stop location implemented inside the cryostat with the focal-plane assembly (FPA).

7.4. Performance

7.4.1. Radiometric Performance

THz Instrument

For the THz instrument, the radiometric performance is driven by the system noise temperature and the associated noise-equivalent temperature difference ($NE\Delta T$) of the heterodyne receiver chain. Requirement targets include an absolute radiometric accuracy of 3 K and sensitivities of the order of 10–25 K across the 1.1–2.1 THz range, depending on channel and operating conditions.

End-to-end performance models propagate noise contributions from the receiver front-end, including mixer noise temperature, optical losses and intermediate-frequency chain effects, to the spectrometer output. For representative conditions, with integration times of a few seconds and bandwidths of the order of 200 kHz, $NE\Delta T$ values are typically around 10 K at ~ 1.1 THz and up to 20–25 K at higher frequencies, with compliance depending on receiver temperature and cooling architecture.

The non-compliance observed for Concept 2 at the lower frequency band is assessed as non-critical from a scientific standpoint, as the deviation is at L1 level and is accommodated by the positive retrieval margin available at L2 as shown in 6.10.

Figure 7.20: THz NEDT performance with 0.2 MHz spectral resolution (Credit: P. Martín-Iglesias).

The current performance model remains under development and provides indicative results capturing the dominant contributors, including receiver noise temperature, optical losses, calibration approach and spectral resolution. A preliminary absolute radiometric accuracy (ARA) budget identifies reconstruction uncertainty and receiver-driven terms, such as system noise temperature, gain stability and calibration transfer errors, as the dominant contributors to radiometric performance.

IR Instrument

For the IR instrument, radiometric performance is driven by the required noise-equivalent radiance (NER), absolute radiometric accuracy and long-term stability. The instrument is designed to meet channel-dependent NER requirements typically in the range of 10^{-5} to 10^{-4} W m⁻² sr⁻¹.

Performance is assessed through detailed signal and noise modelling accounting for photon noise, detector dark current, optical background emission and readout noise. The resulting performance is compliant with NER requirements across all spectral channels, as illustrated in Figure 7.21, with margins varying depending on channel and operating conditions.

The absolute radiometric accuracy is specified to be better than 5% (T) and 3% (G), with dominant contributions from calibration blackbody knowledge, thermal background emission and detector non-linearity. The baseline calibration concept, combining orbital cold-space measurements with blackbody measurements every scan, supports long-term radiometric stability better than 2% (T) and 1% (G). Overall, the combination of in-flight calibration and stable thermal design is expected to be compliant with the radiometric performance requirements for atmospheric retrievals.

Figure 7.21: IR NER requirement vs. predicted NER performance for the limiting maximum signal case (Credit: T. Agócs).

Figure 7.22: IR ARA requirement vs. predicted ARA performance including contributors (Credit: T. Agócs).

UV-Vis Instrument

The radiometric performance of the UV–Vis instrument is primarily governed by the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), spectral resolution and radiometric stability over the 240–800 nm range. During daytime conditions, the instrument exceeds the required SNR threshold of 100 with margin. At night, performance is more challenging due to low radiance levels, requiring longer integration times (up to 2 s) and pixel binning to meet the minimum SNR requirement of 50.

A key driver of radiometric performance degradation is the dark current, which becomes particularly critical at low signal levels and increases significantly over the mission lifetime due to radiation effects. For this reason, the UV-Vis detector is cooled at an operational temperature of 273.15 K. Figure 7.23 illustrates the expected End-of-life (EOL) SNR with aluminium shielding and including degradation due to radiation and molecular contamination, estimated as 10%. An additional contributor to radiometric performance is stray light – currently estimated at 5% – which can further degrade SNR. This is expected to be well contained within the current margin to the SNR performance, with additional shielding expected to improve current results. Additionally, thermal margin in the design exists allowing to further cool the design to 263 K which provides additional performance improvement.

Figure 7.23: UV-VIS SNR at night for BOL and EOL at 273.15 K with 5mm (left) and 10mm (right) Al shielding (Credit: OIP).

7.4.2. Spectral Performance

THz Instrument

For the THz instrument, the simulated spectrometer outputs in Figure 7.24 demonstrate the capability to resolve key atmospheric emission lines at high spectral resolution (200 kHz). The results confirm accurate retrieval of both strong and weak lines, including atomic oxygen and CO, which are critical for temperature, composition and wind retrievals. The achieved spectral resolution is consistent with the requirement for precise spectral knowledge of the order of 100 kHz for key species, enabling accurate determination of line centres and supporting wind retrieval through Doppler shift estimation.

IR Instrument

For the IR instrument, the spectral performance is determined by the characteristics of the spectral filters and the resulting Instrument Spectral Response Function (ISRF). The instrument meets channel-dependent spectral requirements, including defined bandwidths and out-of-band rejection on the order of 0.3%. The spectral response is driven by the filter design in the intermediate focal plane, ensuring uniform behaviour across the field of view. The selected concept provides control of bandpass shape and rejection of out-of-band radiation, supporting accurate radiometric measurements and minimising

Figure 7.24: Simulated spectrometer outputs at 200 kHz spectral resolution: (left) atomic oxygen spectral response at 2060 GHz for a tangent altitude of 100 km; (right) CO spectral response at 1151 GHz for a tangent altitude of 80 km (Credit: D. Deibele).

spectral cross-talk. Overall, the analysis indicates compliance with the required ISRF characteristics, ensuring sufficient spectral fidelity for atmospheric retrieval without significant contamination from adjacent spectral regions.

UV-Vis Instrument

For the UV-Visible instrument, the spectral performance is driven by the required spectral resolution and sampling over the spectral range. The instrument achieves a spectral resolution of 2 nm, with a spectral sampling ratio of 2.5 between 275 nm and 775 nm, ensuring compliant sampling of spectral features. The spectrometer provides consistent spectral resolution across the spectral range, enabling accurate retrieval of trace-gas absorption features while maintaining sufficient signal-to-noise ratio.

7.4.3. Calibration Concept

Calibration is interleaved with science observations within the measurement cycle, ensuring negligible impact on scientific data acquisition while maintaining long-term radiometric and spectral stability. A measurement cycle is defined as the acquisition of a vertical profile followed by the return to the initial tangent altitude, including any additional time driven by external constraints for the Keystone instruments, see Figure 7.7. The specific in-orbit calibration approaches implemented for each instrument are described in the following subsections. All instruments will be subject to on-ground calibration and characterisations campaigns.

THz Instrument

For the THz instrument, regular calibration during measurement operations relies on the availability of cold-sky reference conditions within the measurement domain. During each measurement cycle, cold-sky calibration opportunities are exploited along the vertical profile through spectral windows within the instrument spectral range that are free of atmospheric signals—i.e. regions where no atmospheric species exhibits emission lines. In addition, as the concentration of atmospheric species decreases with increasing altitude, emission lines progressively vanish, yielding further calibration windows above specific tangent heights. An on-board calibration is implemented through a flip-mirror system enabling periodic observations of a hot blackbody target (~ 300 K). This calibration is performed at least once per measurement cycle, after completion of each vertical profile, during the return time to the bottom of the subsequent profile. This operational concept ensures a clear temporal separation within each measurement cycle, with cold-sky calibration performed during the vertical scan and on-board calibration accommodated during the return phase. The calibration frequency therefore depends on the operational mode through the corresponding profile duration, as detailed in the next chapter.

IR Instrument

The IR instrument uses a traditional two-point calibration concept, combining orbital-daily cold-space observations with measurements of an internal blackbody reference source during each scan cycle, accessed through a dedicated flip mirror in order to ensure compliance to the radiometric requirements. The cold-sky observations will be accessed by the platform attitude control by extending the observations to higher limb altitudes of around 300 km. Radiometric stability and detector performance are provided by use of the thermal stability knowledge, to 1 mK, configuration supported by the cold-space radiator and active focal-plane cooling down to 60 K, complemented by periodic verification of spectral registration and channel response.

UV-Vis Instrument

The UV-Visible instrument follows a calibration concept distinct from the thermal and THz instruments, combining extensive ground characterisation with in-orbit vicarious radiometric calibration and dark current correction using dark-space pointing. On-ground calibration focuses on validating the telescope, spectrometer, and full system performance, including optical quality, radiometric and spectral response, geometric accuracy, and alignment, followed by thermal-vacuum testing to confirm behaviour under representative conditions.

In flight, the baseline approach for dark current correction combines periodic dark-space observations, with daily-monthly frequency, with accurate detector temperature monitoring of 100 mK to correct for the impact of detector temperature variations. Radiometric calibration is performed through monthly vicarious calibration using targets such as the Moon or suitable Earth scenes, while spectral calibration is assumed stable based on ground characterisation and does not require dedicated onboard systems.

7.4.4. Observation-Mode Performance

The combined geometric and radiometric analyses indicate that the Keystone mission concept satisfies threshold performance requirements across the full altitude range while approaching goal values for several key parameters.

The selected scan strategies provide a balance between vertical sampling, radiometric integration time and horizontal coverage: slower scans prioritise sensitivity and vertical resolution in the upper mesosphere and lower thermosphere, while faster scans improve spatial coverage and revisit. The compliance status for each observation mode, considering the full set of sampling requirements, is summarised in Table 7.6. The compliance assessment is based on the assumptions of a fixed integration time of 2 s per sample for the THz instrument to meet radiometric performance requirements, while the altitude range, vertical sampling and vertical resolution are treated as design inputs; the resulting along-track sampling (ALT) is therefore a derived quantity once these constraints are applied. In addition, realistic platform scanning acceleration profiles are accounted for in the analysis, ensuring that the derived sampling performance reflects physically achievable pointing dynamics.

The Phase 0 analyses confirm the internal consistency of the mission architecture and its compatibility with observation geometry, sampling and radiometric performance requirements.

Pointing, Tangent-Height and Co-registration Performance

End-to-end geometric simulations were performed using line-of-sight reconstruction and sensitivity models representative of the Keystone limb-viewing geometry. The analyses consider the impact of spacecraft position and attitude uncertainties, scan kinematics, thermo-elastic deformation, instrument alignment knowledge and detector geometry on tangent-point geolocation, tangent-height reconstruction and inter-instrument co-registration.

Mode ID	Range [km]	Vertical resolution [km]	Vertical sampling [km]	ALT sampling [km]	Predicted Phase 0
Zoom Vertical	70–110	2.5	1	800	800 km
Zoom Horizontal	70–110	5	2	400 (G) 550 (T)	539 km
Deep	50–150	5 in [50–110] 10 in [110–150]	2 in [50–110] 4 in [110–150]	1000	992 km
Standard Operational	70–250	5 in [70–110] 10 in [110–150] 25 in [150–250]	2 in [70–110] 4 in [110–150] 10 in [150–250]	800 (G) 1250 (T)	1225 km

Table 7.6: Summary of observation modes and corresponding vertical sampling characteristics, together with their compliance status. Platform scan case. (green: compliant, red: non-compliant).

Geometric performance simulations were performed using an analytical model of the Keystone limb-viewing geometry and associated sensitivity analyses. The analysis showed that the dominant error contributors vary depending on the performance requirement, reflecting different sensitivities to spacecraft position, pointing knowledge, instrument alignment, and detector geometry. Absolute tangent-point knowledge is driven by the overall line-of-sight reconstruction chain, including thermoelastic deformation between star trackers and instrument optical modules and residual instrument misalignments. In contrast, tangent-height knowledge and vertical co-registration are primarily driven by pointing knowledge around the scan axis, which constitutes the critical degree of freedom.

The compact payload architecture minimises relative inter-instrument misalignments, with the star trackers moved onto the payload module to decrease further thermoelastic distortions contribution to the absolute pointing budget. Across-line-of-sight co-registration is driven by focal-plane geometry, in particular the separation of the outer IR channels, leading to large horizontal co-registration offsets at low tangent heights.

Sensitivity analyses indicate that tangent-height reconstruction is highly sensitive to pointing knowledge around the scan axis, with a conversion factor of approximately 8–10 m per arcsec of line-of-sight angular error. In other words, a 1 arcsec error in the scan-axis pointing knowledge translates into a ~10 m error in tangent-height determination. In comparison, the sensitivity to spacecraft position uncertainties is significantly smaller and, within the adopted modelling approach, found to be negligible. Geometric performance is therefore primarily driven by alignment knowledge and thermoelastic stability rather than orbit reconstruction accuracy.

Overall, the analyses indicate margins for absolute tangent-point knowledge and along-line-of-sight co-registration, while the most demanding requirements remain tangent-height knowledge below 110 km and across-line-of-sight co-registration driven by scan-axis stability and focal-plane geometry, as summarised in Table 7.7.

Geometric requirement	Required performance	Dominant driver	Predicted Phase 0
Absolute TP knowledge	5 km (G) / 10 km (T)	LOS reconstruction	2.7 km
Absolute TH knowledge	100 m (G) / 400 m (T) below 110 km 400 m above 110 km	Scan-axis pointing	350 m
Vertical co-registration	100 m (G) / 400 m (T) below 110 km 400 m above 110 km	Scan-axis stability	300 m
Along-LOS co-registration	20 km (G) / 200 km (T)	Relative LOS alignment	3.6 km
Across-LOS co-registration	2 km (G) / 55 km (T)	IR focal-plane geometry	54 km

Table 7.7: Summary of geometric performance requirements (green: compliant, red: non-compliant).

8. SYNERGIES AND COMPLEMENTARITIES

Keystone is designed to provide a new global observational capability for the MTS, but its full scientific value would be realised through integration with the wider international observing system. Ground-based instruments provide high-precision local measurements, continuous temporal coverage, and long-term context for independent comparison and validation (where possible), stability assessment and scientific synergy, while current, planned and heritage satellite missions provide complementary measurements of airglow, noctilucent clouds, composition, temperature and dynamics. Importantly, these assets do not duplicate Keystone: rather, they provide the independent reference observations, temporal sampling and historical continuity that can help to interpret Keystone's co-located THz, IR and UV-Vis observations. These synergies directly support the Keystone Science Goals defined in Section 3.2: SG.1 on MTS composition and thermal balance, SG.2 on multi-scale coupling, and SG.3 on whole-atmosphere modelling. This chapter identifies the principal ground-based, satellite and heritage datasets that are complementary to Keystone, and explains how they strengthen the mission's ability to characterise MTS chemistry, dynamics, vertical coupling, and space weather-related variability.

8.1. Synergies with Ground-based Observations

Ground-based observations provide local, high-cadence context for Keystone observations across the mesosphere, lower thermosphere and ionosphere. These instruments sample complementary aspects of the MTS, including neutral temperature and density, winds, airglow, cloud structure, plasma variability and geomagnetic forcing. The main ground-based observing systems relevant to Keystone are summarised in Table 8.1, and selected station locations are shown in Figure 8.1. Their role in independent comparison and validation, where possible, stability assessment, sampling and interpretation is discussed further in Section 8.4.

Lidar Systems

Lidar systems provide some of the highest-vertical-resolution measurements available in the MTS, and therefore form an important component of the ground-based observational context for Keystone. Their vertical resolution, typically better than 1 km, exceeds the expected Keystone vertical resolution of approximately 2.5–10 km, making them particularly valuable for independent comparison and validation, stability assessment and interpretation of fine-scale atmospheric structure. Rayleigh and Rayleigh-Mie-Raman lidars exploit molecular and aerosol backscatter to measure neutral density and temperature profiles, typically over approximately 50–90 km. They also provide information on noctilucent clouds and aerosol layering, making them useful reference measurements for Keystone's infrared and UV-Visible observations of the upper mesosphere. Metal resonance lidars, operating on atomic resonance lines of meteoric metal layers such as Na, Fe, K, Ca, Ca⁺, Ni and Li, extend this capability into approximately 80–110 km. By measuring metal-layer abundance together with Doppler broadening and Doppler shifts, these systems provide high-precision temperature and wind observations, with representative accuracies of order 1 K and a few m s⁻¹ under favourable observing conditions.

Lidar observations are complementary to Keystone in both sampling and measurement capability. Ground-based lidars provide continuous local measurements with very high vertical resolution, while Keystone would provide global vertically resolved observations of winds, temperature and composition across the MTS. Coordinated observations would support independent comparisons with Keystone temperature, wind and constituent retrievals, assessment of vertical smoothing and representativeness errors, and interpretation of small-scale variability associated with gravity waves, tides, metal layers and noctilucent clouds.

Figure 8.1: Selected ground-based instruments in synergy with Keystone: Specular Meteor Radars (SMR), Fabry-Perot Interferometers (FPI), Incoherent Scatter Radars (ISR), airglow imagers, lidars, Mesosphere-Stratosphere-Troposphere Radars (MST) (Credit: C. Stephan).

Radar Networks

Radar systems provide the continuous temporal coverage needed to characterise winds, waves and turbulence in the MTS. They are particularly important for independent comparisons to and interpretation of Keystone Line-of-Sight (LOS) wind products, and their fixed locations complement Keystone's global but temporally discrete sampling (see Section 5.3).

- **Meteor radars (70–110 km):** Meteor radars infer neutral winds by tracking the drift of ionised meteor trails (Hocking et al., 2001). They routinely provide hourly mean horizontal winds and are widely used to characterise tides, planetary waves and gravity wave variability.
- **SuperDARN meteor winds (~95 km):** Although primarily designed for ionospheric plasma convection, SuperDARN radars also detect meteor echoes in their lowest range gates. These observations provide horizontally averaged winds near 95 km, typically integrated over a layer of approximately ± 6 km (Hall et al., 1997). Individual systems can support Keystone LOS wind studies, while the wider network can be used to assess planetary waves (Kleinknecht et al., 2014) and migrating and non-migrating tides (Hibbins et al., 2019).
- **Partial-reflection (MF) radars (60–95 km):** MF radars detect partial reflections from turbulence-induced refractive-index irregularities. By tracking these structures, vector winds can be derived with typical temporal resolutions of order one hour.
- **MST radars and PMSE observations:** Mesosphere-Stratosphere-Troposphere (MST) radars provide vertically resolved observations of atmospheric structure and dynamics. At polar latitudes they are particularly important for observing Polar Mesospheric Summer Echoes (PMSE), which provide context for extremely cold mesopause conditions, ice-particle formation and strong layering.
- **Incoherent scatter radars (80–500 km):** Incoherent scatter radars observe ionospheric plasma parameters, from which neutral winds, temperatures and densities can also be inferred. These observations extend the ground-based context into the thermosphere and ionosphere, supporting comparison with Keystone during geomagnetic disturbances, wave events and atmosphere-ionosphere coupling episodes.

Airglow Imagers and Spectroscopic Observations

Ground-based airglow observations provide complementary information on mesospheric and lower-thermospheric dynamics, temperature and wave structure. These passive optical measurements ob-

Instrument type	Altitude [km]	Primary parameters measured
Rayleigh-Mie-Raman (RMR) lidar	50–90+	Neutral density, temperature, NLC particle properties
Metal resonance lidar	80–110	Temperature, winds, metal density (Na, Fe, K, Ca, Ca ⁺ , Ni, Li)
Meteor radar	70–110	Neutral winds, tides, planetary waves, gravity wave variability
MF radar	60–90	Neutral winds, tidal and planetary waves
MST radar	60–100	Turbulence, PMSE, layering, vertical winds
SuperDARN radar array	~95 meteor; 100–400 ionosphere	Meteor winds, plasma velocity, irregularities, convection
Incoherent scatter radar	80–500+	N_e , T_e , T_i , ion composition and drift
Airglow imager (OH/Na)	~87–90 layer	OH temperature, Na radiance, horizontal wave structure
Airglow imager (O/O ₂)	~95–100 layer	Radiance, temperature, horizontal wave structure
Airglow spectrometer (OH, O, O ₂ , Na)	87–100	Temperature, emission radiance and, in some cases, winds
Magnetometer	–	Geomagnetic current variations, auroral activity
Ionosonde	80–800+	Virtual height and density of E- and F-region ionospheric layers
GNSS receiver (ground-based)	60–1000+	Total electron content, ionospheric irregularities
GNSS (radio occultation)	50–~800	Electron-density profiles, ionospheric irregularities

Table 8.1: Ground-based instrumentation relevant to Keystone.

serve emissions from relatively thin layers, including OH at ~87 km, Na at ~90 km, and O and O₂ emissions in ~95–100 km, making them sensitive to gravity wave perturbations.

Airglow imagers provide the horizontal context on scales not resolved by limb profiles. Brightness variations reveal gravity wave horizontal wavelength, propagation direction and phase speed, while multi-emission observations can give limited information on vertical propagation. OH temperature mappers add continuous thermal context by retrieving temperatures within the hydroxyl layer.

Airglow spectroscopy provides related information on temperature, radiance and, in some cases, winds. High-resolution systems can retrieve winds and temperatures from Doppler shifts and line broadening of atomic oxygen emissions (Kristoffersen et al., 2013), while moderate-resolution systems derive temperatures and band radiances from OH Meinel and O₂ emissions (e.g. Espy and Stegman, 2002). Networks such as the [Network for the Detection of Mesospheric Change \(NDMC\)](#) provide long-term OH temperature and airglow observations from more than 50 stations worldwide.

Magnetometers, Ionosondes and GNSS Receivers

Ground-based observations of geomagnetic and ionospheric variability provide essential context for interpreting Keystone observations during disturbed conditions. Auroral forcing, ionospheric electrodynamics and geomagnetic activity can strongly affect upper atmospheric temperatures, densities, winds and composition, and therefore need to be characterised alongside Keystone observations.

Global magnetometer networks, including the [SuperMAG](#) collaboration (Gjerloev, 2012), provide continuous information on auroral electrojets, geomagnetic disturbances and ionospheric current systems. When combined with SuperDARN observations, these data help identify auroral boundaries, plasma convection patterns and large-scale electrodynamic forcing.

Ionosondes and ground-based GNSS receiver networks and onboard LEO satellites provide complementary information on ionospheric structure, including electron-density profiles, layer heights, critical frequencies, and total electron content. Because Keystone is fundamentally a neutral-atmosphere mission, its unique contribution lies in providing the missing neutral constraints. Consequently, integrating Keystone data with these ground-based plasma datasets would be valuable for identifying TIDs, sporadic E-layer, plasma structuring, and the broader atmosphere-ionosphere coupling processes.

8.2. Synergies with Current and Planned Satellite Missions

MATS

The Mesospheric Airglow/Aerosol Tomography and Spectroscopy (MATS) mission, launched in 2022, uses limb observations of atmospheric airglow and noctilucent clouds (NLCs) to investigate gravity waves, tides and mesospheric cloud structures. Its main relevance to Keystone is its high-horizontal-resolution view of wave morphology, cloud structure and small-scale variability in the mesosphere and lower thermosphere.

MATS and Keystone provide complementary views of the same coupled region. MATS constrains horizontal wave structure and NLC morphology, while Keystone would provide vertically resolved winds, temperature and composition across the MTS. Even if direct temporal overlap is limited, MATS-derived climatologies of wave activity, NLC occurrence and airglow variability would provide useful precursor context for interpreting Keystone observations and evaluating high-resolution atmospheric models. Given the current mission timeline, temporal overlap between MATS and Keystone is very unlikely; MATS should therefore be treated primarily as a heritage mission for mesospheric wave and NLC context, rather than as a likely source of simultaneous correlative observations.

SOVA-S

The Satellite Observation of waVes in the Atmosphere – Scout (SOVA-S) is one of the two recently selected ESA Scout missions (ESA, 2026). SOVA-S will focus on small-scale atmospheric gravity waves and their role in coupling the middle atmosphere, thermosphere and ionosphere. Using a nadir-viewing camera, SOVA-S would image the hydroxyl (OH) Meinel (3,1) Q-branch nightglow column near 1.5 μm at approximately 5 km horizontal resolution. These observations are designed to provide wavelength, orientation and phase-speed information for waves with horizontal wavelengths of approximately 10–250 km. SOVA-S would be optimised for the horizontal structure and intermittency of small-scale gravity waves over approximately 80–120 km. Keystone, by contrast, would provide vertically resolved winds, temperature and composition across the MTS, including direct observations of atomic oxygen. Because SOVA-S observes an integrated OH airglow column, it is primarily sensitive to waves with sufficiently long vertical wavelengths to remain coherent across the emitting layer; Keystone provides the associated altitude structure and background-state information. The currently foreseen launch of SOVA-S is in 2030, with a mission duration of 2 years at threshold and 5 years as a goal. Temporal overlap with the Keystone mission lifetime is therefore uncertain but possible. Even without simultaneous observations, SOVA-S climatologies of small-scale wave occurrence, intermittency and source-region variability would provide important context for interpreting Keystone observations and evaluating high-resolution MTS models.

STRIVE

The Stratosphere Troposphere Response using Infrared Vertically-resolved light Explorer (STRIVE) is a NASA Earth System Explorer mission selected in 2026 for implementation. STRIVE will provide daily, near-global, high-resolution observations of atmospheric temperature, composition, aerosols and clouds from the upper troposphere to the mesosphere. Its two limb-viewing instruments, ALICE and ARGOS, are designed to retrieve vertically resolved profiles of temperature, ozone, trace gases, aerosol and cloud properties, with dense horizontal sampling and vertical resolution on the order of 1 km.

STRIVE and Keystone sample adjacent and dynamically connected regions of the atmosphere. STRIVE focuses on the upper troposphere and stratosphere, including stratosphere-troposphere exchange, ozone chemistry, aerosols and fine-scale wave structure. Keystone focuses on the MTS, including winds, temperature and composition through the mesosphere, lower thermosphere and ionosphere. Together, the

missions would provide observational continuity across a much larger fraction of the atmosphere than either mission alone. A key synergy concerns vertically propagating gravity waves and composition-dynamics coupling. STRIVE constrains wave structure, transport and composition variability in the upper troposphere and stratosphere, while Keystone observes the corresponding thermal, dynamical and compositional response higher in the atmosphere, where wave dissipation and momentum deposition become central. Joint use of the two datasets would strengthen evaluation of whole-atmosphere and space weather models. Assuming nominal schedules, STRIVE and Keystone are likely to have significant temporal overlap, enabling coordinated studies of wave propagation, stratosphere-mesosphere coupling and composition-dynamics interactions.

OMPS and JPSS Observations

Satellite observations of noctilucent clouds (NLCs), also referred to as polar mesospheric clouds (PMCs), during the Keystone mission period are expected from the Ozone Mapping and Profiler Suite (OMPS) instruments aboard the Joint Polar Satellite System (JPSS) satellites, including JPSS-3 and JPSS-4. OMPS includes ultraviolet nadir and limb measurements that can detect NLCs/PMCs near the upper edge of their scan ranges.

OMPS and Keystone provide complementary observational capabilities for studies of NLCs and the polar summer mesopause. OMPS observations provide spatial sampling and continuity within the operational JPSS framework, while Keystone UV-Visible and infrared observations would provide limb-sensitive NLC observations together with co-located temperature, composition and atmospheric-state information. Keystone is also expected to provide additional information on NLC particle properties, which is not provided by OMPS. The two observing systems therefore provide complementary perspectives on NLC variability. Combined analysis of OMPS and Keystone observations would support improved interpretation of NLC occurrence, spatial variability and long-term change, while also helping to connect operational JPSS cloud detections with the broader Keystone MTS science dataset.

ODEM

ODEM (Oxygen Detection in Earth's Meso- and Thermosphere) is a small satellite mission dedicated to measure the global altitude distribution and concentration of atomic oxygen in the mesosphere and thermosphere (100-250 km). The observation concept utilises the spectrally high-resolution measurement of the 2.06 THz emission line of atomic oxygen in limb-view with a heterodyne spectrometer from a small satellite in low Earth orbit. The mission is currently undergoing a Phase 0/Phase A study. The University of Stuttgart with its Institute of Space Systems is responsible for the satellite bus and DLR Institute of Space Research in Berlin is responsible for the THz instrument and data processing. Funding is provided by the German Space Agency. If selected for implementation, ODEM would be launched in 2030 with an operational time of up to three years. ODEM is a precursor mission for the 2-THz instrument on Keystone.

DYNAMIC

DYNAMIC (Dynamical Neutral Atmosphere-Ionosphere Coupling) is a NASA mission designed to study how changes in Earth's lower atmosphere influence its upper atmosphere, where space weather like auroras and satellite disruptions are manifested (see <https://soma.larc.nasa.gov/stp/dynamic/>). The DYNAMIC mission was recommended by the 2013 Decadal Survey for Solar and Space Physics. NASA has selected three proposals for concept studies. One of the proposals is to be selected for realisation in 2026. The DYNAMIC mission is scheduled to start around 2031. It is complementary to Keystone in that it would primarily investigate the dynamic processes of the mesosphere and thermosphere, whereas Keystone would mainly investigate the chemistry.

8.3. Long-term Continuity with Heritage Datasets

Heritage UV-Vis Limb Observations

Previous satellite missions have demonstrated the value of ultraviolet and visible limb observations in the mesosphere and lower thermosphere. Key heritage datasets include WINDII on UARS (Shepherd et al., 1993), OSIRIS on Odin (Llewellyn et al., 2004) and SCIAMACHY on Envisat (Bovensmann et al., 1999). These instruments measured airglow, noctilucent clouds, temperature structure and compositional variability using techniques including grating spectrometry and field-widened interferometry.

These datasets are directly relevant to Keystone because many previous UV-Vis retrievals of atomic oxygen and airglow structure relied on photochemical assumptions that could not be validated globally. Keystone's direct atomic oxygen observations, together with co-located temperature, wind and composition observations, would allow improved evaluation of those retrieval assumptions. Cross-comparison with WINDII, OSIRIS and SCIAMACHY would also support longer-term records of MTS composition, airglow variability, noctilucent clouds and upper atmospheric change.

SABER, MLS and Infrared/Microwave Limb Sounding Heritage

The Sounding of the Atmosphere using Broadband Emission Radiometry (SABER) instrument on NASA's TIMED satellite provides the principal infrared limb-sounding heritage for Keystone. SABER is a 10-channel broadband radiometer covering approximately 1.27–17 μm , with products including kinetic temperature, pressure, geopotential height, O_3 , CO_2 , H_2O , infrared emission rates from NO , OH and O_2 , and derived $[\text{O}]$, $[\text{H}]$, radiative cooling and chemical heating rates (Esplin et al., 2023). This directly supports the photochemistry and atomic oxygen science case discussed in Section 5.3.

SABER is directly relevant because it provides more than two decades of context for MTS temperature, composition, airglow and energetics, while Keystone would provide direct atomic oxygen observations using THz limb sounding. Cross-comparison and harmonisation would place selected Keystone products in a longer-term context and improve interpretation of SABER-derived oxygen, hydrogen and energetics products. The Microwave Limb Sounder (MLS) on NASA's Aura satellite adds complementary microwave limb-sounding heritage, including long-term records of temperature, O_3 , H_2O and CO in the upper stratosphere and mesosphere, widely used for studies of tides, planetary waves and stratosphere–mesosphere coupling.

8.4. Calibration, Stability and Interpretation Support

The scientific value of Keystone depends on the traceability of its mission data quality. Following the principles established in the Quality Assurance Framework for Earth Observation (QA4EO, <https://qa4eo.org>), uncertainty estimates and quality indicators would be established for Keystone data products based on error analyses covering the key uncertainty drivers (see Section 5.1). The role of the wider observing system in this chapter is to identify the external observations that can support calibration monitoring and validation, long-term stability assessment and scientific interpretation of Keystone products. Ground-based networks are particularly important for this purpose because they provide stable, high-cadence and long-duration observations across different observing geometries.

Calibration Monitoring and Long-term Stability Assessment

Keystone's THz, IR and UV-Vis measurements are all sensitive to instrument calibration, pointing and line-of-sight knowledge, radiometric or spectral response, and retrieval assumptions. Well-characterised lidar, radar and spectroscopic datasets would provide independent reference measurements for assessing the stability and consistency of Keystone temperature, wind, composition and airglow products.

Co-located comparisons, defined using parameter-dependent spatial and temporal windows, would allow systematic assessment of biases, altitude registration, representativeness differences and long-term drift, building on comparison and assessment approaches used for missions such as ICON/MIGHTI. (Harding et al., 2021; Englert et al., 2023).

Sampling, Aliasing and Temporal Interpretation

Keystone would provide global limb observations, but a single satellite cannot fully resolve the temporal evolution of tides, planetary waves and other rapidly varying structures. Continuous ground-based radar, lidar and airglow measurements provide the local-time and temporal context needed to distinguish true geophysical variability from sampling effects. Distributed radar networks are particularly useful for separating migrating and non-migrating tidal components and for constraining planetary-wave variability (Zhou et al., 2018). Simultaneous Keystone observations of NLCs, temperature and airglow, interpreted alongside ground-based lidar and PMSE radar measurements, would also support studies of polar summer mesopause microphysics and cloud variability.

Observation-Model Comparison and Forward Modelling

Comparison with models would require explicit treatment of Keystone's sampling, vertical resolution, line-of-sight geometry and retrieval sensitivity. Model fields should therefore be transformed into observation-equivalent quantities using forward operators and realistic sampling before comparison with Keystone products. This is consistent with the retrieval and data-usage framework described in Chapter 5. Ground-based observations provide independent constraints on background state, winds and variability, helping to distinguish model biases from artefacts introduced by observational filtering or incomplete sampling.

8.5. Scientific and Operational Added Value

Keystone adds value by combining co-located, vertically resolved observations of temperature, winds, composition, and airglow in a region where existing observations are fragmented across instruments, platforms and observing geometries. When used with ground-based networks, heritage satellite datasets and future missions, Keystone would provide a reference framework for interpreting MTS variability, testing retrieval assumptions, evaluating whole-atmosphere models and supporting operational applications. This broader observing system gives Keystone value both during the mission and after its lifetime, because traceable Keystone products can be used in later reprocessing, reanalysis and cross-calibration of related atmospheric datasets.

Atmospheric Coupling and Dynamical Variability

Keystone's temperature, wind, composition and airglow products would provide important information on atmospheric coupling and dynamical variability. While its capability to directly observe signatures of gravity waves, tides, and planetary waves is limited by its spatio-temporal sampling, Keystone does observe the consequences of atmospheric wave activity and supplies the broader MTS state in which these processes occur. Keystone data would be exploited in synergy with ground-based radars, lidars and airglow imagers, which supply local temporal context for these processes. The main value is therefore not direct gravity wave characterisation, but improved interpretation of wave-driven variability, mixing and vertical coupling.

Photochemistry and Atomic Oxygen

Atomic oxygen controls much of the chemistry, airglow and radiative balance of the MTS, but global observational constraints acquired thus far are mostly indirect. Keystone's direct atomic oxygen observations, combined with IR and UV-Vis emission observations and heritage datasets from SABER, MLS,

OSIRIS and SCIAMACHY, would allow improved testing of photochemical assumptions used in earlier retrievals. This benefit extends beyond the Keystone mission lifetime: once the relationships between direct atomic oxygen observations, airglow emissions and atmospheric state have been quantified, Keystone can provide a reference for reprocessing and reanalysis of heritage and contemporary datasets that rely on indirect photochemical constraints. Ground-based airglow spectroscopy and lidar observations would provide additional local constraints on temperature, emission variability and atmospheric structure.

Space Weather, Drag and SSA Relevance

Keystone observations of composition, temperature, winds and density-related quantities would improve understanding of the lower thermosphere and its response to geomagnetic forcing. Keystone data would be used to enhance satellite-drag and orbital-decay studies by providing improved constraints on the atmospheric state controlling thermospheric density variability, composition-dependent drag effects and storm-time perturbations. These applications link directly to the thermospheric-density and drag motivation described in Section 2.3, and support wider space situational awareness by improving interpretation of the environment encountered by satellites in very low Earth orbit. Because atomic oxygen is chemically reactive, Keystone's composition observations may also support improved assessment of spacecraft-surface exposure. Magnetometer, ionosonde, GNSS and SuperDARN observations would provide the electrodynamic and ionospheric context needed to interpret Keystone observations during disturbed conditions, including auroral forcing, TIDs and changes in thermospheric structure.

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ACRONYMS

ACEO	Advisory Committee for Earth Observation
ACOM	Atmospheric Chemistry Observations and Modeling
ADC	Analog to Digital Converter
AE	Autumn Equinox
AEJ	Auroral ElectroJet
AGATA	Antarctic Geospace and ATmosphere reseArch
ALT	Along Track
AOCS	Attitude and Orbit Control System
APARC	Atmospheric Processes and their Role in Climate
ARA	Absolute Radiometric Accuracy
AXT	Across Track
BOL	Beginning Of Life
CAIRT	Changing-Atmosphere Infrared Tomography
CEEPS	CAIRT End-to-End Performance Simulator
CESM	Community Earth System Model
CME	Coronal Mass Ejection
CNES	Centre National d'Études Spatiales
CNRS	Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique
COPUOS	United Nations Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space
COSPAR	Committee on Space Research
CRISTA	Cryogenic Infrared Spectrometers and Telescopes for the Atmosphere
CSIC	Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas
DLR	Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt
DTM	Drag Temperature Model
DYNAMIC	Dynamical Neutral Atmosphere-Ionosphere Coupling
ECSS	European Cooperation for Space Standardization
EE	Earth Explorer
EEJ	Equatorial Electrojet
ENSO	El Niño and the Southern Oscillation
EO	Earth Observation
EOGB	Earth Observation Graphic Bureau

EOL End Of Life

EPB Equatorial Plasma Bubble

EQM Engineering Qualification Model

ERS Extended Reference Scenarios

ESA European Space Agency

ESEQ Essential Space Environment Quantity

ESRANGE European Space and Sounding Rocket Range research centre and rocket launch site

ETM Empirical Tidal Modes

ETON Energy Transfer in the Oxygen Nightglow

EUV Extreme Ultraviolet

FAC Field-Aligned Current

FFT Fast Fourier Transform

FIRS Far-InfraRed Spectrometer

FM Flight Model

FoV Field of View

FPA Focal Plane Assembly

FPI Fabry-Perot Interferometers

FWHM Full Width at Half Maximum

GAW Global Atmosphere Watch

GDEX Geoscience Data Exchange

GM Geometry Module

GNSS Global Navigation Satellite System

GRANADA Generic RAdiative transfer AnD non-LTE population Algorithm

GREAT German Receiver for Astronomy at Terahertz Frequencies

GSOOS Generic Simulator of Earth Observation Optical Sensors

HF High Frequency

HRDI High Resolution Doppler Imager

HWM Horizontal Wind Model

IAGA International Association of Geomagnetism and Aeronomy

IAMAS International Association of Meteorology and Atmospheric Sciences

ICMA International Commission on the Middle Atmosphere

ICON ICOSahedral Nonhydrostatic modelling framework

ICSW Interdivisional Commission on Space Weather

IDCA Integrated Detector and Cooling Assembly
INGV Istituto Nazionale di Geofisica e Vulcanologia
IPCC Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
IR Infrared
ISC International Science Council
ISP Instrument Support Panel
ISR Incoherent Scatter Radars
ISRF Instrument Spectral Response Function
ISWAT International Space Weather Action Teams
ISWI International Space Weather Initiative
ITU International Telecommunication Union
IUGG International Union of Geodesy and Geophysics
JAWARA Japanese Atmospheric General circulation model for the Upper Atmosphere Research
JUICE Jupiter Icy Moons Explorer
KEEPS Keystone End-to-End Performance Simulator
KOPRA Karlsruhe Optimized and Precise Radiative Transfer Algorithm
L1 Level 1
L2 Level 2
LEO Low Earth Orbit
LER Limb Emission Rate
LO Local Oscillator
LOS Line of Sight
LTAN Local Time at Ascending Node
LTE Local Thermodynamic Equilibrium
MAG Mission Advisory Group
MATS Mesospheric Airglow/Aerosol Tomography and Spectroscopy
MCT Mercury Cadmium Telluride (detector)
MIGHTI Michelson Interferometer for Global High-resolution Thermospheric Imaging
MIPAS Michelson Interferometer for Passive Atmospheric Sounding
MJO Madden–Julian Oscillation
MLS Microwave Limb Sounder
MLT Mesosphere and Lower Thermosphere
MO Mission Objective

MSIS Mass Spectrometer and Incoherent Scatter radar reference atmospheric model

MSISE Mass Spectrometer and Incoherent Scatter radar reference atmospheric model - Extended

MST Mesosphere-Stratosphere-Troposphere

MSX Midcourse Space eXperiment

MTS Mesosphere–Thermosphere System

NCAR National Center for Atmospheric Research

ND Number Density

NDACC Network for the Detection of Atmospheric Composition Change

NDMC Network for Detection of Mesosphere Change

NEDT Noise Equivalent Delta Temperature

NER Noise Equivalent Radiance

NLC Noctilucent Cloud

NLTE Non-Local Thermodynamic Equilibrium

NRL Naval Research Laboratory

NRLMSIS Naval Research Lab MSIS

NTNU Norwegian University of Science and Technology

ODEM Oxygen Detection in Earth’s Meso- and Thermosphere

OMPS Ozone Mapping and Profiler Suite

OSAS-B Oxygen Spectrometer for Atmospheric Science on a Balloon

OSIRIS Optical Spectrograph and InfraRed Imager System

PAM Performance Assessment Module

PC-MCT PhotoConductive Mercury Cadmium Telluride (detector)

PL Payload

PMC Polar Mesospheric Clouds

PMSE Polar Mesospheric Summer Echoes

PSD Particle Size Distribution

PV-MCT PhotoVoltaic Mercury Cadmium Telluride (detector)

PW Planetary Waves

Q2DW Quasi-two-Day Wave

QA4EO Quality Assurance Framework for Earth Observation

QBO Quasi-Biennial Oscillation

QCL Quantum Cascade Laser

QM Qualification Model

QON Quasi-Optical Network

R2O Research to Operations

RAL Rutherford Appleton Laboratory

RF Radio Frequency

RFM Reference Forward Model

RMR Rayleigh-Mie-Raman

RTM Radiative Transfer Model

SABER Sounding of the Atmosphere using Broadband Emission Radiometry instrument

SCAR Scientific Committee on Antarctic Research

SCIAMACHY Scanning Imaging Absorption SpectroMeter for Atmospheric CHartography

SCOSTEP Scientific COmmittee on Solar-TErrestrial Physics

SE Spring Equinox

SG Science Goal

SGM Scene Generator Module

SM Structural Model

SMR Specular Meteor Radars

SNR Signal-to-Noise Ratio

SOFIA Stratospheric Observatory for Infrared Astronomy

SOVA-S Satellite Observation of waVes in the Atmosphere – Scout

SPIRIT Spatial Infrared Imaging Telescope

SRL Scientific Readiness Level

SS Summer Solstice

SSA Space Situational Awareness

SSO Sun-Synchronous Orbit

SSW Sudden Stratospheric Warming

STM Structural Thermal Model

STRIVE Stratosphere Troposphere Response using Infrared Vertically-resolved light Explorer

SWI Submillimetre Wave Instrument

TH Tangent Height

THz Terahertz

TID Travelling Ionospheric Disturbance

TIDI TIMED Doppler Interferometer

TIE-GCM Thermosphere–Ionosphere Electrodynamics General Circulation Model

TIMED Thermosphere-Ionosphere-Mesosphere Energetics and Dynamics
TP Tangent Point
TRL Technology Readiness Level
TT&C Telemetry, Tracking and Command
TV BALLET Thz Visible BALLoonExperiment
UA-ICON Upper-Atmosphere ICOSahedral Nonhydrostatic modelling framework
UARS Upper Atmosphere Research Satellite
UV UltraViolet
VER Volume Emission Rate
Vis Visible
VLEO Very Low Earth Orbit
VMR Volume Mixing Ratio
WACCM Whole Atmosphere Community Climate Model
WACCM-X Whole Atmosphere Community Climate Model eXtended
WCRP World Climate Research Programme
WINDII Wind Imaging Interferometer
WMO World Meteorological Organization
WS Winter Solstice

A. SCIENCE READINESS ASSESSMENT

This Appendix presents the scientific maturity of the Keystone mission at the end of Phase 0. It evaluates the science maturity within ESA EOP's Scientific Readiness Level (SRL) framework (ESA, 2025b), as a self-assessment compiled by the ESA Mission Scientist based on inputs from the Mission Advisory Group (MAG), by responding to the guiding questions and providing the evidence required.

A.1. SRL 4 Guiding Questions

Translation of Science Goals to Mission Objectives and Requirements

Question: Are the science goal(s) translated into mission objectives, mission requirements and system requirements in a fully traceable way?

Answer: The Keystone Science Goals are presented in Section 3.2 and their translation into Keystone Mission Objectives is presented in Section 3.5. The mission requirements are illustrated in Chapter 4, where Mission Objectives are mapped on specific observation requirements (Section 4.1) and the latter are traced to measurement requirements (Section 4.4). The Keystone mission concept was then formulated to implement these requirements, and it is discussed in detail in Chapter 7.

Conclusion: Science Goals have been traced down to Mission Objectives and requirements and used to formulate a mission concept. SLR 4 has been reached.

Model linking geophysical scenarios to measurement data

Question: Is a model (software package) available that allows the computation of measurement data based on geophysical input data?

Answer: Yes, radiative transfer models are available to the Keystone team, which allow simulating the measurements (at Level 1) for each of the three instruments for given specific geophysical scenarios. The geophysical scenarios are drawn from output of the high-resolution, whole-atmosphere, general-circulation models WACCM-X (Section 6.1), with fully coupled chemistry and dynamics provided by the University of Leeds, and UA-ICON in a setup without interactive chemistry (Borchert et al., 2019) provided by IAP Khlungsborn. Then, orbits are extracted based on geolocation data provided by University of Bath to obtain atmospheric profiles at the geolocations (latitude, longitude, and tangent point altitude), representative of any given scenario of orbit and scan sequence. Based on WACCM-X atmospheric profiles, radiative transfer models are used to simulate the measurement that Keystone's instruments would see from that given orbit and viewing geometry. For the THz spectral range, the radiative transfer simulations follow the methodology described in Hansen et al. (2025) (Section 6.2.1). For the IR domain, the radiative transfer model used is the Reference Forward Model (RFM) (Dudhia, 2017), fed with NLTE-level populations calculated with GRANADA (Funke et al., 2012) (Section 6.2.2). For the UV-Vis range, the SCIATRAN (Mei et al., 2023) model is used (Section 6.2.3). Furthermore, retrieval schemes for key THz species (O, O₂, H₂O and temperature), as well as for O from the UV-Vis instrument are available to the Keystone team.

Conclusion: Models are available that allow the computation of measurement data based on geophysical input data for all three Keystone instruments. SRL 4 has been reached.

Technical and scientific review of the model

Question: Is the model technically and scientifically adequate and has it been independently reviewed?

Answer: Yes, the atmospheric models used (WACCM-X, UA-ICON, MSIS, DTM) have been extensively validated and are widely used. The RFM radiative transfer model (Dudhia, 2017) has been widely used by the community and validated against other radiative models such as KOPRA under NLTE assumptions (von Clarmann et al., 2002). The GRANADA NLTE algorithm (Funke et al., 2012) used for IR assess-

ments has been extensively applied to SABER data analysis; it is part of IMK–IAA scientific processor for MIPAS retrievals, and has been validated through comparisons with other NLTE models, including that used in SABER operational retrievals (Feofilov et al., 2009). The SCIATRAN model (Mei et al., 2023) used for UV-Vis assessments is publicly available and has been developed and extensively used for SCIAMACHY. The simulation and retrieval scheme used for the THz assessment has been developed at DLR and published in the peer-reviewed literature (Hansen et al., 2025). The excellent match of THz radiative transfer simulations with real atmospheric spectra from a balloon campaign is taken as a verification. It has also been verified by comparison with an optimal estimation retrieval scheme for THz species developed at RAL (Gerber et al., 2018).

Conclusion: All models used are published, and most are very well established. SLR 4 has been reached.

Sensitivity of the measurement data to geophysical parameter

Question: Has the sensitivity of the measurement data to the targeted geophysical parameter been demonstrated based on representative measurement data (e.g. campaign data) or in any other way?

Answer: The sensitivity of the measurements to geophysical parameters is presented in Chapter 6. The scenarios considered capture the variabilities of the atmosphere targeted by Keystone SGs (Section 3.2). The scenarios describe the spatial and temporal distributions of the Keystone observables, including trace gases abundances, temperature, and line-of-sight winds. The scenarios under test include the natural atmospheric variability (diurnal, seasonal, and latitudinal), as well as varying solar activity and a strong solar storm. Radiative transfer calculations have been performed for each of the three payloads for these geophysical scenarios to determine the response at Level 1 at each limb altitude, as well as the measurement sensitivity to relevant changes in the atmosphere. In addition, the Level 2 performance has been assessed for key products including, O, O₂, H₂O, temperature and along-track wind (Section 6.2.1).

For O specifically, a measurement campaign employing a stratospheric balloon has been conducted (Section 6.3.2). The THz measurements acquired in this campaign are fully consistent with the radiative transfer simulations. The capability of IR and UV-Vis measurements to retrieve the targeted geophysical parameters has been demonstrated in previous missions, including SABER/TIMED, OSIRIS/Odin, and SCIAMACHY/Envisat, which have successfully delivered L2 products and provide a strong heritage for the Keystone IR and UV-Vis instruments. (e.g. Remsberg et al. (2008); Rezac et al. (2015); Llewellyn et al. (2004); Bovensmann et al. (1999)).

Conclusion: The measurement response to the geophysical processes has been simulated; the tracing from L2 to L1 uncertainty requirements as described in Chapter 4 has been consolidated. The capability of the IR and UV-Vis measurement concept is further supported by extensive heritage from previous satellite missions. For the novel observation of atomic oxygen, a stratospheric balloon campaign (Section 6.3.2) has proven the validity of radiative transfer simulations performed. SRL 4 has been reached.

Information content analysis

Question: Has an information content analysis been performed and have the geophysical parameters contributing to the measurement data been identified?

Answer: The information content of the spectral measurements of the three Keystone payloads with respect to the observables has been demonstrated for all foreseen data products (see Chapters 4 and 6 for detailed information). In many cases, for example THz, full retrieval schemes were developed and tested as part of the study for this proposal. For some data products, the information content has been demonstrated in heritage missions, with SABER/TIMED being the heritage mission for Keystone's IR payload and both SCIAMACHY/Envisat and OSIRIS/Odin the heritage missions for the UV-Vis payload of Keystone. Since Keystone's UV-Vis instrument has a higher SNR compared to SCIAMACHY and OSIRIS

and otherwise very similar L1 requirements, Keystone would retrieve the data products retrievable from those two missions and likely extract even weaker emissions. For the IR, possible changes to the long wave edge of IR2 (15 μm) for temperature retrievals and pressure registration are described in (6.2.2), showing no loss in capability compared with SABER/TIMED. A more comprehensive and quantitative evaluation of the measurements' information content including the determination of the averaging kernel matrix and the number of degrees of freedom would be carried out for each data product in Phase A. Conclusion: Information content has been established either heuristically or based on heritage instruments with similar sensitivity. SRL 4 has been reached.

Scientific risk analysis

Question: Has a scientific risk analysis been performed?

Answer: The main scientific risks have been identified and adequate mitigation measures have been found. While 2.5 THz limb sounding of atmospheric species has been performed on MLS (Wu et al., 2008), the synergy between THz and UV-Vis observations has not yet been explored. There is a risk that performance issues interfere with the scientific use. To mitigate this risk, a balloon campaign dedicated to Keystone is planned for summer 2026. The balloon payload allows co-located measurements of the mesosphere in the THz and the UV-Vis. The campaign data would be used for testing retrievals and consistency of observables across the spectral domains, in Phase A.

The observation of atomic oxygen using the THz is new. There is a risk that performance of L2 products based on THz measurements are not as good as anticipated due to retrieval problems. To mitigate this risk, retrieval schemes for THz observables have already been developed and retrieval experiments have been conducted in Phase 0, going beyond the mandatory top-down sensitivity analysis.

For the development of the IR and UV-Vis L2 retrieval schemes, it is envisaged to build on heritage from past IR and UV-Vis missions. The relevant experts and tools need to be brought in the Phase A activities. There is a risk that these experts are unavailable in the relevant time frame. To mitigate this risk, broad collaborations with several relevant retrieval groups have been established already during Phase 0. For the IR retrievals, this includes groups with extensive experience in NLTE retrievals with MIPAS and SABER at the Instituto de Astrofísica de Andalucía (IAA-CSIC) and the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT), and MIPAS LTE retrievals at Oxford University. For the UV-Vis retrievals, this includes groups at the University of Greifswald, Stockholm University, and the University of Saskatchewan (working on the UV-Vis retrievals with OSIRIS and SCIAMACHY). Corresponding retrieval studies have been an integral part of instrument modelling and sensitivity studies already during the Keystone Phase 0.

Conclusion: An analysis of the scientific risks has been performed. The main risks have been identified and adequate mitigation measures have been found. SRL 4 has been reached.

Demonstration data set of measurement data

Question: Has a demonstration data set of measurement data been produced?

Answer: Yes, synthetic measurements in the form of atmospheric limb-spectra have been produced for all the three payloads, THz, IR, and UV-Vis. The measurements cover different atmospheric conditions (geophysical scenarios) and the nominal scan range. Radiometric noise in these measurement have been taken into account. Real measurements at 2 THz and 4.7 THz have been taken during a balloon campaign from Timmins (CA) in August 2025. These spectra clearly show the strong spectral lines of atomic oxygen at both frequencies and perfectly match dedicated radiative transfer model simulations.

Conclusion: The novel measurements of Keystone (direct observation of atomic oxygen from limb-viewing THz measurements) have been demonstrated using synthetic data and sensitivity assessments as well as based on real data from a dedicated balloon campaign for Keystone. SRL 4 has been reached.

Complementary and/or alternative missions

Question: Has the mission concept been discussed with respect to complementary and / or alternative missions?

Answer: Complementary observations and/or alternative missions to Keystone are discussed in Chapter 8. The Keystone team is not aware of any other mission that measures atomic oxygen and studies its role in the MTS. The NASA candidate mission DYNAMICS (briefly introduced in Section 8.2, currently in evaluation) is a mission in preparation and it would have a 2 THz receiver to measure atomic oxygen, but the measurements focus on winds and dynamical phenomena, not chemistry and composition as Keystone aims to do. The best complementary measurements of Keystone would come from ground-based observations. Ground-based upper atmospheric measurements from radar or lidar, together with Keystone, would strengthen its science and expand it towards the study of atmospheric tides. In Chapter 8, a suite of ground-based observations with an altitude coverage of 50 km to 200 km and above has been identified. These include Rayleigh-Mie-Raman (RMR) Lidars, Metal Resonance Lidars, Meteor Radars, MST Radars, MF Radars, Airglow Imagers, Incoherent Scatter Radars, and Ionosondes. Chapter 8 also discusses long-term continuity with heritage datasets.

Conclusion: Keystone is unique in providing first global measurements of atomic oxygen and related species in the MTS. The strongest candidate for complementary measurements is from ground-based networks of radars and lidars and they are discussed in the report. SRL 4 has been reached.

A.2. Roadmap to SRL 5

A short roadmap has been established, outlining the main activities required to ensure that the Keystone mission achieves Scientific Readiness Level 5 by the end of Phase A.

The planned activities include the maturation of retrieval methodologies, with a clear and consistent tracing from L1 performances to mission performance at L2. This involves further refinement and validation of existing approaches, alongside the adoption and adaptation of heritage techniques where appropriate, supported by close collaboration with established expert groups in the retrieval communities. It would also include the consolidation of the vertical scanning capability considering technical feasibility and scientific need. The strategy for optimising vertical range and sampling, along-track sampling, and radiometric performance would be further consolidated.

The development of an end-to-end simulator (KEEPS, briefly outlined in Section A.3) is foreseen. KEEPS would integrate scenes generation, instruments modelling and data processing chains, in order to allow a quantitative assessment of the mission performances.

Further work would focus on expanding and consolidating the portfolio of geophysical product retrievals, ensuring robustness across the different spectral domains and measurement techniques (THz, IR and UV-Vis). This would include the validation of retrieval performance through the use of high-resolution model data and dedicated simulation studies, enabling direct comparison between retrieved and reference geophysical parameters. Multiple models with interactive dynamics-chemistry coupling are available for the generation of geophysical scenarios, including WACCM-X and UA-ICON.

Results from campaign activities (e.g. TV-BALLET briefly outlined in Section 6.3.2) would support the experimental test of the retrievals and consistency of observables across the THz and UV-Vis spectral domains.

A.3. End-to-End Performance Simulator

The Keystone End-to-End Performance Simulator (KEEPS) is under development by GMV Aerospace and Defence SAU within an ESA contract. It benefits from high readiness and reduced technical risk through targeted reuse of the developed and validated CAIRT End-to-End Performance Simulator (CEEPS), also developed by GMV (ESA, 2025a). The Geometry Module (GM) and Scene Generator Module (SGM)

are inherited from CEEPS and can be reused across all three instrument chains with limited adaptations such as forward and AXT limb pointing specifics and extension of the scene vertical range. The CEEPS SGM provides orbit following 3-D grids, fast interpolation/merging of model and climatological inputs, hydrostatic adjustments, and photochemical corrections (including auxiliary quantities required for handling non-LTE), offering a validated basis for KEEPS scene generation. The strongest reuse applies to the mid infrared (mid IR) chain, where CEEPS already provides a mature baseline for IR forward modelling using KOPRA/GRANADA (Stiller et al. (2000); Funke et al. (2012)), including non-LTE capabilities. For the UV-VIS chain, KEEPS would also reuse heritage software, building on SASKTRAN (Bourassa et al. (2008), Zawada et al. (2015)) for the forward model and `skretrieval`¹ for the retrieval. For the THZ chain, KEEPS would implement an adaptation of the end-to-end framework documented in Hansen et al. (2025). For the Instrument Simulation (ISM) and Level 1 Processing Module (L1M), reuse is necessarily selective because the CAIRT payload was a Fourier Transform Spectrometer. Nevertheless, KEEPS would inherit applicable limb adapted simulation elements from CEEPS where feasible and complement them with GMV’s Generic Simulator of Earth Observation Optical Sensors (GSOOS) heritage, a generic tool for the simulation of optical instruments (UV-VIS and IR) and L1 processing. A common Performance Assessment Module (PAM), shown in Figure A.1 is provided, as a GMV generic framework, used in previous activities and whose core functionalities have been verified.

Figure A.1: Keystone End-to-End Performance Simulator (KEEPS) flowchart illustrating the Performance Assessment Module (PAM) (Credits: GMV, A.A. Martin-Canca).

¹<https://github.com/usask-arg/skretrieval> (Accessed 12 June 2026).

B. RELEVANCE TO EVALUATION CRITERIA

This appendix refers to the evaluation criteria for the Earth Explorer 12 mission assessment that have been agreed with the ESA member states and documented at Programme Board for Earth Observation (PB-EO) level.

Sections B.1, B.2, B.3, and B.5 provide the summary of the Keystone MAG's assessment of the Keystone mission with respect to the Evaluation Criteria 1-3 and 5. In Sections B.4 and B.5, the mission feasibility, maturity and programmatics are assessed by the Agency.

B.1. Criterion 1 - Relevance to the ESA EO Science Strategy

Keystone is an Earth Explorer 12 candidate mission designed to explore the Mesosphere-Thermosphere System (MTS) through measurements of composition, temperature, and winds. It would deliver the first direct global observations of atomic oxygen across the MTS, and it aims to resolve key processes governing atmospheric coupling, energy balance, and variability (Chapters 2 and 3). Section 3.3 establishes the traceability of Keystone to ESA's EO Science Strategy (ESA (2024)), mapping Overarching Science Themes, Science Questions, and Areas of Action to the mission Science Goals (Section 3.2). Keystone adopts a holistic Earth system perspective, addressing the MTS as a key component of atmospheric coupling processes (Chapter 2). The Science Goals are linked to four Overarching Science Themes: ST-II, ST-III, ST-V, and ST-VI, and to key Science Questions (SQ51, SQ45, SQ46), through the investigation of composition, energetics, and variability in the MTS. These are further connected to ESA Areas of Action, notably A1 (frontier science), A2 (societal benefits), and A4 (observational gaps), supported by the mission's requirements and observational concept (Chapters 4 and 7). This ensures clear traceability from ESA priorities to Keystone Science Goals and their implementation. In addition, the evolution of science goals and mission objectives with respect to the EE12 proposal is outlined in Section 3.6.

B.2. Criterion 2 - Scientific Merit, Uniqueness, Impact and Value

Clear formulation of science goals

The scientific motivation underpinning Keystone is translated into three clearly formulated Science Goals (Section 3.2). SG.1 ('MTS Characterisation') aims to characterise the composition, composition, density, chemistry, and thermal balance of the Mesosphere–Thermosphere System (MTS) through global observations of atomic oxygen, together with key trace gases, radiative cooling processes, and airglow emissions. SG.2 ('Multi-Scale Coupling') aims to characterise and quantify coupling processes acting across spatial and temporal scales within the MTS, including atmospheric waves, inter-hemispheric transport, and the response to solar and geomagnetic forcing. SG.3 ('Whole-Atmosphere Modelling') aims to improve the representation and prediction of the coupled chemistry–climate system in next-generation whole-atmosphere models, with applications to space weather, climate forcing, and satellite drag forecasting.

Review of the current state of scientific understanding

Chapter 2 outlines the current understanding of the Mesosphere–Thermosphere System (MTS) as a key region controlling the exchange of energy, momentum, and composition between the lower atmosphere and near-Earth space. It is well established that MTS processes are driven by the combined influence of internal dynamics and external forcing, including atmospheric waves, tides, and solar–geomagnetic activity (Section 2.1). A central element of this understanding is the role of atomic oxygen as the dominant constituent governing MTS chemistry and energetics, acting as the primary reservoir of chemical potential energy and controlling heating and cooling processes (Section 2.2).

Identification of critical knowledge gap

Critical knowledge gaps are identified in Chapter 2, arising from the current understanding of the Mesosphere–Thermosphere System (MTS), building on the review of its composition, energetics, and variability (Section 2.1). While the dominant role of atomic oxygen in controlling MTS chemistry and energy balance is well established, the absence of direct, global observations prevents the closure of energy and chemical budgets and limits quantitative validation of models (Sections 2.1-2.2). Further gaps are identified in the characterisation of multi-scale coupling processes and their interaction with solar and geomagnetic forcing (Sections 2.1-2.2), as well as in the representation of space weather impacts and satellite drag processes (Section 2.3). In addition, the limited capability to quantify long-term variability and climate-related trends reflects fundamental constraints in both observations and modelling. These interconnected gaps, clearly highlighted in the discussion of process-level uncertainties (Section 2.4), define the primary scientific drivers for the Keystone mission.

Advancement beyond the current state of the art

The scientific motivation for Keystone arises from the central role of the Mesosphere–Thermosphere System (MTS) as the dynamic interface between the lower atmosphere and near-Earth space, combined with the current limitations in its observational characterisation (Chapter 2). Although key processes governing MTS physics, chemistry, and variability are qualitatively understood, existing observations remain fragmented in altitude, sampling, and sensitivity, preventing a consistent and quantitative description of the system. In particular, the lack of direct, global measurements of key variables, most notably atomic oxygen, limits the ability to constrain energy balance, composition, and coupling processes. Building on this motivated scientific gap, Keystone aims to provide a step change in understanding by enabling comprehensive, co-located observations of MTS state variables, thereby addressing the fundamental processes driving variability and improving whole-atmosphere modelling capabilities. The advancement in scientific knowledge in relation to the current state of the art is presented in Section 3.1.

Urgency and Timeliness

The urgency and timeliness of the Keystone mission arise from the combination of unresolved scientific limitations and rapidly evolving societal needs. As outlined in the scientific motivation (Section 3.1), the Mesosphere–Thermosphere System (MTS) remains insufficiently characterised due to fragmented observations and the lack of direct measurements of key variables, limiting predictive capability for space weather, climate processes, and satellite drag. At the same time, the increasing reliance on space-based infrastructure and the rapid growth of satellite constellations amplify the need for accurate, physically based understanding of the upper atmosphere. The data usage perspective (Section 5.3) further reinforces this urgency by highlighting the immediate applicability of Keystone observations to operational domains, including orbit prediction, re-entry modelling, and communication system resilience. Taken together, these aspects demonstrate that Keystone addresses a critical and time-sensitive gap, where improved observations are required both to advance fundamental science and to support emerging operational demands.

Clear formulation of mission objectives

Section 3.4 presents a set of clearly formulated and traceable Mission Objectives that translate the Science Goals defined in Section 3.2 into specific observational targets and measurable requirements. Each Mission Objective is explicitly linked to one or more Science Goals and is expressed in terms of quantifiable parameters within the Mesosphere–Thermosphere System (MTS), including composition, temperature, winds, and density. In particular, MO.1 and MO.2 address the characterisation of MTS composition and energetics, MO.3 targets the determination of thermal structure and variability, and MO.4 focuses on dynamical processes such as winds and coupling. Together, these objectives define

the observational scope required to characterise the MTS, resolve multi-scale coupling processes, and support whole-atmosphere modelling. This structured formulation ensures consistency between the scientific motivation (Section 3.1), the identified knowledge gaps (Chapter 2), and the measurement requirements and data products defined in Chapters 4 and 5.

Traceability of mission objectives to science goals and review of relevant observations

Section 3.5 demonstrates the clear and systematic tracing of the Science Goals (Section 3.2) to the corresponding Mission Objectives (Section 3.4), ensuring a consistent and transparent translation from scientific motivation to observational requirements. Each Science Goal is mapped to specific Mission Objectives (MO.1-MO.4), establishing a direct linkage between the targeted physical processes, such as MTS composition, energetics, coupling, and dynamics, and the defined geophysical products. This structured traceability ensures that the Mission Objectives fully capture the scope of the Science Goals while providing a coherent framework for deriving measurement requirements and data products (Chapters 4 and 5).

Review of current state of observations relevant to the science goals

The current state of observations relevant to the Keystone Science Goals is characterised by a combination of heritage measurements and significant observational limitations (presented in Chapters 2 and 8). Existing observations from satellite missions, ground-based instruments, and rocket soundings have provided important insights into MTS composition, temperature, and dynamics, establishing the qualitative understanding of key processes such as radiative–chemical interactions and atmospheric coupling. However, these measurements remain fragmented in altitude, spatial coverage, and temporal sampling, and rely largely on indirect retrievals for critical parameters such as atomic oxygen. As a result, they are insufficient to provide a consistent, co-located, and vertically resolved description of the Mesosphere–Thermosphere System (MTS), limiting the ability to fully address the Science Goals related to MTS characterisation, multi-scale coupling, and whole-atmosphere modelling (Section 3.2). This observational gap limits the validation of models and the quantification of variability and coupling processes, motivating the need for a comprehensive and integrated measurement approach as proposed by Keystone.

Identification of critical observational gaps

The review of current observations highlights key gaps that limit the quantitative understanding of the Mesosphere–Thermosphere System (MTS). Building on the assessment of observational capabilities (Chapter 2) and their relevance to the Science Goals (Section 3.2), existing measurements are fragmented in coverage and rarely co-located. In particular, the lack of direct, global observations of atomic oxygen, the dominant species controlling MTS chemistry and energetics (Section 2.2), prevents closure of energy and chemical budgets. Additional limitations arise in the characterisation of multi-scale coupling processes (Section 2.2) and space weather and satellite drag impacts (Section 2.3), as well as in the simultaneous observation of key state variables required to meet the Mission Objectives (Section 3.4). These deficiencies, summarised in the discussion of process-level uncertainties (Section 2.4), define the critical observational gaps addressed by the Keystone mission.

Impact of the proposed contribution and existence of alternatives

The Keystone mission provides a step change in capability by delivering global, co-located observations of key Mesosphere–Thermosphere System (MTS) variables required to meet the Science Goals (Section 3.2) and Mission Objectives (Section 3.4), including the direct measurement of atomic oxygen (Sections 2.2 and 3.1), which enables closure of energy and chemical budgets. Existing observational systems remain fragmented and largely indirect (Chapter 2), and are therefore insufficient to meet the combined Mission Objectives. While complementary measurements provide important context, syner-

gies and potential scientific opportunities (Section 5.3), no current or planned missions offer the integrated observational approach required. Keystone is therefore uniquely positioned to address these objectives and support the scientific understanding of the MTS.

Complementarities with existing and planned systems

Complementarities with existing and planned systems are a central aspect of the Keystone mission concept, as detailed in Chapter 8. Keystone enhances the overall observing system by providing co-located and vertically resolved measurements that complement the partial coverage and indirect retrievals of current observations (Chapter 2). Through its integrated measurement approach, the mission supports the achievement of the Science Goals (Section 3.2) and Mission Objectives (Section 3.4) in synergy with other space- and ground-based systems. In particular, Keystone strengthens interoperability across observing assets (Chapter 8) by providing a consistent reference for key variables such as atomic oxygen (MO.1), enabling improved cross-calibration, data assimilation, and interpretation. From a data usage perspective (Section 5.3), it contributes to a coordinated multi-mission framework, where its observations complement and extend existing datasets rather than duplicating them.

Consolidation of the mission concept with respect to the original science goals

The Keystone mission concept has been progressively consolidated to ensure consistency with the Science Goals defined in Section 3.2 and their evolution (Section 3.6). This process has led to a clearer alignment between the scientific objectives and the observational concept, with an increased focus on key drivers such as atomic oxygen, MTS composition, and multi-scale coupling processes. The mission architecture and measurement strategy have been refined accordingly, ensuring that each Science Goal is supported by the required observables, Mission Objectives (Section 3.4), and Mission Requirements (Chapter 4). From a data exploitation perspective, this consolidation is reflected in the definition of its data (Chapter 5), where the mission design enables both scientific analysis and operational applications. Overall, the evolution described in Section 3.6 reflects a more coherent and better aligned mission concept, while continuing to build on the foundations established in the original proposal.

B.3. Criterion 3 - Scientific Feasibility and Maturity

Specification and documentation of observation requirements

The observation requirements are defined and documented in Chapter 4 (Mission Requirements). They specify the required performance in terms of vertical resolution, spatial and temporal sampling, accuracy, and coverage for key Mesosphere–Thermosphere System (MTS) variables, including composition, temperature, winds, and density (Sections 4.2.1, 4.2.2, 4.3). This specification is informed by the scientific motivation (Section 3.1) and the identified knowledge gaps (Chapter 2), ensuring direct traceability from mission objectives to measurement needs. The resulting framework provides a consistent link from scientific drivers to observational implementation, and supports the definition of data products and applications described in Chapter 5.

Traceability of observation requirements to mission objectives

The traceability of observation requirements to the Mission Objectives is explicitly established in Section 4.1, where the required spatial and temporal sampling is defined in direct relation to the observational needs derived from MO.1-MO.4 (Section 3.4). This linkage is further formalised in Table 4.1, which maps key observables, such as composition, temperature, winds, and density, to their corresponding Mission Objectives and required performance levels. Together, Section 4.1 and Table 4.1 ensure a clear and consistent translation from Mission Objectives to measurable observation requirements, supporting the achievement of the Science Goals (Section 3.2).

Problem areas in scientific feasibility and maturity

Potential problem areas in scientific feasibility and maturity are identified and analysed in Chapter 6, with further discussion in Appendix A.1 (in particular in the paragraph “Scientific Risk Analysis”), where the retrieval performance, sensitivities, and associated uncertainties are briefly discussed. These analyses show that achieving the required measurement performance depends on the availability of robust observational constraints and the effective exploitation of the synergy among the Keystone instruments. The identified challenges are directly linked to the current limitations in observational knowledge and process representation described in Chapter 2, in particular the uncertainties in MTS composition and energetics (Sections 2.1-2.2), as well as in multi-scale coupling and variability (Section 2.3) and space weather-related processes (Section 2.4). While these issues do not compromise the overall feasibility, they highlight areas where further validation, uncertainty characterisation, and refinement of the measurement and retrieval approach are required to ensure consistent scientific performance.

Assessment and documentation of mission concept feasibility at SRL 4

The assessment and documentation of the Keystone mission concept at Scientific Readiness Level (SRL) 4 are provided through the feasibility and performance analyses described in Chapter 6, with detailed quantitative support given in Appendix A. These parts of the document demonstrate that the underlying scientific principles, measurement approaches, and retrieval methodologies are sufficiently developed and grounded in existing knowledge, while also identifying key sensitivities and uncertainties. The analyses show that the proposed observation concept is capable of addressing the Mission Objectives (Section 3.4) within the defined mission requirements (Chapter 4), although further validation, calibration, and refinement are required in selected areas. Together, Chapter 6 and Appendix A provide a consistent and documented basis for assessing the scientific feasibility of the mission concept at the end of Phase 0 of SRL 4.

B.4. Criterion 4 - Technical Merit, Maturity and Risk

During the Phase 0 preparatory activities, the consortium defined a system concept capable of fulfilling the Keystone mission requirements with two different THz instrument concepts. The main technical risks and mission-critical elements were identified, and risk-retirement activities were initiated. A technology pre-development plan has been established to mitigate these risks and to raise the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of the critical elements to at least 5 by the end of Phase B1. No technical showstoppers have been identified to date that would prevent proceeding to Phase A.

Satellite and platform

The proposed platform builds on the ongoing Copernicus Sentinel Expansion CO2M mission and the EOS Standard platform and is assessed as capable of accommodating the Keystone payload in terms of mass, power, and data rate. Several subsystems would nevertheless require adaptation to address the specific mission needs, including payload accommodation, thermal needs, limb sounding viewing geometry and the scanning strategy.

Vertical scanning and across-track manoeuvres are implemented at platform level through dedicated Attitude and Orbit Control System (AOCS) modes, with no expected hardware modifications from heritage. Although not considered critical, vertical scanning and co-registration requirements are a key driver for mission objectives and therefore remains a point of attention for Phase A due to its impact on mission performance. None of these adaptations are considered to introduce significant technical risk at this stage. All platform equipment proposed for Keystone are assessed at a TRL not requiring any specific pre-development activities.

Keystone is compatible with Vega-C maximum launch capacity and fits within the fairing envelope. Mass

and volume margins are available to accommodate potential growth during later development phases. The mission also complies with the ESA space debris regulations applicable at the time of writing this report.

Payload

Keystone carries three co-aligned limb sounders operating in the THz, IR, and UV–Vis spectral domains. Each instrument is implemented as an independent instrument with dedicated optical chain, thermal control, detector chains, Data Processing Unit and Instrument Control units. All three are accommodated on a common Instrument Support Panel (ISP) within a dedicated payload bench/module which is mechanically and thermally decoupled from the platform, providing a consistent mechanical reference for the payload elements. The following elements are identified as critical items due to their technological maturity and/or their relevance for the technical and programmatic feasibility of the mission:

- The **THz instrument** builds on heterodyne limb sounder heritage, particularly the JUICE SWI instrument, including Schottky sub-harmonic mixers, multiplier-based Local Oscillator chains and high-resolution digital spectrometers, with a similar telescope and receiver architecture extended to ~ 2 THz. The main critical parameters directly affecting radiometric sensitivity include the receiver short-term gain stability and mixer noise performance, particularly due to the limited maturity of technologies above 1.2 THz. Additional developments are required for 2 THz front-ends (mixers and integrated LNAs), LO multiplier chains and broadband cryogenic LNAs, as well as for digital FFT spectrometers which provide the required spectral resolution but have no space heritage.
- The **IR instrument** relies on established infrared detector and optical technologies with significant heritage from previous Earth observation missions, including focal plane concepts based on PV-MCT and PC-MCT materials. The main critical items concern the detector performance at long wavelengths and the associated thermal requirements, which necessitate cryogenic operation (~ 60 K) to meet radiometric performance. This drives the implementation of a cryocooler system, whose integration, power consumption and induced disturbances represent key constraints, together with the final selection and validation of the focal plane concept.
- The **UV–Vis instrument** is based on high-TRL spectrometer technologies with strong heritage, including concepts derived from OSIRIS, and mature detector solutions. The main critical items are associated with the optical design and radiometric performance, in particular the grating efficiency and straylight behaviour, as well as polarization sensitivity and calibration stability. In addition, demanding SNR at night and dynamic range requirements impose constraints on optical throughput and system configuration, which require further verification.

B.5. Criterion 5 - Programmatics

Scientific Roadmap, Justification and Credibility

Scientific roadmap justification and credibility

A short roadmap toward achieving SRL 5 by end of Phase A is presented in Section A.2 and it provides a pathway based on the performance assessments and sensitivity analyses discussed in Chapter 6. It identifies the key needs for maturation, such as the development of an end-to-end simulator (outlined in Section A.3), validation of retrieval performance, refinement of measurement assumptions, and targeted supporting activities, and links them directly to the Mission Objectives (Section 3.4). The roadmap therefore establishes a credible and justified progression to Phase A, supported by focused studies and preparatory efforts, including potential campaigns.

Identification and discussion of problem areas

Problem areas are identified through the feasibility and performance analyses presented in Chapter 6, supported by an assessments in Appendix A, in particular in the paragraph “Scientific Risk Analysis”. These analyses highlight sensitivities in measurement performance and retrieval accuracy that affect the achievement of the Mission Objectives (Section 3.4) and Mission Requirements (Chapter 4). While these issues do not compromise overall feasibility, they point to areas requiring targeted validation, refinement, and effective use of measurement synergies to ensure robust and consistent scientific performance.

Implementation dependencies and risk of unavailability

The implementation of the Keystone mission concept depends on the coordinated availability and performance of its key system elements, as defined by the observation requirements (Section 4.1) and the feasibility analyses (Chapter 6). In particular, the successful delivery of co-located, multi-instrument measurements relies on the integration and performance of the different payload components, as well as on the robustness of retrieval methodologies and data processing chains (Appendix A), in particular the end-to-end simulator (Section A.3).

Risks of unavailability are therefore primarily associated with potential limitations in measurement performance, incomplete validation of retrieval approaches, or constraints in achieving the required observation coverage. While these risks are mitigated through the design of the measurement concept and the use of complementary datasets, they highlight the importance of continued validation and contingency planning to ensure that the Mission Objectives (Section 3.4) can be achieved under realistic operational conditions.

Technology Pre-development, Development Approach and Schedule

Pre-development plan to reach TRL 5

The pre-development activities foreseen for Phases A and B1 primarily focus on increasing the TRL of the critical elements identified in Criterion 4 (B.4).

First priority activities address the main instrument drivers:

- For the **THz instrument** the pre-development activities include the development and validation of ≥ 2 THz front-end components such as local oscillator chains, sub-harmonic mixers and associated low-noise amplifiers. IF processing chain required the adaptation and qualification of high-resolution digital processing solutions to the Keystone operational environment.
- For the **IR instrument**, the pre-development activities are focused on the focal plane assembly and the associated thermal architecture. In particular, the detector technologies require further development to meet long-wavelength performance, with the current limitations in cut-off representing a critical aspect. This is directly coupled with the implementation and validation of the cryogenic chain, including the cryostat and its interfaces, which is required to achieve the targeted radiometric performance.
- For the **UV-Visible instrument**, the pre-development activities focus on optical performance and instrument-specific adaptations. In particular, the diffraction grating is identified as a critical element at system level, requiring optimisation of efficiency, surface quality and straylight behaviour. In addition, although detector technologies benefit from high heritage, the associated electronics chains (including proximity electronics, data handling and power units) require dedicated design and qualification to ensure compatibility with the Keystone instrument configuration and operating conditions.

Second priority activities would aim to consolidate performance margins and further reduce residual risks:

- For the **THz instrument**, this includes the validation of calibration targets, the optical distribution network and the scaling of heritage telescope and cryogenic architectures to the Keystone frequency range.
- For the **IR instrument**, second priority activities address the optimisation of optical components (including filters and telescope design), calibration sub-systems and their lifetime, as well as interface aspects between the focal plane and associated front-end electronics.
- For the **UV-Visible instrument**, activities focus on the detailed definition of optical coatings, filters and straylight control, as well as the finalisation of instrument-specific electronics and their qualification within the overall system configuration.

The proposed plan is considered suitable to address the identified risks and to achieve the target TRL by the end of Phase B1, provided that sufficient financial resources are available and continuity of work between Phase A and Phase B1 is maintained.

Development approach

Keystone would be implemented through a phased approach across Phases B2/C/D/E1, with the standard formal reviews to verify the status of design, development, procurement, and integration of both development and flight models. The industrial consortium proposes parallel developments conducted by several suppliers at instruments, platform, and satellite level.

For the **THz instrument**, the development approach combines early breadboarding and engineering models for the low TRL receiver chain elements, followed by an EQM/PFM approach for the complete instrument. Emphasis is placed on the early validation of critical subsystems, including the ≥ 2 THz front end, local oscillator chains and spectrometer/Intermediate Frequency processing, to consolidate their performance prior to system-level integration.

For the **IR instrument**, the development approach is focused on the focal plane assembly and thermal chain, with EM and EQM models used to validate detector performance and cryogenic operation. The instrument then follows an EQM/PFM philosophy, allowing the verification of radiometric performance and calibration subsystems before flight model implementation.

For the **UV-Visible instrument**, a conventional development approach is adopted, based on EM/EQM/FM models and building on the high level of heritage. Dedicated models are used to qualify optical components and instrument-specific electronics, ensuring compatibility with the Keystone configuration and verification of radiometric and straylight performance.

At **payload level**, the development approach follows a modular philosophy, with parallel development of the three instruments and the scanning subsystem for the back-up scanning concept. Payload elements are verified at component and instrument level through EM/EQM models, followed by an integrated payload Proto-Flight Model used for system-level qualification. Electrical and functional verification of payload–platform interfaces is performed using engineering models and representative units prior to satellite integration.

At **platform and satellite level**, the development approach and model philosophy are based on the following principles:

- Platform equipment reused without modification is treated as direct Flight Model (FM).
- Equipment requiring modifications would either undergo delta-qualification or be implemented as Proto-Flight Model (PFM).

The satellite PFM would be used to perform thermal, mechanical, and EMC qualification, without the use of Structural Models (SM) or Structural Thermal Models (STM) at platform level. This approach may introduce programmatic risk, as any design issues identified during PFM qualification could directly affect

the flight model. However, if successfully implemented, it also offers the potential benefit of reducing the overall development duration.

Schedule

The Keystone schedule is driven by the development of the instruments. The schedule assumes a Phase B1 to start in Q2 2029 and a Phase B2/C/D/E1 starting in Q4 2030 following the bidding and negotiation phase. Based on such assumptions, a launch in the 2036–2037 timeframe is considered achievable.

Other Programmatic Considerations

Keystone baseline presented in this report is compliant with the relevant ECSS standards applicable to the Earth Explorer programme and with the space debris regulations in force at the time of writing this report. No known International Telecommunication Union (ITU) regulatory issues have been identified. Alternative providers at unit/component level and at instrument level are or would be investigated during Phase A to foster competition and further mature each instrument and related technologies.

During Phase 0, no technical mission showstoppers were identified that would prevent progression to Phase A.